

STUDY ON USE OF E-BOOKS SOFTWARE IN PUBLIC LIBRARY IN WEST BENGAL

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CMJ UNIVERSITY

In partial fulfillment for the award of the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

IN

LIBRARY & INFORMATION SCIENCE

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Declaration

This is to certify that the Thesis entitled “**STUDY ON USE OF E-BOOKS SOFTWARE IN PUBLIC LIBRARY IN WEST BENGAL**” submitted to **CMJ University**, is a partial fulfillment for the award of the Degree of **Doctor Of Philosophy In Library & Information Science** is my unique work under the supervision of **Dr. S. CHANDRAPPA**, Associate Professor, Department of Library & Information Science, CMJ University, Shillong, Meghalaya, India. The thesis has not been submitted before for the award of any degree, diploma or similar title of this or any other University.

Place: Shillong (Meghalaya)

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**STUDY ON USE OF E-BOOKS SOFTWARE IN PUBLIC LIBRARY IN WEST BENGAL**” submitted to CMJ University, Shillong, Meghalaya, India by **ABDUL MUSREF KHAN** for the award of **Doctor Of Philosophy In Library & Information Science** is a record of research work done under my supervision and guidance. This thesis has reached the standards fulfilling the requirements of the regulations for the Degree and it was not previously formed the basis for any other degree or diploma and I additionally affirm that the Thesis speaks of an autonomous work with respect to the Candidate.

Place: Shillong (Meghalaya)

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DEDICATED TO MY GRAND MOTHER

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

CERTIFICATE

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

PREFACE

Chapter No:	Title	Page No
1	CHAPTER-1 Introduction	1-16
1.1	Introduction	5
1.2	Statement of the problem and its significance	12
1.3	Aims and Objectives	13
1.4	Scope and Limitation	14
1.5	Size of Sample	15
1.6	Methodology Adopted	15
1.7	Scheme of Work	16
2	CHAPTER-2 Literature Review	17-35
2.1	Introduction	19
2.2	Review of Previous researches	20
3.	CHAPTER-3 Public Libraries In West Bengal And Their Digitization	36-115
3.1	Introduction	38
3.2	Growth and Development of Public Libraries	40
3.3	Public Libraries in West Bengal	52
3.4	Digital Libraries	81

3.5	Digitization of Public Libraries in West Bengal	86
3.6	Online Public Access Catalogue	93
3.7	E-Books	96
3.8	E-book Software	98
3.9	Types Of Software	100
3.10	Use of E-book Software in Public Libraries in West Bengal	109
4.	CHAPTER-4 Data Interpretation And Analysis	116 – 126
4.1	Introduction	118
4.2	Data Interpretation and Analysis	119
4.3	Suggestion	128
5.	CHAPTER-5 Findings And Conclusion	127 -131
5.1	Findings	129
5.2	Conclusion	130
	References	132 -138
	Appendix-I	139-141
	Annexure I-List Of Publications	
	Published a Paper in International Research journal of Management Sociology Humanities (IRJMSH) ISSN: 2277-9809 (O) Vol 3, Issue 3, November, 2012, Page Nos: 159 -172 Title of the Paper: Library Digitization and Use of E-Books Software in Public Library of West Bengal: A Study	
	Published a Paper in International Research Journal of Commerce, Arts and Science (CASIRJ) ISSN: 2319-9202 (O) Vol 3, Issue 3, October, 2012 Page Nos: 194 -208 Title of the Paper: Study On Use Of E-Books Software In Public Library In West Bengal	

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
3.2	Assistance to libraries covered by RRRLF. (RRRLF/Activities)	50
3.3.1	Government Libraries in West Bengal	63
3.3.2	District-wise distribution of Public Libraries in Undivided Bengal	64
3.3.3	No. of Public Libraries in West Bengal during 1947 – 1977	65
3.3.4	Other Important Libraries	66
3.3.5	Century Old Libraries	75
3.3.6	Government Aided Libraries in West Bengal	80
3.4	DL Time-Line (Sources: Hsinchun and Yilu, 2005)	84
3.10	Software used in Public Library	115
4.1	Library Collection Details of Selected Libraries	119
4.2	User Opted Services	121
4.3	Use of Software	122
4.4	Useful Modules of Software	123
4.5	Difficulties in use of Software	125

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No	Title	Page No
3.1	Distribution of Century Old Libraries in West Bengal	79
4.1	Library Resources	120
4.2	Library Services	121
4.3	Use of Software	122
4.4	Useful Modules of Software	124
4.5	Difficulties in use of Software	125

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Form
CCF	Common Communication Format
CDS/ISIS	Computerized Documentation System Integrated Set of Information System
DBMS	Database Management System
eIFL	Electronic Information for Libraries
GNU: GPL	General Public License
GSDL	Greenstone Digital Library Software
ICT	Information Communication Technology
IDRC	International Development Research Center.
LIBINFO	Library and Information Science Students' Association
MARC	Machine Readable Catalogue
NISCAIR:	National Institute of Science Communication And Information Resources
OA	Open Access
OAI	Open Achieve Initiative
OSS	Open Source Software
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
OPAC	Online Public Access Catalogue
SOPAC	Social Online Public Access Catalogue
UNESCO	United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

PREFACE

This is an era of advancement in technology in each and every field of daily livings. Nowadays we can see technology is being used for most of our daily routine works like we can call a taxi or cab by just clicking on the travelling apps such as UBER and OLA, we can order food and get it delivered at our doorstep within time, technology is also used in home appliances and daily household things like we can turn on or off the lights or fans by just tapping the button of the application software with our mobile. Like these areas the technology is also being applied to our education system to make it easier to learn and understand for people.

This is the golden era of digital in every field. People can access any information regarding anything in the world by just using their mobile phones. Digital enhancement has made learning very easy for the peoples. Nowadays there are many software and websites are available which are providing education online to their user by using mobile phones or computers.

So the technology has also changed the way of reading books. When everything is being digitized then why we stick to the traditional method of studying and reading books which is very crucial nowadays when life is on the run. We cannot carry books with us everywhere, some boos are small and easy to carry, but what about the books which are thousand pages long and hard bind. So here comes the technology which completely changes the way of reading books and make it very easy to carry books anywhere and read them anytime. This technology is named as E-BOOKS, which are a soft copy version of the original hard bind physical books. And to read these soft copy books the software used is called e-book reader.

E-Books are the PDF (Portable Document Format) files which can be stored in computer memory or in mobiles and to read these pdf files many pdf readers are available in the market. The best and the very popular PDF reader is Adobe Acrobat developed by a company named Adobe.

Nowadays, most of the libraries are also adopting the digitalization of traditional library system. They are also providing mobile access of their books to their users by storing their books' pdf version. They are making pdf version of each and every books, journals, print media, research papers, newspapers, thesis, national and international documents, maps etc. So that user can access them from anywhere.

A digital library is a sorted out gathering of assets of any kind, made open to a characterized network for reference or getting. The present innovative progression has changed customary libraries into a digital library framework, where reports and substance of different types can be put away in digitized arrange and can be recovered all the more effortlessly. The manual techniques for library administration has been supplanted by software driven computerized frameworks to control membership, acquires, book issues, new passages, participation and so forth. Since a digital library offers more stockpiling extension, substance can likewise be as e-books, e-magazines, sounds, recordings, PPT or some other multi-media based data. Current digital libraries are storehouses of mass substance, put away as digital items to make them promptly referable. This thesis provides a study on the use of e-books software in public libraries in West Bengal. The study was undertaken by studying the different websites of online public libraries of West Bengal. which use one or the other e-books software. Some of these e-books software are: Alice for Windows, Virtua, Techlib Plus, Libsys, Granthalay, Maitreyi, Sanjay, DELMS, Librarian, WYLYSYS, DELDOS, TLMS, Libsuite, DSpace, Greenstone, NewGenLib, EPrints, Atrium, Insignia Library System, Density Library Manager, Koha and many more. New data made accessible through library locales utilizing e-books software include: Pictures, Theses, Research Papers, Book Chapters, Patents, Annual Reports, Videos/Audios, PPTs, Rare books, Institutional productions, Book Cart office, and so on. E-books Software have additionally influenced libraries to encounter all the

more intriguing by encouraging self-transferring/downloading of reports and client communication on the web. E-books Software have additionally been instrumental in advancing asset sharing other than filling in as an apparatus to librarians to build up their IT abilities.

Thus when the libraries in India and specially in West Bengal adapting digitalization very rapidly we realize that we must perform a dense study on digital library of West Bengal public libraries and find out the use of E-book Software in these public libraries. The topic “Study on use of e-books software in public library in West Bengal” has been undertaken by the investigator. The present study has been divided into Six chapters as follows:

Chapter-1: Introduction.

Chapter-2: Literature Review.

Chapter-3: Public Libraries in West Bengal and Their Digitization.

Chapter-4: Data Interpretation and Analysis.

Chapter-5: Findings and Conclusion.

References and Appendix

Publications

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CHAPTER: 1
INTRODUCTION

CHAPTER - 1

INTRODUCTION

- 1.1 Introduction**
- 1.2 Statement of the problem and its significance**
- 1.3 Aims and Objectives**
- 1.4 Scope and Limitation**
- 1.5 Size of Sample**
- 1.6 Methodology Adopted**
- 1.7 Scheme of Work**

1.1 Introduction

A Public Library is the finished result of man's battle against syndication and centralization of human information in the hands of few. The idea of democratization of learning came in the Nineteenth Century England as a result of long renaissance movement.

From antiquated mud tablet storage facility to the new age digital library this change was not straightforward and simple and took around 2500 years to cover the way. Library is one of only a handful couple of most established foundations that still survive. Amid days of yore libraries went about as support of human progress.

Amid Vedic time in India information spread process used to be oral and must be put away in human memory yet when man improved letters in order attempted to record his procured learning and astuteness about God, nature and other human species. His feeling and sentiments from this time forward would be brought down on accessible medium that could be safeguarded for children. That storage facility of all collected shrewdness would be called library and the antiquarians followed such libraries in Asyria before the introduction of Christ (BC 668 – 26). The Asyria library saved on dirt – tile books as cut and engraved mud tiles were utilized as composing medium. At that point papyrus sheets supplanted dirt tablets. Amid the Roman Period the considerable Alexendria Library in Egypt had 500,000 moves of Papyrus sheets. With the fall of Roman Empire, the library was obliterated.

In India, handled palm leaves or banana leaves were utilized as composing medium till the late eighteenth century. Hand-made papers were utilized despite the fact that palm leaf paper turned out to be exceptionally famous and all incredible Indian written works were scripted on palm clears out. Libraries came well before the printed books. There were storage facilities of contents at each religious community, church, sanctuary and theological college. A library was a pride ownership of the Kings and Nawabs. Indeed, even individual researchers would get contents for their own research and research. A

researcher like Huen Tsang would cross the distance from china to India looking for academic contents. Atish Dipankar and Raja Rammohun Roy attempted brave trek to Tibet, a forbidden state looking for contents put away in cloisters or in private ownership.

As books were kept under reconnaissance in the private libraries keeping them far-off of average citizens, there was likewise ask among some private people for individual book gathering outside the religious communities. Books were stolen, plundered and even obliterated. The remote trespassers at the principal opportunity would assault libraries to wipe out the last remnants of Country's way of life and astuteness. They would pulverize books and sanctuaries and would plunder treasures. As a rule the researchers escape their nation with some significant books in their ownership for security. The Vaisnabites escaped a similar route from Bengal to Vrindaban with colossal compositions despite Muslim attack. At the point when constantepole tumbled to the Turks the occupant Greeks traveled to Italy with heap of books and their inventive brains abandoning everything. That brought forth European Renaissance after 1453.

Albeit sorted out libraries were under the control of predominantly religious foundations on the opposite side private libraries jumped up amid the original copy time (fourteenth century) the desires for private book accumulations prospered outside the cloisters. School and colleges in Europe set up their own particular libraries. Proficient copyists developed to duplicate contents legitimately or furtively. Some would commission unique scholars to compose for them only. Book exchange distinctive frame existed and people who required would purchase contents from that market. Be that as it may, from that point forward some private accumulations turned into a piece of present day library. In India all Rajas and Zaminders had such smaller than normal to sizeable libraries in their castles. At the point when Tipu Sultan of Hyderabad was crushed by the British, his important library was pulled down and all books were acquired Kolkata and were given to Fort William library and halfway to the Asiatic Society Library. Amid Tipu's opportunity imported printed books were accessible. Printing press for business printing arrived at India just toward the finish of eighteenth century yet printed books used to be transported in from Europe. Tipu's library gotten to countless books and original copies.

Numerous original copies would have been gathered by private authorities using any and all means. Till today numerous Indian families had compositions acquired from their precursors as family treasures.

In Europe numerous private gatherers set up their important libraries for example Sir Thomas Bodley's. Bodleyan Library was an amazing private accumulation of books by a solitary man – that is presently an autonomous library at Oxford.

In Bengal excessively private accumulations of huge Rajas, Zaminders and of numerous famous people presently incorporate numerous public library racks. I can give at-least two occurrences from my visit to West Bengal libraries. Zaminder Joykrishna Mukherjee of Uttarpara assembled a radiant royal residence to house a public library on the Ganges. A comparative wonderful house came upon the gave arrive on the bank of the Hooghly at Bally – the whole building cost was borne by the nearby upper class.

At the point when the public library movement achieved crescendo many liberal people appeared to help a public library in their region. A considerable lot of those libraries have now crossed their centennial year. People helped them develop block to block and felt pride to connect themselves with their development and improvement. In India volumes of significant private accumulations of the Maharajas, Zaminders and erudite people were given to class/school or public libraries. Amid the main portion of the nineteenth century a call was given to give books to Calcutta public library. Numerous reacted to that call.

Every public library in India was advanced by such private gifts of books. Beneficiaries of numerous book gatherers gave their whole library with log stock and barrel. Not just books public library movement in India achieved so high a pitch that numerous even gave the whole house to a public library. Around 60 percent Public Library buildings amid the 19 – twentieth century were based on given land.

The utilization of e-books have expanded drastically finished the most recent couple of years (Zickuhr et al, 2012). This has been driven by the advancement of e-Readers and other digital perusing gadgets, which have made access to e-books less demanding for the overall population (Richardson and Mahmood, 2011). Accordingly e-books have been conveyed to the consideration of the general population making an ascent popular. Open libraries have been slower to add e-books to their index than scholarly libraries (Ashcroft, 2011). There are various explanations behind this, including distributing and mechanical issues, which are talked about in the writing analyzed underneath. This thesis mainly focused on performing a detailed study on public libraries in West Bengal to find out how these public libraries are using the e-book reading Software and which software is widely used in most of the public libraries. This research also aims to find out the pros and cons of digitalization of public libraries in West Bengal and also provide knowledge of how easy or difficult is to use the available e-book reading Software in public libraries.

This research thesis on e-books and their reading software is to perform a study on libraries, their staff and their reactions to e-book execution (Kelsey, 2012; Moyer and Thiele, 2011) and the use of e-book software in these public libraries. Library benefactors are a critical gathering which is by and large generally overlooked. Open libraries should present e-books as the interest for them in their locale increments. As more individuals wind up mindful of e-books, and as the cost of the innovation falls, request expands (Duncan, 2011). The ebb and flow look into distinguishes straightforward entry as one of the primary issues for e-book clients (Ashcroft 2011). By far most of the exploration on this theme has been done abroad, as is apparent in the writing surveys by Moyer and Thiele (2011) and Linda Ashcroft (2011).

Printed books multiplied in European market by the later piece of fifteenth century. That realized a progressive change in public personality. Books out of the blue were made accessible to the scope of public yet even the renaissance Europe needed to sit tight for three hundred years for achieving books to public. News papers were entrenched by the turn of eighteenth century. Be that as it may, public library in England came just in 1850. In the mean time books were by and large gathered by the libraries claimed by

Cathedrals, Colleges and Private Collectors. However the messages of social change were scattered through books. Be that as it may, the general people could barely stand to purchase books. The ordinary citizens needed to hold up till the second 50% of the nineteenth century to approach the store of books at free of cost or at ostensible cost. A library for the people and by the people came into reality just amidst the nineteenth century.

The public library is an idea in light of humanist vote based hypothesis. The heroes of public library movement would put stock in democratization of information and people's entitlement to know. This idea planted seed of all other human rights that currently cover all mankind with the seal of the UN. Appropriate to Information and ideal to Education radiate from the privilege to Knowledge, the essential theory of public library.

The Public Library made an incredible effect on human personality and human culture. With the headway of human advance, Books multiplied and through books millions got instructed. Instruction realized further changes. The principal change was the adjustment in the attitude. Humankind presently gained intensity of thinking and the estimation of soundness and they never again would submit to superstition and fanaticism.

Along these lines the scattering of information among the people in snappiest conceivable time was made conceivable through printed books. Dissimilar to original copy, printed learning would no more be conceivable to keep covered up under the area of the congregation or under private ownership by a couple. Learning presently could be diffused to the millions because of the open access Public Library. Syndication on learning was split down. Another world request was introduced distinctive parts of the world with the new contemplations. Books rise above articulations of social movement and ethos of human advancement.

At that point a significant sizeable number of politically and socially cognizant Indian nationals were set up to acknowledge anything that assistance them promote their insight deductively socially and mentally. Interests in different orders had just been developed by the understudies of Hindu College. Under the capable administration of Raja Rammohun Roy a sizeable gathering among the Calkatans ended up keen on advance instruction. So

they figured a public library would convey some natural air to them. A gathering of English talking adolescents as of now rose in Calcutta who were the results of Hindu College and would be quick to peruse more books in English. Such huge numbers of them progressed toward becoming individuals from Calcutta Public Library.

By the turn of twentieth century the flexibility movement achieved its higher top in India, the devoted understudies discovered two crucial focuses to help the public library movement. Right off the bat, the library as a social association stayed self-ruling, a non-administrative establishment where a future pioneer of the nation could put his/her first engraving of initiative. Association in public library activity helped adolescents create socio-political administration aptitude and sorting out capacity. Public library used to breed ground for future pioneers. Also, a library gives degree to proceeding with instruction on plenty of subjects. Libraries would store adequate number of energetic written works and even restricted books were accessible furtively. So public libraries were to offer the two openings and difficulties to many. Besides, amid the Raj numerous Indians changed their fortune by getting to be business visionaries.

Perceiving that the Libraries' targets are to disperse information as generally as could reasonably be expected; fill in as a noteworthy vehicle to encourage production of new learning; encourage ideal utilization of learning by all divisions, for example, government, industry, provincial segment and common society; and guarantee that people from all segments and all parts of the nation have simple access to learning applicable to their necessities, in their own particular dialect; the Working Group on Libraries makes the accompanying suggestions.

Perceiving that the Libraries' destinations are to

- disperse information as generally as could be expected under the circumstances;
- fill in as a noteworthy vehicle to encourage formation of new learning;
- encourage ideal utilization of information by all areas, for example, Government, industry, rustic segment and common society; and
- guarantee that people from all divisions and all parts of the nation have simple access to learning significant to their requirements, in their own dialect;

The Working Group on Libraries makes the accompanying proposals.

Calcutta Public Library was set up in 1836. The Imperial Library was established in 1891 and was formally opened to general society on 30 January 1903 at Metcalf Hall, Kolkata. The points and goals of the Imperial Library were all around characterized in a Notification in the Gazette of India. The strategy of procurement extensively clung to by the Imperial Library was plot by Lord Curzon in his discourse at the initiation.

After Independence the Government of India changed the name of the Imperial Library to the National Library, with the establishment of the Imperial Library Act, 1948, and the accumulation was moved from the Esplanade to the present Belvedere Estate. On first February 1953, the National Library was opened to the general population, by Maulana Abul Kalam Azad. The principal official site of the National Library (www.nlindia.org) was propelled on 22 January 2002.

Library sellers have stepped toward making their product social with the appearance of personalization includes in their items. The present sites enable clients to cooperate with each other and to make and offer content. Sites, similar to Web 2.0, Library 2.0, Library Thing, Face-book, and Flickr interface clients with each other and empower them to stay in contact and talk with each other on the web. Clients present photographs and recordings on these destinations where they can include labels, remarks, and notes without anyone else and each other's things. Individuals from LibraryThing make an inventory of books that they have pierced, or are keen on, and can audit, rate, and label books as well as observed what other Library Thing individuals possess similar books. Social sites unite divergent clients paying little respect to their geographic area, encouraging associations among individuals who have comparative interests (e.g. www.ravelry.com/ for the individuals who like sewing and knitting), proficient associations (e.g. www.linkedin.com/), or who simply need to share data and have online discussions (Trainor, 2009). Till today, we know about OPAC, yet now web OPAC, Social OPAC (SOPAC) and so on are assuming essential part to recover required data and intelligent interface.

Software incorporates the electronic program applications that enable the equipment to play out an arrangement of capacities, for example, following flow or inventorying (Cohn, 1998).

An arrangement of charge is known as program, and an arrangement of program is known as software. The equipment works based on an arrangement of projects of software (Sharma, 1993). Essentially, software is the program that runs the PC to deliver the required outcomes. It is said that, "A PC without software is like a man without his cerebrum, or a library with neither books nor administrators". Hence, on guideline, the determination of software precedes equipment. The creator underlined the software required for library housekeeping schedules and data recovery benefits in detail (Malik, 1994).

A Software bundle can have at least one PC projects to take care of a particular issue. A software dialect gives an uncommon kind of language structure and sentence structure to the software engineer to empower him to give directions in a basic and justifiable way. Composing projects and creating software bundles includes extraordinary preparing, diligent work, time and cash. For creating in-house software to take care of complex issues these prerequisites end up serious and unmanageable. Because of these confinements, the rehearsing bookkeepers or data researchers are going for business software bundles rather than in-house created ones.

Software is the one of the fundamental parts of the PC framework. It is the principle segment that makes the PC to control information. Software is an arrangement of projects that decide the preparing of the PC. Without software the PC is only a machine. Software is the primary interface between the machine and man. It is in charge of the handling either numerical or sensible information. Presently a wide horde of software are accessible for various utilizations of the library.

Computerization of library and data administrations includes non-numeric information preparing, content recovery, and control of series of characters. Data can be utilized for these reasons and for particular needs, unique reason software are likewise accessible in the market. The different classes of such software and their highlights are: Basic software

for information section, approval, arranging, converging of documents, and altering of information.

Word handling software to control content stockpiling, review, utilize and alter; arrangement of edges, expansion and cancellation of series of characters, control passages and so on.

Database administration frameworks (DBMS) are for creation and administration of databases, record administration frameworks, social database administration frameworks (RDBMS), organize and various leveled DBMS. Content recovery bundles for capacity and recovery of non-numeric record (forbidden and even illustrations). These are independent software, require least contribution of PC pros, records are autonomous of variable length for normal dialect, content, approach information by setting, reversed document get to, UIs which makes them basic and simple to utilize. These join hunt and ordering offices and other vital highlights.

Software can likewise be related with seeking on the web recovery framework and CD-ROM databases. Major online frameworks have their own particular software generally written in order dialect, which give access to outer databases. They likewise give private or individual document office and allow altering of pursuit records on micros.

West Bengal Public Library Network starts its balance by giving library office at the entryway advance of the clients, who needs different sorts of data. Any client can approach the system whenever with the assistance of a PC terminal. The State Central Library of West Bengal which is handled by the Directorate of Library Services, Department of Mass Education Extension and Library Services is the zenith Library in the system. The District Libraries are likewise part of this electronic system.

Some of the important public libraries of Bengal are - State Central Library (Kolkata, Established in 1956), Kolkata Metropolitan Library (Kolkata, Established in 1980), Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library (Hooghly, Established in 1859), North Bengal State Library (Coochbehar, Established in 1870), Govt. Central Library (Darjeeling, Established in 1961), District Library, Uttar Dinajpur (Uttar Dinajpur, Established in

2004) and others. The oldest district library of West Bengal is BURDWAN UDAYCHAND LIBRARY, which was established in 1954-55 in the heart of the town with two storied building.

The study was undertaken by studying the different websites of online public libraries of West Bengal which use one or the other e-books software. Some of these e-books software are: Alice for Windows, Virtua, Techlib Plus, Libsys, Granthalay, Maitreyi, Sanjay, DELMS, Librarian, WYLYSYS, DELDOS, TLMS, Libsuite, DSpace, Greenstone, NewGenLib, EPrints, Atrium, Insignia Library System, Density Library Manager, Koha and many more. New data made accessible through library locales utilizing e-books software include: Pictures, Theses, Research Papers, Book Chapters, Patents, Annual Reports, Videos/Audios, PPTs, Rare books, Institutional productions, Book Cart office, and so on. E-books Software have additionally influenced libraries to encounter all the more intriguing by encouraging self - transferring/downloading of reports and client communication on the web. E-books Software have additionally been instrumental in advancing asset sharing other than filling in as an apparatus to librarians to build up their IT abilities.

1.2 Statement Of The Problem And Its Significance

Articulation is the key sentence of the research issues based on which research is done and strong contentions are produced. The announcement of the issue portray the foundation of the investigation, its hypothetical premise and hidden suspicions and the issues in solid, particular and serviceable inquiries.

The library professionals are fit in with questions like:

- Are the library professionals intrigued to make strides in initiative of digitization of public library and find use of e-book software handy?
- To find out the problems of using e-book software in West Bengal public libraries.
- Are the users extremely intrigued to get information as quick as could with the help of E-book Software?

The response to the above expressed inquiries cannot be uniform and in that capacity are fluctuated and very total. The contentions to these inquiries, no doubt will rely on a few circumstances which change from library to library.

Library is a not-for-profit association confronting bunches of imperatives like budgetary abridgements, declined client base, deficiency of prepared labor, insufficient space, absence of expert energy and work culture and so forth. Every one of these prompts productive and powerful utilization of labor inside librarian's restrictions, consequently digital library initiatives would be the main reasonable answer for control the immense measure of bibliographic information rose out of publication postpone data blast and data flood. The present study in this way will be sober-mindedly huge for the accompanying reasons.

- It intends to do a research study in the case of existing public libraries accessible digitally anywhere can be considered for the use of E-book Software.
- Aim to provide a complete study of digital public libraries which are using e-book Software in West Bengal.

The proposed result can be utilized by library organizers, leaders and managers including National Library on India, District Libraries on West Bengal and other public libraries in West Bengal as a parameter for finding the use of E-book Software in public libraries.

Subsequently, the estimation of the announcement of the present research, “Study on use of e-books software in public library in West Bengal” cannot be overlooked.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

In each social study there must be particular points and targets for which the examination is to be led. An examination has no significance with no unequivocal points. The primary objective of the present study is to make investigation into the present state of use of E-book Software in public libraries in West Bengal.

- To make an assessment of the existing status of public digital library facilities in West Bengal.
- To assess the present state of the use of the E-book Software in Public libraries in West Bengal.
- To identify the use of different e-book software in public libraries of West Bengal.
- To find out the features available in different e-book software those are being used in public libraries of West Bengal.
- To prepare the comparative statement of different e-book software of public libraries.

1.4. Scope and Limitations of the Study:

Before taking our research study at next level, it is exceedingly fundamental to decide its degree and its restrictions which will be useful for convenient fruition of the examination. On the off chance that the limit of research isn't predetermined, it ends up troublesome with respect to the agent to work in a logical way. The scope and limitations of the present study therefore has been restricted only to the study of the current status of use of E-book Software in West Bengal public libraries. However the present study has kept the following limitations in its scope.

The present study includes only those public libraries of West Bengal which are digital and have their collection available in e-book format for finding out the use of e-book software in these public libraries. This study tries to unfold the current state of use of existing E-book Software in West Bengal public libraries which have already been digitized and using any type of available e-book software for accessing the e-book collection of their books.

Software

- DSPACE
- KOHA
- LIBSYS

Library:

- Central Library - The University of Burdwan
- The Asiatic Society Library
- The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library
- Indian Statistical Institute Library
- Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library

1.5 Size of Sample:

Research study for public benefit primarily based with the social phenomena. It studies the behavior of human being as a society and their response and attitude under different circumstances. The quality of any investigation and its timely completion primarily depends upon the size and quality of sample included in the study. Thus the role of sample in this research is quite significant.

The present research study '*Study on use of e-books software in public library in West Bengal*' is done by visiting the available website link of digital libraries of West Bengal on the official website of West Bengal National Library- West Bengal Public Library Network.

1.6 Methodology Adopted:

Research methodology essentially indicates the way decided for achieving the objective on result, conclusion or speculation. It is a studious request and examine or basic and thorough examination or experimentation having for its point, the revelation and their right translation. Strategy basically supports a constant research for information and comprehension.

For the gathering of information in social research, there are different systems or strategies are received. For the most part, the survey strategy, perception strategy, contextual analysis technique, basic occurrence procedure and Diffusion contemplate system and so on are the few for acquiring data. For the present examination, the accompanying strategy and methods are taken after:

- Questionnaire method for obtaining librarians and users opinions and for collection of information and data relevant to the research topic.
- A survey method is followed to study several public libraries which are digital and using any type of available e-book software in their library on selection basis both from West Bengal district and Non-District libraries such as national Digital Library, National Library Kolkata, Burdwan Public Library etc.

The present investigation consists of public libraries of West Bengal that are using e-book software.

1.7 Scheme of Work

The scheme is a skeleton or blue print of the research work that has followed systematically during the period of investigation. For the sake of clarity and logical relevance which deals the entire spectrum of its investigation, the present study divided under five broad chapters:

CHAPTER: 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

CHAPTER - 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

2.2 Review of Previous Researches

2.1 Introduction

Review of literature related to this topic is most important part of this thesis and very important for a researcher who is willing to do a research in the same area. Review and study of the literature work related to the topic of public library is mainly to discuss, evaluate, reactions and results of the researchers who have carried out similar research in the field of digital public libraries in West Bengal.

To carry out any research study, a researcher must have necessary understanding and appropriate knowledge with the previous research works that has already been completed in the field of his/her selected research topic. Thus reviewing of related research literature provides an opportunity to the researcher to familiarize himself/herself with the current understandings and knowledge in the area or field of his/her choice of research with the available results of these researches, which can be very useful to start or forward his/her research.

Literature Review of previous researches in the same area in any research satisfies following purposes:

- It empowers new researchers to get him/her familiar with the possible hurdles and difficulties in the topic of their research.
- It gives a clear cut picture about the accountable work done in the field of his/her research by the existing or forgoing researchers and the degree to which equivalent research work has been done and the notable or extendable point of the research from which he/she should carry forward his/her research work.
- It assists the researcher to steer clear of unexpected and unwanted errors and duplication of previously developed satisfactory research findings also unfruitful problem areas which may demonstrate repetitive later.
- The literature review of previous work likewise gives the researcher a viable comprehension of the examination technique directed and in addition the entrenched standards of social research.

- It empowers the researcher to comprehend the genuine imperatives and issues experienced by the past researchers while doing their exploration on the given field so that, the present specialist receives fundamental advances, methodologies, procedures including evolving his/her way to guarantee his examination issue free.
- Such survey likewise assist the researchers with checking their discoveries, derivations', conclusions and feelings with that of the discoveries of the past researchers so that, validness and dependability of the outcome can be streamlined.

E-book software is considered as an imperative issue for libraries. In any case, just few quantities of studies have been found on the point of e-book software for libraries. More in particular, in setting of West Bengal, no examinations have been completed on e-book software for Library Automation/Management. In any case, it doesn't imply that no examination has been done on the point in light of the fact that there are a few researchers, creator or then again researchers at the universal level who have said a certain something or the other in connection to the e-book software for library digitization.'

2.2 Review Of Previous Researches

In this research study, the researcher has discussed various sources of the previous research works done in the same research area, in both hardcopy or softcopy versions of the research so as to find out the related literature work on the topic of his/her research. A handful of related literature work were collected from many different journals, conference papers and proceedings, websites of libraries, e-journals, bibliographies, digital archives, etc. and were then reviewed very carefully in a most appropriate systematic order. Some of the literature writing inspected that merit specify are as under:

Richvalsky and Watkins (1996) in their paper on “Design and Implementation of a Digital Library” characterize digital library and portray the outline and usage process which they have followed in their association in making digital library. They additionally recommended some key outline issue engaged with making a digital library, for example, equipment, software, database openness, web index, dialects and so on. Various issues that should have been represented while making a digital library and the most imperative issues are security and adaptability. In the event that a site isn't anchor, critical information can without much of a stretch be lost or adulterated. Another imperative issue is keeping up the nature of the information in the digital library.

Hasting and Tennant (1996) in their publication “How to Build Digital Libraries” bring up that digital libraries require to choose, gain, sort out make available and save digital accumulations. They underline digital administrations must be arranged, actualized and preparing be bestowed for the new assignments and obligations that digital libraries request. Based on proposition put together by University of California, Berkeley library foundation of digital library advancement of instruction USA, the organization has prepared library data researcher, gallery and document experts in digital library issues and methods.

Rashid (1996) audited on "Library Automation an Overview" the significant advancements in the zone of library automation, measure, library management framework, and information recovery framework, OPAC, CD-ROMs and systems administration. Further, he gathered that librarians and merchants are working into a single unit to enhance administration and frameworks and grow new items because of client needs.

Chapman and Kenney (1996) in their paper “Digital Conversion of Research Library Materials: A Case for Full Information Capture” they advocate a methodology to pick ask about materials in light of their insightful regard and to describe specific necessities for audit change to cutting edge picture shape in perspective of their educational substance.

In a rapidly advancing world, the primary report is the base variable and building automated assembling to be profitable as far as might be feasible.

Hulser (1997) described in his paper, “Digital library: Content Preservation in a Digital World” that the data administrations pattern and bearings that develops this point took after by a portrayal of IBM digital library and its segments that empower organizations to adequately address their digital substance administration issues. The investigation likewise incorporates the coordinated capacities or making, catching, looking and getting to, circulating, putting away and overseeing and additionally rights administration.

Satyanarayana and. Rath (1997) in the article entitled “Digital Libraries-their Perception and Use”, the researchers talk about different parts of digital libraries. They clarified that a digital library is a library of digital archives ancient rarities and records. The presumptions fundamental the plan of digital libraries, their utilization in data get to and the unmistakable part the digital libraries play in educating and learning are likewise talked about by the creators. They have likewise brought up that real issues like protected innovation, copyright and the entrance to electronic data.

Cleveland (1998) in his study in “Digital Libraries Definition Issues and Challenges” expressed that the development or digital libraries brought forth the equal expressions of digital library like virtual library electronic library and library without dividers. He additionally characterized the idea or digital library and talked about the real issues and difficulties in making digital library.

Smith (1999) in his article: “Why Digitize” he brings up numerous issues. As indicated by the creator, digital records won't and cannot supplant simple archive. To change over everything in digital shape would not be right. He expressed that to make simple materials more open the transformation as well as through digital restricting guides and connected database or pursuit apparatuses. Digital tiles can give additional conventional access to data. Digital innovation can in fact end up being a volume instrument to upgrade learning and stretch out the exploration data assets to the individuals who look

for them. All in all, the creator expresses that digital innovation can be extra toolbox rather a substitution for the built up simple media.

Airy, Salmon (1999) has exhorted "the most recent pattern of library proficient is certifiably not a gigantic gathering of materials however of 'paperless library' and a la mode library as opposed to being 'record rich' flourishes to be 'get to rich'. For such rich access to data, computer is a fundamental apparatus to be utilized. It will be smarter to computerize all libraries exercises and services in certainty since library digitization will get great outcome in more noteworthy precision, quick, handling, organizing controls, quality administration, and notoriety of library."

Sangam and Leena. (2000) in their paper "Digital Library Services in Information Services in a Networked Environment in India" specifies the importance and meaning of digital library and gives its targets, characters and portrays the distinctive administrations gave by digital library. Additionally draw the consideration of different boundaries in the advancement of the digital library.

Hanif, Uddin (2000) in his paper "The role of rural libraries in the rural development of Bangladesh" has underlined the part of country libraries in each and each town of Bangladesh. These are: i) To inform the rustic individuals for better wellbeing, water supply and sanitation, ii) To mindful about government arrangements, iii) To help better products, iv) To inform about ecological contamination. The investigation investigated the bury linkages amongst libraries and rustic improvement and likewise featured some provincial parts of the nation.

Bhardwaj and Sukla (2000) characterized the library digitization as a bland term used to indicate the different exercises with an enhancing nature of items and services of library and data focuses. It upgrade the speed, profitability, sufficiency and effectiveness of the library proficient staff and spare the labor to evade some normal, dull and administrative assignments, for example, recording, arranging, writing, duplication checking and so on.

Biradar (2000) contemplated the part of provincial libraries in meeting the information needs of agriculturists especially in Kerala. The poll and meeting techniques were utilized for gathering the important information from the libraries and 1000 ranchers. The examination recommends that librarians had persuaded the agriculturists about the importance of libraries and accessibility of perusing materials and satisfactory gathering was not accessible in rustic library.

Jeevan (2001) in his article, “Indian Library Need for Incremental Progress towards Digital Libraries” ordered Indian libraries into frame age as first second, third and fourth basing on IT framework in libraries. In this exploration paper he examined some essential activities and significant obstacles, issues and prospects for usage in the Indian setting.

Malwad (2001) in his provocative article, “digital libraries: present past and features” talked about definition and notable highlights of digital libraries. He additionally depicted digital library includes by featuring continuous undertakings at IISC, Bangalore and IBM digital library.

Parekh (2001) in her commitment to CALIBER 2001 conference “Digitization: an over View of Issues” starts her research discussion with the idea and importance of digitization and the procedures engaged with the digitization and spotlight on digitization of print materials instead of articles, sound film or video chronicles.

Arora (2001) in his research on “Building of Digital Libraries: An Overview” underscores digitization procedure of print materials. He clarifies working of digital accumulation and the foundation required to get to them is a test that each library needs to manage. The article revels into mechanical advancement Cultural Revolution and substance improvements that prompted transformation in development and advancement and digital libraries.

Kiran and Babu (2001) in their research paper on topic “Digital Asset Preservation with Reference to Archival Materials” talk about the digitization procedure of print materials. He clarifies working of digital accumulation and the foundation required to get to them is a test that each library needs to manage. The article reveals into mechanical advancement Cultural Revolution and substance improvements that prompted transformation in development and advancement and digital libraries.

Nithyanandam (2001) in his research study “Infrastructure for Digital Management A case Study for Pondicherry Engineering College” features the activities under taken at Pondicherry building College library with particular reference to the advancement of foundation for digital resource administration.

Narssimhan (2001) made a valuable research study on “Infrastructure for Digital Management Modern Impact of Electronic Media” talked about digital partition issues, archive administration frameworks, digital protection and its necessities. The innovative plausibility for digital administration has been clarified to sum things up alongside relocation procedure setting movement and digital partition.

Jayamani (2001) portrayed the profundity arranging of digitization in the paper “A Model of Digital Library for the TN Dr. MGR Medical University”. It additionally talks about the utility of digital library different goals diverse stages for execution, specialized issues and essential required framework.

Lohia (2001) published a research paper entitled, “Need for Digital Libraries: And Emerging Reality” talked about definition, idea significance require qualities and elements of digital library and furthermore couple of profitable recommendations are given the advantage of digital library.

Sharma, Singh and Ahmad (2001) in their paper “Digital Components in Digital Environments Highlighted in India”, the word digital library has been established even more a vulture than as an innovation application as the greater part of data experts in India do not have the best possible learning with respect to digital libraries. The article has a tendency to clarify the toms and the digital parts of the digital libraries and clarify their working for looking through the correct data.

Sahoo and Rao (2001) in a scholarly research article on “Planning and Designing of a Digital Library” focused on the arranging and outlining of a digital library. It likewise talks about setting or merchandise, labor arranging, settling issues like IPR, the essentials for planning a digital library, procedure of digitization of print, sound and video data recovery perspective creating of web interface and dealing with the regularly developing electronic data assets.

Krishnamurthy (2001) in his paper "Development of computer catalogue at Indian Statistical Institute, Bangalore Centre Library", discussed about Retrospective Conversion ventures of inventories took after by at Indian Statistical Institute, Bangalore Center Library.

Majeed (2001) clarified about social improvement and libraries benefit portfolio for a town library. The paper examined as public library is perceived wherever as a social establishment in our general public, it is as yet where books are issued to its individuals and not very many of our libraries are working as cores to social exercises in their general vicinity. The paper outlined how town librarian in our state can work compelling and likewise rundown of services.

Goswami and Ghosh (2002) embraced a research on “Digital Library Environment Indian Context” talked about the definition rise of digital libraries and change of information to digital arrangement. A short survey of a portion of the Indian libraries introduce part in digital condition and given. The paper additionally depicted the different digitization works in Indian condition and their present situation and digital program is featured.

Ciriac, Deshmukh and Rajlakshmi (2002) directed a research overview on “Digitization of Libraries for Modern Era” clarified the idea digital libraries. The creators underlined that a decent digital library must be legitimately prepared in order to spread the coveted data and furthermore to get to it out of the digital stockpiling media. The reason for digitization is to gather, store, arrange and disperse data quickly from one end to the next and tight clamp verse using a PC. They contend that it isn't the PC alone that makes the digital library conceivable, yet digital systems like the web which can be duplicated and disseminated messages the world over in a flash and at an ostensible cost.

Gupta (2002) in a research “Digitization Pros and Cons” featured the quality and shortcoming of digitization in a documented situation and investigate the advantages and disadvantages of digital chronicled material on the world with web and furthermore investigates a portion of the numerous issues associated with choosing and building up a digital authentic gathering.

Bhattacharyya (2002) published a research on “Digital Library : A New Trends in Information Management” manages data methods through dialog on different parts of digital library including definition, needs and reason, capacities, organizing standards and convention, standers procedure of data recovery through web innovation application and protection.

Haggis and Goulding (2003) basically analyzed the public library arrangements for remote networks. It engraves techniques for giving a public library administration to one house stop customer of South Linclon Shires Mobile libraries. The article follow out the four strategies that were chosen for the services which are book via mail, Village shop libraries expanding the house hold services and transporting customer to the library. The investigation featured the issues including social incorporation, best esteem and public library standard which is to be considered while supplanting the loan house stop portable library benefit.

Borse(2004) in his paper "Retrospective conversion of library catalogue: a case study of Library of North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon" said the benefits of Retrospective change and how this university has finished their Retrospective transformation work.

Moyo, (2004) states that data advancements have prompted the change of library services from customary services, for example, card indexes, printed books and periodicals, bibliographic guidelines, inperson/up close and personal reference, to new services and conveyance modes joining: electronic accumulations, for example, e-books, e-diaries and databases; virtual reference services, and other online services. Development of new services that are impossible to miss to the on the web/Web condition is the pattern in current electronic libraries.

Holly (2005) managed the need, difficulties, devices and techniques for library web content administration and gave a few contextual investigations of library sites.

Mullins and Lienha (2005) investigate the initiatives as saw and rehearsed by public library pioneers and focal part of authority in public libraries. The examination plans to explore to pioneers past the national limits with a specific end goal to create understands of the public impression of current pioneers in the field of public librarian send. Meeting techniques was utilized for the present research , where thirty senior public pioneers were chosen for top to bottom eye to eye meet in the three purview. The significant finding of the examination are impression of senior public library pioneers, crosswise over national limits makes theoretical commitments administrations, as well as to visitor writing on perceived initiatives. This investigation features initiatives as the cardinal factor on which every single organizational component depends over all adequacy.

Muir (2005), in his article "An introduction to the open source software issue" followed the issue on Open Source Software (OSS). He portrayed highlights and usage of open source software and what is going on with OSS applications in colleges and other libraries in the western world like USA, Canada, New Zealand and so on. As indicated by

this article, OSS enables developers to modify the software and redistribute it, with the necessity that they roll out these improvements accessible to other designers.

Joint (2006) in his article "Evaluating library software and its fitness for purpose" gave a calculated paper in light of existing software assessment models. The fundamental purpose is to adjust general standards utilized for evaluating software quality to more particular prerequisites normal for information recovery and instructive applications in library situations. It additionally gave a model of software quality which grasps various top level factors. These are usefulness, unwavering quality, ease of use, effectiveness, practicality and movability.

Bathrinarayanan (2006) "Digital Libraries A Boon for Human Services" talks about the general foundation and digital library and open source software (OSS). The paper additionally brought up the criteria can be embraced for digitization of records. Software this paper features what is and OSS, its highlights software permitting preferences and focal points, highlights and capacities and Greenstone.

Semi and Riyahiniya (2006) in their study on "Awareness and User and Digital Resources in the Libraries of Isfahan University or Medical Science Iran" depicted the connection amongst mindfulness and utilization of digital assets among understudies in relevant connection to Isfahan University of restorative science. Results show that 70% understudies know and digital assets accessible in college database however 69% at that point do will in utilizing assets. So also 62% know and disconnected database where as just around 19% utilized them through focal library LAN Network. Around 70% know about online database open by means of focal library site and around 53% of respondents know about focal library book and diaries database where as more than 50% of them 54% have alluded to men planned database, following by 87.2% of the understudies that the accessible digital assets considerably meet their data needs. The examination uncovered that understudies are less intrigued to utilize online database which has credited to variables, for example, inconsistent give introduction and set number of terminals associated with the middle in focal library the investigation unfurls clients are

confronting a few issues like low speed network and deficiency of lacking equipment offices.

Parthasarathi Mukhopadhyay (2006) in his research study "Public Library based Web-enabled Community Information System for Rural Development in India: Designing A FLOSS based Multilingual Prototype" examined about software system for public library based web empower multilingual network information services by using open standard and open source software.

Schaffner (2007) stressed the requirement for good library web interface and online community inventories (OPAC).

Sharma, (2007) found that the majority of the scholastic libraries in West Bengal are utilizing the UNESCO's software CDS/ISIS and WINISIS all the more famously because of its free appropriation. Alternate reasons are accessibility of the preparation gave by numerous preparation establishments and even endorsed in the Syllabus of Master's Degree in Library and Information Science, TU. A portion of the scholarly libraries have utilized neighborhood influenced software to bundle for the digitization. It is likewise discovered that numerous other private school libraries are utilizing basic database just for the record keeping matter which is made by the understudies as an undertaking work. These sorts of database have either housekeeping activities or different offices which may make issue in future by losing its record and investigating the information.

Dinkleman and Stacy-Bates (2007) inspected the accessibility and access instrument of electronic books accessible in the sites of scholarly libraries in the relationship of Research Libraries (ARL) and gave helpful proposals to enhance it.

Satpute (2008) clarified about the part of public library in national advancement. Public library is an organization which cares for the instructive, social, recreational and information needs of the general public and it is thought to be an essential piece of the general public to assume an important part in the dissemination of thoughts and the

inventive utilization of the general public. It portrayed that the public library assume an exceptionally significant part in the national advancement with instructive improvement and to meet the instructive, social and information needs. The paper inferred that social advancement and it firmly identified with the social life, financial and mechanical improvement, Agriculture and country improvement, recreational focus and political cognizance.

Bendhani (2008) has undertaken a survey “Digital Library System : A Need for Emerging Information Society” talked about in this data and electronics age, a digital/virtual library holds a key part in instruction and research in this specific situation, the paper manages the need of digital library framework for the prosperity of the present data society. Taking a gander at the noticeable part. A digital library plays in instructing and taking in the talk and centers upon the issues relating to digital libraries and arrangement thereof and features exceptional consideration towards content creation stockpiling and recovery and so on. The paper additionally contacts upon its belongings or connection with the financial and legitimate issue. The central expectation at the finishing up comment of this paper is to endeavor the need and prospects of digital library and the issues and with recommending some answer for them.

Singh (2008) Studied “Digital Preservation: Why and How” talked about how to digitize the library assets and by what means will they be taken care of, how to manage digital resource and how would you protect a digital resource the choice of software for digitization.

Pyati, Ajit (2008) his article on "Open Source Software and Libraries" inferred that OSS, may not be a remarkable democratizing innovation that huge numbers of its intense backers assert it is. Be that as it may, OSS and the free software development give an opportunity and opening to libraries to re-imagine other options to the strength of corporate, industrialist methods of software advancement. Libraries are participating in these developments, yet more work should be done in seeing how to support these

ventures and in estimating a bigger political voice for libraries in wrangles about mechanical democratization.

Randhawa (2008) portrayed in his article on "Open Source Software and Libraries" that OSS clients can run, duplicate, appropriate, think about, change, share and enhance for any reason. Open source library software's does not require the underlying expense of business software and empowers libraries to have more noteworthy control over their workplace. Library experts ought to know about the upsides of open source software and ought to include in their advancement. They ought to have essential learning about the choice, establishment and upkeep. Open source software requires a more prominent level of figuring duty than business software. Library experts don't contemplate the upsides of open source software for digitization and consequently are hesitant to utilize it.

Kumar, Joshi and Sharma (2008) on their paper "Building Digital Library Using LS Digital" depicted digital library innovations are quickly creating to take into account the data needs of the general public. LS digital is business software for building digital library and an extra" thing to Libsys software and therefore is completely perfect with Libsys. The whole procedure is completely digitized in this way requiring least exertion by the client and mix with Libsys database verifiable. It gives awesome advantages to the client who might have the capacity to seek both digitized and non-digitized library gathering through a typical library OPAC. LS digital backings the capacities like-assets, structure, definition, filtering adaptations, upkeep, PDF change, explore database support, looking and recoveries.

Ratna Bandyopadhyay (2008) in his paper "Information Literacy And Public Library Services In West Bengal, India" assesses the services of the public libraries in West Bengal. It was discovered that clients incline toward the accompanying data proficiency services offered by public libraries: data identified with their occupations, wellbeing and family welfare, employments and vocations. These services are for the most part given through TV programs, varying media materials, data stands and web access to websites. It has been discovered that numerous segments of society have been profited. The paper

also give some directions to acquaint innovative services with make the data education programs more compelling. These proposals for public libraries incorporate giving PC labs web access for preparing to clients in web and PC utilization. Data education projects ought to be removed from the library for detainees, doctor's facility and home-bound patients. Likewise for networks with low proficiency rates data education projects ought to be directed with varying media materials for more noteworthy viability.

The research Paper on "Enhancing Full text Search Capability in Library Automation Package: A Case Study with Koha and Greenstone Digital Library Software" by authors Anuradha and Sivakaminathan (2009) was about issues of digitalization software packages accessible with open source software. They give propelled highlights of looking and recovering of bibliographic records, none of them encourage full content ordering and seeking. The vast majority of the accessible open source digital library software encourages ordering and seeking of full content archives in various configurations.

Library digitization software, incorporating every one of the exercises and schedules of the library is fundamental software for the libraries and is alluded to as Integrated Library Automation Package (ILAP). An ILAP implies an undertaking asset arranging framework for a library, used to track things possessed, orders made, charges paid, and supporters who have obtained the things. At the end of the day it is one where all the library exercises, for example, acquisitions, recording, course, serials, and the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) are digitalized.

There are numerous ILAP accessible in the market that addresses the issues and also spending plans. Notwithstanding, with the open source software development making up for lost time, a couple of open source library computerization bundle (LAP) are likewise accessible, which are practically identical with any business LAP. To give some examples: Koha, Evergreen, OPAL, PhpMyBibli, OpenBook, OpenBiblio. Among these Koha is the primary open source library computerization software and is broadly utilized.

Ratna Bandyopadhyay (2010) in her paper ““Come to your Library”: BLA Project for Promotion of Reading in West Bengal, India” talks about the activities of a couple of public libraries in the locale of Howrah, Kolkata also, South 24 Parganas for advancement of perusing and utilization of library.

Rouknuzzaman, Hasan and Akanda (2011) talked about to recommend a measured way to deal with KM training in the domain of digital library learning and furthermore audit the logical writing of the field and a smaller than normal case investigation of international master in digital management in “A Framework for Knowledge Management Education in Digital Library Learning”. The research talks about developing countries of DL and KM and investigates the present province of DL learning and KM training in library and data science. IT investigations a smaller than expected case and demonstrate that the IKM module of DILL involves measurements of substance, setting, individuals, process and innovation. At long last, this paper proposes a system of KM specialization in the DILL program which comprises of four modules in light of the four noteworthy point of view of KM data innovation, business and human. In any case, DL experts require an extensive variety of aptitudes and capabilities identified with vital administration of data, IT administration, business process administration and human capital administration to work in information serious association like a DL.

Shukla (2011)in his paper “Digitization Practices in India: Issues and Challenges” portrayed the exercises of CDAC Noida and said that CDAC was carrying holography into the digital library wherein CDAC could consolidate content, sound and video together in to the library science language and present a projection framework which couldn't be a level screen session would be a table in onto which a three-dimensional picture would come up. You could snare at it and get more data. Dr. Shukla certified that Dr. Raj Reddy of Carnegie Mellen University once said that in regards to a billion books had been distributed on the planet over and out of them just 15% books were accessible in print today, 85% were either no longer in production or filed some place. On the off chance that this was the circumstance we are unquestionably gaining admittance to only 15% of the accessible books. How might we bring this 15% up to 100% was the test? He included this could be accomplished through digitization of books. There were two stages

to experience one was to make the substance in the digital frame and second was to make meta information for looking through that substance. He noticed that so as to digitize books it is discovered that 15% of them were sans copyright. So under the mission it is discovered that under 20% had particular copyrights and for 65% books copyright subtle elements were not clear. He said that in excess of 18 lakh books put away onto 4c terabyte space on a PC and it's available to the general population.

Dhiman, Anil Kumar and Yasoda (2011) assess the public library in Internet age. The paper talked about the public library which is open by the public and for the most part established from public sources and might be worked by government worker. It demonstrated that public libraries serve assorted networks thoroughly considered the nation they are spread sporadically in India, comprise of State Central Library in each state, District libraries, Urban public libraries at the urban areas and Rural public library at the Village. The libraries are primarily upheld by the state Government and neighborhood specialists and a few times by the Central Government creating organizations. The paper presumed that public library are the method for changing over them in to Knowledge Center and prone to add to long lasting library.

CHAPTER: 3

PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN WEST BENGAL AND THEIR DIGITIZATION

CHAPTER - 3

PUBLIC LIBRARIES IN WEST BENGAL AND THEIR DIGITIZATION

3.1 Introduction

3.2 Growth and Development of Public Libraries

3.3 Public Libraries in West Bengal

3.4 Digital Libraries

3.5 Digitization of Public Libraries in West Bengal

3.6 Online Public Access Catalogue

3.7 E-Books

3.8 E-book Software

3.9 Types Of Software

3.10 Use of E-book Software in Public Libraries in West Bengal

3.1 Introduction

A Public Library is the finished result of man's battle against syndication and convergence of human information in the hands of few. The idea of democratization of information came in the Nineteenth Century England as a result of long renaissance development.

From the earliest starting point, the public library has been accepted as social foundation in light of the popularity based hypothesis "of the general population, by the general population and for the general population". The IFLA/UNESCO Public Library Manifesto 1994 points of interest the ramifications of public libraries as "the nearby entryway to information, gives a fundamental condition to long lasting learning, free basic leadership and social advancement of the individual and social gatherings", and again expressed the impact of public libraries for learning and development as "a living power for training, culture and data, and as a basic specialist for encouraging of peace and otherworldly welfare through the brains of people". On characterizing a public library it might be perceived that, "an association set up, upheld and subsidized by the network, either through nearby, territorial or national government or through some other type of network association. It gives access to learning, data and works of the creative energy through a scope of assets and services and is similarly accessible to all individuals from the network, paying little mind to race, nationality, age, sexual orientation, religion, dialect, inability, financial and business status and instructive achievement". It is as per Dr. S.R Ranganathan, the vicar of Library development in India, public library is, "one which is available to any individual from the public and every year free of any charge paid as so much service".

Indian situation discloses to us that Maharaja Sayaji Rao Gaekward has led complimentary necessary essential instruction supported by libraries in 1883 in the region of Baroda and from there on without precedent for India free public library services were set up as a framework in 1907 and extended to the entire state.

From antiquated earth tablet storage facility to the new age advanced library this change was not straightforward and simple and took around 2500 years to cover the way. Library is one of only a handful couple of most established foundations that still survive. Amid days of yore libraries went about as support of progress. Amid Vedic period in India learning dispersal process used to be oral and must be put away in human memory yet when man improved letter sets attempted to record his obtained information and astuteness about God, nature and other human species.

In India, prepared palm leaves or banana leaves were utilized as composing medium till the late eighteenth century. Handmade papers were utilized despite the fact that palm leaf paper turned out to be exceptionally well known and all extraordinary Indian written works were scripted on palm leaves. Libraries came well before the printed books. There were storage facilities of contents at each religious community, church, sanctuary and theological school. A library was a pride ownership of the Kings and Nawabs. Indeed, even individual researchers would obtain contents for their personal investigation and research. As books were kept under reconnaissance in the private libraries keeping them far-off of average citizens, there was additionally encourage among some private individuals for personal book collection outside the cloisters.

Albeit sorted out libraries were under the control of basically religious foundations on the opposite side private libraries jumped up amid the original copy time (fourteenth century) the desires for private book collections prospered outside the cloisters. School and colleges in Europe set up their own libraries. Proficient copyists developed to duplicate contents legitimately or secretly.

In Europe numerous private gatherers set up their profitable libraries for example Sir Thomas Bodley's. Bodleyan Library was an unbelievable private collection of books by a solitary man – that is presently an autonomous library at Oxford.

In Bengal excessively private collections of huge Rajas, Zaminders and of numerous famous people currently incorporate numerous public library racks. I can give at-least two occurrences from my visit to West Bengal libraries. At the point when the public library development achieved crescendo several liberal individuals appeared to help a

public library in their territory. A considerable lot of those libraries have now crossed their centennial year. Every single public library in India were enhanced by such private gifts of books.

3.2 Growth and Development of Public Libraries

The public library is an idea in light of humanist majority rule hypothesis. The heroes of public library development would have confidence in democratization of learning and individuals' entitlement to know. This idea planted seed of all other human rights that presently cover all mankind with the seal of the UN. Appropriate to Information and ideal to Education exude from the privilege to Knowledge, the essential rationality of public library.

Library during Ancient Period

"The historical backdrop of the advancement of the public library might be said to be as old as that of education in India". Amid Vedic circumstances, the understudies remained in the master gruha for quite a while for education. Since ancient circumstances, India is by and large especially applicable looking for learning and insight. Oral correspondence was the best means among the general population of India and composing was not accessible. "The soonest composed and recorded materials found in India are the engravings on stone mainstays of King Asoka (300 BC); these engravings could be known as the first outside open libraries". (Patel;2004;3). Afterward, Ashrams appeared in India and understudies contemplate under the supervision of understood educators. They kept numerous compositions for utilization of the educators and understudies and additionally for the guests. Numerous understudies joined ashrams and such enormous ashrams were known as Vidyapeeth, where quantities of educators are locked in to instruct the understudies. These educational establishments gathered various compositions and different materials which can help in their instructing and every day schedule. They kept and saved painstakingly. "The perusing materials, obviously, identified with numerous subjects framed the source material for transmitting learning in various floods of education and culture. The accumulations may be compared to modern libraries since they were deliberately kept up and widely utilized by understudies and

instructors alike". Such ashrams or vidyapeeths, where original copies and other perusing materials were saved, might be viewed as a sort of library as they serve data and learning to the understudies and network in various ways. PandeyS K Sharma expressed that; "In India, since the ancient circumstances libraries have been working as beacons for the individuals who needed to peruse and to broaden the limits of different disciplines. References are accessible to demonstrate that Nalanda University (in Bihar) had its own particular multistoried library in 600 AD with monstrous gathering of original copies. The gathering of the library was housed in three structures, each having nine stories and three hundred rooms. This library was opened by the then Emperor of India, King Davapal. The library was open for anyone that was known researcher and appreciated perusing, deciphering and notwithstanding replicating the records kept in the library. Chinese voyager Whuen Sang is known to have counseled this library in the seventh century and to have taken from here many treatises to China and Japan. This library was totally crushed by Bakhtiar Khilaji, who attacked India in 1205 AD and, destroyed all libraries and burns them. The library continued consuming for around a half year". (Sharma,1987 -97).

Libraries in ancient India additionally created at different well known focuses of adapting, for example, Vikramshila and Odantapuri. Colleges of ancient India, as Taxila and Vikramshala additionally have significant gathering on tantras and compositions in their libraries.

During Medieval Period

Muslims for the most part rule the Medieval Period of India. Truly, it is otherwise called Mughal Period. There were awesome changes in social and political, as well as on education and library framework amid this period. The Muslim rulers made awesome commitments to Indian culture and libraries assumed a huge part in the socio cultural improvement of the country. "The time of Mughal is considered as the brilliant time of Indian history for its educational, scholarly, and library activities". (Khursid, 2004, 6).

Babur, lord of Kabul attacked India and added Delhi to his kingdom. "He built up the principal Mughal Imperial Library in 1526". (Patel, 2004, 6). Babur acquired compositions from his dad and kept in his library and furthermore gathered books from various wellsprings of his kingdom. Babur passed on in 1530 and was prevailing by his child Humayun.

Humayun much lived in Agra and set up library in his castle. He set up a library at Agra Fort, which was overseen by Lal Beg. In his library, he kept books, overlaid pen cases, portfolios, picture books and lovely works of calligraphy. After the demise of Humayun, his child, Akbar, succeeded him in 1356. Akbar is viewed as one of the best Mughal lord. Akbar enhanced the administration of library with some specialized works. He designated Sheik Faizi to oversee and control library services. Akbar was extremely enthusiasm for original copies and selected calligraphers to duplicate great compositions. He set up a different library for ladies at Fatehpur Sikri and made extraordinary change to the library. At the season of his demise in 1605, the Imperial Library has twenty-four thousand books. (Patel, 2004, 6). Jahangir, another rule of Mughal period, made a law that when a well off man kicked the bucket heirless, the property ought to be utilized for building and repairing schools, cloisters, libraries, and different organizations.

Some well off and researchers, as Abdul Rahim Khan-I-Khanan, Shaik Faizi, Gulbadan Begum and ruler of Mysore and Jaipur additionally have their private libraries. Some Hindu learning focuses additionally have libraries. "The libraries of these focuses contain enormous accumulations of original copies on religion and theory and also different subjects like prescription, science and history". (Datta;2004;172-173). Christian teachers have likewise contributed for the libraries since the happening to Vasco da Gama in India.

Amid the Mughal time frame, library specialized works, viz. Accessioning, Classification and Cataloging were likewise done in some ways. The head custodian was known as "Nizam" and the associate bookkeeper as "Muhatin" or "Darogha". Other staff of libraries amid Mughal period is Scribes, Book Illustrators, Calligraphers, Copyists, Translators, Bookbinders and Gilders. (Patel, 2004,7).

During British Period

The Britishers came to India essentially to build up exchange and trade. Some of them were extremely intrigued for the upliftment of rich social legacy of India. "Various Academic foundations were built up amid the British time frame by the East India Company (the delegates of the British Empire) and by the Christian evangelists". (Patel;2004;8). The University of Calcutta was set up in 1857 and its library was opened in 1873. Different Universities, University of Bombay and University of Madras were set up in 1879 and 1907 individually. There were just nineteen Universities in India before 1947. Colleges were furnished with libraries as per the Indian University Act of 1904. The Bengal Royal Asiatic Society set up library in 1784, Bombay Royal Asiatic Society in 1804 and Calcutta Public Library in 1835. (Sharma; 1987; 99). Foundation of these libraries edified and lit up the normal mass and might be dealt with as the premise of the idea of public libraries to the Indian individuals. A portion of the fundamental libraries set up in nineteenth. Century in India is Andrews Library, Surat in 1850, Gaya Public Library, Gaya in 1855, Long Library, Rajkot in 1856, Connemara Public Library, Madras in 1860, Government, Library, Janagarh in 1867, Adyar Library, Adyar in 1886 and Dahi Laxmi Library, Nadiad in 1892. Aside from these, different libraries, similar to the Gujarat Vernacular Society close by with a library in Ahmadabad 1848 and Barton Library, Bhavnagar in 1882 were likewise settled. A portion of the Indian states additionally founded public libraries. For example, Baroda set up Baroda State Library in Baroda in 1877, Cochin propelled Public Library and Reading Room in Trichur in 1873, Dhar built up Victoria General Library in Dhar in 1856, Indore set up General Library in Indore in 1852, Jaipur set up Maharajah's Public Library in Jaipur in 1899. Others states additionally settled such sort of libraries, viz. Jammu and Kashmir in 1879, Kahtiawar, in 1886, Kolhapur in 1850, Nizam's Dominion in 1891 and Travancore in 1829. (Patel; 2004; 9). The primary imperative date in the change of public libraries in India is 1808 when the Bombay Government started a plan to record libraries, which were to be given duplicates of books distributed from the 'Assets for the Encouragement of Literature'. (Bhattacharjee; 2002; 82).

The commitments of His Highness the Maharaja Sayajirao III, Gaekwar of Baroda towards library development in India can't be neglected. He is recollected today as the Father of Library Movement in India. At 18 years old, in 1881, he was endowed with full intensity of the government of Baroda in the Gujarat talking area of the Bombay Presidency and the Peninsula of Kathiawar. Baroda's populace was transcendently rustic, the principle occupation was agriculture. The general population as a rule were monetarily poor and socially in reverse. As per him, education was the foundation to remake another social and financial life and education ought to be the privilege of the humblest villager. He presented free and obligatory education in his royal states. Baroda turned into the main domain among the local states as well as in British India to have mandatory free essential education. (Nagar;1983;22). He opined that essential education was to be the plain base and chose to save it by methods for libraries, which were simply the main offices for unending widespread education. He chose to build up library as a test in one of the towns of a taluka and keeping in mind the end goal to actualize his thought promptly; he issued requests to his pastors. "In adjustment to his ruler's directions, the Minister of Education arranged a point by point intend to open Circulating Libraries in the State, which was affirmed in March, 1907. Each public library established through the State's money related help was to be named as Circulating Library". (Nagar;1983;26). In 1906, he went to America as "a spectator, an understudy covetous of getting all the information and experience that could empower him to make his own State a model one in India". (Nagar;1983;20). He was in particularly inspired by the library services of America for the advancement of the general population in their social, monetary and educational life. He at that point welcomed an American, William Alanson Borden, an understudy right hand of Charles A Cutter, who is functioning as Librarian of the Young Men's Institute, New Haven, Connecticut to come and built up library services in India. In light of his welcome, Borden achieved Baroda on November 6, 1910, and turned into the Director of State Libraries. It can be followed back that public library development began since 1910 in India. Borden makes an overview of libraries in Baroda and reasons that there were more than 241 libraries, holding a little more than 100000 volumes. In any case, he didn't discover any of those libraries satisfactorily housed, nor did he discover them retired in such a way as to make them most attractive to pursuers or

advantageous to those in control. He at that point make proposition for the best services of libraries in the State as:

- i.** Should Your Highness feel arranged to allow me the important expert, I propose to sort out a Department of Public Libraries, to rank with alternate Departments of Your State, with the essential types of gear of officers and representatives, and so forth and to bring every one of the libraries previously mentioned under its control and administration.
- ii.** To bind together every one of the accumulations of books in Baroda City into one Central library.
- iii.** To add to this Central library, general and specialized books.
- iv.** To erect a reasonable library working of flame resistant development, with perusing rooms, consider rooms, Women's Library, Children's library, Lecture corridor, Library school, and official workplaces.
- v.** To make that library to be Free Public Library of Baroda City, and furthermore the primary storage facility for all the important chronicled archives and papers now in private turns in the State, yet which the proprietors would most likely be happy to have put away in a sheltered place.
- vi.** To make it additionally the inside from which voyaging libraries should begin and from which the books, new and old, could be conveyed to the different branch libraries in the distinctive towns, urban areas, and towns of the State. (Nagar;1983;38).

The Maharaja clearly acknowledged Borden's recommendations, and requested that the entire plan may be executed in parts. The Library Department was made under Order No.9/19, January 30, 1911, for arranging libraries in Baroda. As the Director of state libraries, he arranged a system of free public libraries comprising a state focal library, four district or divisional libraries, forty-five town libraries, and in excess of a thousand town libraries-all coordinated into one chain framework. (Nagar; 1983;3). Borden assumed a main part for the foundation, administration and association of public libraries in India. Because of framework, inside two decades 85% of the Baroda urban and rustic

populace approached libraries. (Patel; 2004;10). Borden created library grouping plan to suit Indian libraries.

Another incredible commitment of Borden was the foundation of the principal library school in India, in which he prepared his own particular collaborators and successors. Borden directed the principal formal library-preparing program in India at Baroda in 1911. He was instrumental in the foundation of the Baroda Library Club and its diary, "Library Miscellany", distributed quarterly in three dialects in the vicinity of 1912 and 1919.

College of Madras made the post of University Librarian in 1923 and Dr. S R Ranganathan joined the post on 4 January 1924. (Ranganathan;1957;19). Ranganathan distributed his Five Laws of Library Science in 1931, Colon Classification in 1933 and Classified Catalog Code in 1934. He likewise arranged Model Public Library Bill and drives to enact library charge in Indian states. He made a huge commitment for the advancement of libraries in India.

Educationists, scholarly people and individuals in library cherishing mind began Calcutta Public Library in 1835 and the same was introduced on 21 March 1836 for the public. In 1944, Calcutta Public Library was moved to another and expansive building, raised to pay tribute to Lord Metcalf, the Governor General of India.

Lord Curzon, the then Viceroy and Governor-General of India stumbled Calcutta in 1899 and found a pathetic condition of the Calcutta Public Library. He obtained the privileges of the Library from the proprietors and later consolidated it with the Official supreme Library included government departmental libraries of the East India Company. He at that point pronounced initiation of a most recent Imperial Library of India on 30 January 1903 in the Metcalf Hall. In 1948, soon after the freedom of India, Imperial Library was changed over into the National library of India and was housed in the Viceroy's Palace in Calcutta, to be exact, the Belvedere Palace.

Post-Independence Period

Public libraries in India made a brilliant development after the autonomy of India in 1947. The focal and the state governments turn various advances forward for the change of the country from the perspective of instruction and trusted library as vital piece of it. The projects achieved by common and focal governments since 1910 for the grown-up and social instruction of the public demonstrated the route for the underwriting of library rules and laws for gifts in-help in the nation. That is the reason the public library turned out to be a piece of the training spending plan. (Jambhekar; 1995; 1). To expand the level of proficiency of 16% of every 1941, the government initiated a few projects, for example, development/augmentation administrations, long lasting training, societal instruction, casual training and grown-up training. The government additionally started a few activities for the advance of society and organized a few assignments in such manner. Libraries were thought to be an essential piece of the Community Development Project that was started amid the primary arrangement time frame. (Naidu; 1990). With a specific end goal to accelerate the speed of financial development, the government considered public libraries to be a fundamental piece of advancement ventures. (Jambhekar; 1995)

The Connemara Public Library in Madras ended up being the State Central Library in 1950 under the stipulation of Madras Public Libraries Act 1948, and ended up one of the three vault libraries in 1955. Delhi Public Library was set up in 1951 as the principal UNESCO Public Library Pilot Project under the joint supports of UNESCO and Government of India to take up "Modern Techniques to Indian Conditions" and to fill in as a model public library in Asia. (Kumbar). In 1954, the Delivery of Books Act was passed to take in the daily paper. The act required each distributor in India to put down one duplicate every one of its publications to the National Library in Calcutta, the Asiatic Society Library in Bombay, Connemara Public Library in Madras, and Delhi Public Library in New Delhi.

Library Legislation in India

People and library relationship to give public libraries under law are making a few endeavors. A section from Dr. S. R. Ranganathan, a number of people invested their opportunity and vitality to put on the statute book public library laws. Outstanding among them are kumar Munindra Deb Raimahasai of Bengal, K. V. Krishna Swamy Iyer, T. R. Venkataraman Sastry, Basheer Ahmed Sayeed of Madras, M.V. Donde of Bombay, K. M. Ujalambkar of Hyderabad and P. N. Kaula of Delhi. It is simply after India's autonomy that Dr. Ranganathan's fantasy of public library Act enactment was satisfied. Through the great workplaces of the then Minister for Education, Avinaslingam Chettiar, a adjusted Bill was presented in the state legislature, which was passed as the Madras Public Libraries Act in 1948. The current status of the public library framework in India is difficult to determine and portray, on the grounds that a united picture isn't accessible. There are twenty nine states and seven association regions in India. All have their own public library frameworks, structure, and example of budgetary help. Nineteen of the states have enacted library enactment and the rest are giving public library benefit without enactment. The states that have enacted library enactment are:-

1. Tamil Nadu (Madras) Public Libraries Act, 1948
2. Andhra Pradesh (Hyderabad) Public Libraries Act, 1960
3. Karnataka (Mysore) Public Libraries Act, 1965
4. Maharashtra Public Libraries Act, 1967
5. West Bengal Public Libraries Act - 1979
6. Manipur Public Libraries Act, 1988
7. Kerala Public Libraries Act, 1989
8. Haryana Public Libraries Act, 1989
9. Mizoram Public Libraries Act, 1993
10. Goa Public Libraries Act, 1993
11. Orissa Public Libraries Act, 2001
12. Gujarat Public Libraries Act, 2001
13. Uttarakhand (Uttaranchal) Public Libraries Act, 2005

- 14.** Uttar Pradesh Public Libraries Act, 2005
- 15.** Rajasthan Public Libraries Act, 2006
- 16.** Bihar Public Libraries Act, 2007
- 17.** Chhattisgarh Public Libraries Act, 2007
- 18.** Pondicherry Public Libraries Act, 2007
- 19.** Arunachal Pradesh Public Libraries Act, 2009

The Advisory Committee for Libraries was constituted in 1957 by the Government of India, with the Chairman named K.P Sinha. The Committee displayed its report in 1959 with an all around portrayed Model Library Bill. The Planning Commission made a Working Group on Public Libraries in 1964 and the Commission set forward its report in 1965 alongside a Model Public Libraries Act. The model bill was come to every one of the states/UTs, which don't have Public Libraries Act. In 1972, the Government of India, Planning Commission shaped Working Group on progression of Public Libraries to render proposals for library advancement. Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation (RRRLF), a self-representing body under the Department of Culture, Ministry of Education, was established in 1972. The primary objective of the Foundation was to help state library administrations for their advancement. In the course of the last thirty-two years, the Foundation has concealed about considerably more thirty-one thousand libraries at assorted levels of help.

Category of Libraries/Kendras etc.	Library Count
State Central Libraries	28
Divisional and District Libraries	451
Sub-Division/Taluka/Tehsil Libraries	501
Towns and Rural Libraries	30134
Nehru Yuvak Kendras	272
Jawahar Bal Bhawans	49
Others	128
Total	31563(1991,Census of India)

Table 3.2: Assistance to libraries covered by RRRLF. (RRRLF/Activities)

The Advisory Committee for Libraries as constituted in 1957 by the Government of India, with K P Sinha as the Chairman. The Committee submitted its report in 1959 with a drafted Model Library Bill. The Planning Commission constituted a Working Gathering on Public Libraries in 1964 and the Commission submitted its report in 1965 with a Model Public Libraries Act. The model bill was sent to every one of the states/UTs, which don't have Public Libraries Act. In 1972, the Government of India, Planning Commission constituted Working Group on Development of Public Libraries to make proposals for library improvement. Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation, an independent body under the Department of Culture, Ministry of Education, was set up in 1972. The fundamental goal of the Foundation was to help state library services in formative works.

In 1979, a library area was set up in the Department of Culture under the Ministry of Education, which area was under the charge of an Under Secretary. The goal was to advance the improvement of public libraries in India. (Jambhekar;1995). A Working Group on Modernization of Library Services and Informatics was named by the Planning Commission in 1983 and submitted its report in 1984 with the detailing of National Policy on Library Services and Informatics. Delhi Public Library turned into a copyright

library in 1982. National Proficiency Mission was embraced in 1986, which accentuated education for ladies and additionally foundation of country libraries. Library systems and frameworks were reinforced at the national level organizations in the improvement of writing in neo - literates.

Fourteen states to be specific, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra, West Bengal, Manipur, Kerala, Haryana, Mizoram, Goa, Orissa, Gujarat, Uttaranchal and Rajasthan have enacted Public Libraries Bills amid 1948 to 2006.

The Government of India, Department of Culture, designated a Committee on National Policy on Library and Information System in 1985. The National Policy on Education, 1986 states that an across the nation development for development of existing libraries and the foundation of new ones will be taken up, arrangement will be made in every educational foundation for library offices, and the status of librarianship moved forward. (Jhambekar;1995).The National Book Policy, 1986 additionally had an impact on libraries, as:

- i)** Provision of perusing material for youngsters by every one of the offices included;
- ii)** That 10 percent of the yearly education spending plan of the governments be used to buy books for libraries.

These objectives are to be accomplished by utilizing formal, non-formal, and open channels of learning. (Jhambekar;1995). Provincial libraries ought to wind up the point of convergence for post literacy what's more, proceeding with educational projects. Distributers, willful associations, what's more, school library programs attempted as a major aspect of the "Operation Blackboard Plan" of the National Education Policy on Education, 1986 were given help. The accompanying five libraries were viewed as national significance and might be expressed in an exceptionally concise way:

- i) National Library, Kolkata was established in 1836 in the name of Calcutta Public Library.

- ii) Khuda Bakhsh Oriental Public Library, Patna was open for the public in October 1891 with 4000 Oriental manuscripts.
- iii) Rampur Raza Library, Rampur was founded by Nawab Faizullah Khan in 1774 AD. It was brought under the management of a Trust till the Government of India took over the library on 1 July 1975 under the Act of Parliament, which declared it as an institution of National importance.
- iv) Thanjavur Maharaja Serfoji's Sarasvati Mahal Library, Thanjavur is one among a few medieval libraries existing in the world.
- v) Harekrushna Mahtab State Library, Bhubaneswar was conceived during 1st Five Year Plan under the advice of Government of India and was completed in 1959, enshrined within a beautiful land of 3 acres in a prime location of Capital City of Bhubaneswar. In 1967, it was named as Gandhi Bhawan commemorating birth centenary of Mahatma Gandhi, the father of the nation.

3.3 Public Libraries in West Bengal

To a man of letters in the present day society, the arrangement of education and the arrangement of library administration should have all the earmarks of being coextensive and concurrent. In any case, generally it doesn't occur to be so. Bengal bears a great convention both in the field of education and in the space of library development as well. But formal presence of library in the genuine feeling of the term isn't as old as that of the start of formal education.

Long before the British, the Dutch and the Portuguese globe-trotters approach in Bengal. With the approach of these Europeans, a reactant change in the financial atmosphere in the nation started to play.

The settlement of the English in Bengal in and around 1690 has a solid bearing on the spread of modern western education and the development and advancement of public libraries in this piece of the land as well as in the entire nation. After the triumph in the

clash of Plassy in 1757 the British got ready for a political control of the nation and henceforth all conceivable express endeavors for a changeless for the reason go to the fore. The British pilgrims needed to consider obtaining books and other distributed materials, even, to think to introduce printing press in this piece of the nation to meet the scholarly needs of the occupants. Bengal Gazette, prevalently known as Hick's Gazette by the name of its editorial manager, was hence begun .Subsequently showed up the Calcutta Gazette. These daily papers illuminates us that there were a couple of flow and subscription libraries in Calcutta for the British settlers. a dissemination library in the Old Fort was controlled by one Mr. John Andrews, Hicky's Gazette advises. We likewise gain from Hicky's Gazette that dating as back as 1770 a public library was there in the old fort which was moved to a 'cool and comfortable place in 1781. We likewise come to know the presence of two flowing libraries in Calcutta, the keep running by Mr. Shakell and the other by Messrs. Macdonald and Arnot. In 1787 these two libraries were acquired by one Messrs. Chicken, Maxwell and Co. furthermore, a major general library was opened under the name "Calcutta Circulating Library." This library was in operation till 1792 after which its gathering was put to public offer. The Bengal Hurcura Library, a unit of another famous daily paper worry of the time, known to be set up in 1798 had additionally a rich accumulation. The Protestant Missionaries who came to Bengal amid the eighteenth century had likewise built up their own libraries lecturing purposes.

The Asiatic Society Library – Beginning of new era of Public Library in West Bengal

As per the writings in the history, library development in West-Bengal ought to must be examined in the light of the land recorded point of view of then the unified Bengal that joins some portion of Assam, Bihar, Jharkhand and Orissa too. The Asiatic Society, Calcutta, as a partner of the Royal Asiatic Society, London was set up in 1784 by the colossal visionary oriental researcher Sir William Jones. Its principle objective being advancement of study and research ever, culture, archaic exploration, science, expressions, dialect, theory and so forth identifying with Asia has, from the earliest starting point, a library, which, by chance, happens to be the start of present day library development in Bengal as well as in India. Not very many library developments bears the

credit to have such a magnificent begin. At first the general public and its library was at the workplace of Sir William Jones, its organizer and later it was moved to its present area at Park Street. Before 1830, Indians were not permitted its enrollment. Rajendralal Mitra, the colossal orientalist, and Ramkamal Sen, the famous etymologist served the library as its bookkeeper. In 1984, the bi-century year of the general public, Government of India pronounced it a foundation of national significance.

Fort William College Library

The Fort William College was built up on eighteenth August 1800 with a view to influence the essayists of the East India To organization familiarize with the indigenous dialects that would help and advance authoritative works of the organization. In like manner a library was there in the school with a brilliant accumulation of books and original copies on Indology. The library was available to the national of Calcutta. Mr. William Hunter was its first bookkeeper. Sri Mohanprasad Thakur was later selected as his aide and who accomplished the qualification compiler of a few word references. In 1830 the Fort William College was broken up and the rich accumulation of its library was gained by the libraries in London, the Asiatic Society, Calcutta and the Calcutta Public Library built up in 1836.

There must not be any misunderstanding that the rise of libraries in each exchanging town in West Bengal is the upshot of the 1979 Library Act. Or maybe, it is to some degree inverse. Close around 90 percent public libraries were developed sooner than the Act, emerged. In Kolkata just, out of 88 supported libraries just 19 spurt after 1979 and out of 10 town libraries basically one was set up after the 1979 Act.

In the districts barely a library could be seen that succeeded 1979 Library Act. The subsequent table will show the figure of supported public libraries in every one of the districts.

National Library Calcutta

It was built up in 1836. It was anything but a government establishment yet it kept running on restrictive premise. Any subscriber paying Rs. 300/- at one time or in three portions was considered as proprietor. Poor understudies and other individuals were permitted to utilize the library free of charges for a predefined timeframe. Dwarkanath Tagor was the principal Proprietor of Calcutta public library. 4675 volumes were exchanged to the Calcutta Public libraries from the school of Fort William library according to the request of Lord Metcalf, the then Governor General of India. In this manner, the center gathering of library comprises of gifts from people and the said accumulation. The library gathered books in Marathi, Pali, Punjabi and Sinhalese. The gifts were gotten consistently from the Bengal Government, and Government of North Western territories was routinely gotten. By consolidating various secretariat libraries, the imperial library was established in 1891, among these libraries the imperative library was of the home department. This library contained numerous books which were taken from East India Company Library, Fort William College library and the East India Board at London. The library was not opened for overall population but rather the utilization was restricted to the best authorities of the senator. In the mid twentieth Century Lord Curzon Governor General of India opened this library for public assistance. He consolidated the accumulation of Calcutta with that of the imperial library for greatest usage of gathering of both the libraries.

The New library was named as imperial library. It was made public at Metcalf Hall, Calcutta on 30th January 1903. The reasons and destinations were characterized by a notice of the Gazette of India "that it ought to be a library of reference, working space for understudy and a store of material for the eventual fate of Indian history specialists, in which, relatively whole work expounded on India, whenever, can be seen and perused."

The primary delegated librarian was John Menzies Macfarlane, a previous Assistant Librarian of the British Museum of London. After his downfall, Harinath De assumed control over the charged in 1911 J. A. Chapman turns into the librarian. Amid his

residency the library made huge development and change. After he resigned Khan Bahadur M AnAsadulla turned into his successor and he worked up to 1947. In 1948 the Imperial Library was renamed as The National Library by the government of India and the fortune of the library was exchanged to the present Belvedere Estate in Calcutta from the Esplanade. The National Library was opened for the public on first February 1953 and B. S. Kesavan was the principal librarian of the National Library. The main purpose of The National Library was propelled on 22 January 2002 by H. E. Sri Viren J Shah as {www.nlindia.org}, the then legislative leader of west Bengal. He likewise discharged a CD ROM on the activities at the national libraries.

The West Bengal Public Libraries Act 1979

The West Bengal Legislature passed this Act and consent of the President was first appeared publicly in the Calcutta Gazette, Extraordinary on the seventh January 1980. West Bengal enacted the Public Libraries Act in 1979 to end up the fifth province of India with library enactment. Its prelude expressed that, "An Act to accommodate the foundation of Public libraries in the State of West Bengal and to direct, manage, focal, administer and to allow acknowledgment to the current libraries in the State as additionally to accommodate an exhaustive provincial and urban library benefit in the State of West Bengal". A portion of the imperative remarkable highlights of this Act are:

- i) Constitution of State Library Council to advise the Government on the issues of public library administrations. Priest in-Charge of Library Services should be the Chairman of the Council.
- ii) Constitution of the Department of Libraries to manage and coordinate the upkeep of Public Libraries.
- iii) Constitution of Local Library Authority for each district. The District Officer should be the Chairman of the Local Library Authority. Arrangement for constitution of Executive Committee for Local Library Authority.

- iv) The Government is engaged to designate District Library Officers and District Librarians in districts. The Government, in interview with the Nearby Library Authority may put a man responsible for a District Library to be called as District Librarian.
- v) Financial administration of nearby libraries rests upon the Local Library Specialist. Methods for expanding stores are:
 - a) Contributions, blessings and salary shape gifts.
 - b) Grants from the government
 - c) Collection of Local Library Authority under the Act.

In 1780, Mr. John Andrews run a business library in Fort William and the first public library; Calcutta Public Library was set up amid the British time frame in 1836, which is presently known as National Library. By 1900, there were 50 public libraries in Bengal. The state government took up a seven level library improvement conspire, which visualized setting up of public libraries at various levels-State Focal Library; District Library; Sub-Division/Area Library; Rural Library; Village Library; and Delivery Stations/Book Deposit Centers. (Patel;2004;114) By 1996, West Bengal has one State Central Library, 22 District Libraries, 120 Sub-Divisional/Town Libraries, and 2276 Rural/Area/Primary Unit Libraries. There are additionally around 3000 non-governmental/non-supported public libraries. (Chatterjee, 2001;114-115) West Bengal is the fifth state in India with Library Legislation in 1979.

West Bengal Public Library Act & Rules

- i) **West Bengal Public Libraries Act, 1979:** To accommodate the foundation of public libraries in the State of West Bengal and to manage, guide, control and direct libraries as additionally to accommodate a thorough rural and urban library and data benefit in the State of West Bengal. While it is convenient to accommodate the foundation of public libraries in the State of West Bengal and to direct, guide, control and administer the libraries as likewise to accommodate a far reaching rural and urban library and data benefit in the State of West Bengal.

- ii) West Bengal Public Libraries (Election Procedure) Rules:** To define the procedure of election and member selection for libraries and conduct of election.
- iii)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Appointment of Director of Libraries) Rules, 1980
- iv)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Directorate of Libraries) Rules, 1980
- v)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Appointment of District Library Officer and District Librarian) Rules, 1980
- vi)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Conduct of Election to the State Library Council) Rules, 1982
- vii)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Local Library Authority Fund) Rules, 1984
- viii)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Local Library Authority) Rules
- ix)** West Bengal Public Libraries (Conduct of Election to the Local Library Authorities) Rules, 1989
- x)** West Bengal Sponsored Public Library Management Rules, 2005
- xi)** Function of different Level of Library
- xii)** Setting up of New Libraries

Foundation and Growth of Academic Libraries in Bengal

Learning and education has its own vision. With the approach of the Europeans in Eastern India, European training and culture was penetrated in Indian society as a characteristic result. A couple of working class individuals of the recently instructed Indians jumped up, who by the light of light of their recently obtained training picked up the capacity to glance through and audit the way of life of the European society and the despicable pitiable state of the kindred locals. To raise the standard of their compatriots they feel the inclination for the spread of training in the nation. The principal scholarly foundation set up in Calcutta was in 1781, the Calcutta Madrasah for the development of Arabian and Persian examinations and Sanskrit College in 1792. However, the primary scholastic organization that was set up with an energy and mission is the Hindu College (now Presidency College) in 1817. Raja Rammohun Roy, the pioneer of present day Indian renaissance assumed an essential part in it, however, monitoring his questionable and aggravating remaining in the then Bengali society emerging out of his nonconformist

perspectives, cleverly maintained a strategic distance from public appearances regarding the foundation of the school. Instantly in 1818 the Serampore College was set up. Other prominent organizations sticks to this same pattern in progression – Oriental Seminary and Sanskrit College in 1823, General Assembly (now Scottish Church College) in 1830, St. Xavier's College in 1835, Hooghly Mohasin College in 1836 and others. Calcutta SchoolBook Society was built up with a library since its commencement. The foundation of scholastic organizations picked up its force when the University of Calcutta the principal college in India was built up in 1857. All such scholarly foundations of higher investigations slowly built up their libraries which before long gained sizeable, profitable and efficient accumulation.

The Calcutta Public Library (1836): New Era in Library Movement in Bengal

As people get educated they felt the necessity to establish libraries for the use of the public irrespective of natives and Europeans. Many eminent citizens of Calcutta – both Indians and Europeans joined the library either as proprietors or as subscribers during its long and eventful career. Among the Indian patrons, mention may be made of Dwarakanath Tagore, Debendranath Tagore, Prasanna Kumar Tagore, Ram Gopal Ghosh, Rustamji Cowasjee, Raja Satya Chandra Ghosal, Nrityalal Shil, Pratap Chandra Singh, Radhanath Sikdar, Peary Chand Mitra, Rasamay Datta, Rasik Krishna Mallik, Sashi Chandra Data, Kishori Chand Mitra, Sambhunath Pandit, and Dr. Mahendralal Sarkar. These are well known students of nineteenth Bengal. Of the European patrons, the following names deserve special mention: J. B. Macaulay, J. C. Marshman, Lord Metcalfe, James Princep, Sir John Peter Grant, J. F. D. Bethune and H. Beveridge.

With this urge in heart 146 citizens of Calcutta, both European and Indian, assembled in a public meeting held on 20th of August 1835. The meeting was convened “to take into consideration the best mode of testifying the public satisfactions” at the emancipation of the press under Sir Charles Metcalf, the meeting adopted the following resolution:

That it is expedient to and necessary to establish in Calcutta a public library of reference and circulation that shall be open to all ranks and classes without distinction and sufficiently extensive to supply the wants of the entire community in every department of literature.

As a result the Calcutta Public Library, a public library in the true sense of the term, finally came into being on 21st of March 1936. The library was initially opened to the public on the ground floor of the residence of Dr. F. P. Strong, Civil Surgeon of 24-Parganas. After a temporary shift to the Fort William in July 1841 it was finally removed to Metcalf Hall on Strand Road.

The nucleus of the library was formed by the donations received from private individuals and through the transfer of the collections of the dissolved Fort William College Library, the valuable collection consisting of 4,675 volumes.

Though the establishment of the library was the result of the initiative of both Indian and European personalities of eminence, the spirit behind this initiative was Mr. J. H. Stocqueler (pseudonym of Joachim Hayward Stocqueler). Siddons' justifiable remark that the city of Calcutta is destitute of a public library, that led to the formation of the assemblage of the eminent figures of the city to remove the want. Peary Chand Mitra and Bipin Chandra Pal, two eminent sons of Bengal served the library as its librarian. After the 1857 the Europeans lost interest in the library and its condition deteriorated to a great extent. Lord Curzon, the then Viceroy of Bengal purchased its collection and merged it with the Imperial Library that he established in 1903. After independence the Imperial Library was renamed as National Library and was finally shifted to Belvedere, Alipore, The residential house of the then Lieutenant general of India. The newspaper reading room, however, is still there at its old location at Esplanade East.

The Imperial Library (1903)

It was on the initiative of Lord Curzon, the then Viceroy of India and John Macfarlane's active hand that Imperial Secretariat Library was converged to shape the Imperial Library and it was opened to the public on January 30, 1903. This Imperial Library might be

viewed as the developing life of the Calcutta Public Library which at last swung to be the National Library, Calcutta.

Growth of Public Libraries in Bengal

The primary library for the Calcutta public is credited with one John Andrews, a book shop by calling, built up a circulating library where books can be acquired from for a charge. Bengal, to talk it all the more accurately India, being under the British rule each occasion of significance that occurred in British society has made some pretty much impact on the Indian partner as her subject. In 1850, the British Public Libraries Act, the first of its kind was promulgated. The Calcutta Public Library was set up only 14 years sooner to this in the year 1836. The two vital occasions has had its profound effect on the psychological constitution of the Indian educated public. Therefore proliferation of foundation of public libraries turned into a pattern amid this period. A portion of the imperative public libraries built up amid the latter portion of the nineteenth century are as per the following:

These libraries are the products of drudge of some gave and dedicated individuals of the concerned territory who, with the soul of advance of the society trusted that the library or at the end of the day, perusing propensity can assume an essential part keeping that in mind. Some place the libraries were dedicated as a wing of a nearby club or other social association. The vast majority of these libraries notwithstanding a couple of, after the enactment of the West Bengal Public Libraries Act, 1979 settled on government acknowledgment and attained diverse status like Rural Library, Town Library and so on as per their particular quality of holding and different positions. Staff compensation and yearly library give on a foreordained premise as indicated by the status of the concerned library is given by the administration.

Government and Government Sponsored Libraries in West Bengal

West Bengal has a strong network of Public Library System comprising of total 2480 public libraries out of which 13 are Government Public Libraries, 2460 Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries and 7 Govt. Aided Public Libraries run by voluntary organizations.

Out of total Govt. Libraries, State Central Library is at the apex of the Public Library System in the State. Besides, there are 7 District Libraries, 4 Town / Sub-divisional libraries and one library of special status namely Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library.

In addition, there are 2460 Govt. Sponsored public libraries which include 19 District Libraries, 232 Town / Sub-divisional Libraries, 2209 Primary Unit / Rural / Area Libraries.

Besides those, there are 319 Community Library cum Information Centers (CLICs), those were established in those Gram Panchayats where there is no Govt., Govt. Sponsored or Govt. Aided Public Library.

Amongst these 2480 Government, Govt. Sponsored and Govt. Aided Public Libraries, 344 libraries were established before independence, 418 libraries were established after independence up to implementation of West Bengal Public Libraries Act, 1979, and 1711 libraries were established after independence up to till date. Some libraries are age-old and bear their important role till date.

Sl. No.	Name of the Library	District	Year of Establishment
1	State Central Library	Kolkata	1956
2	Kolkata Metropolitan Library	Kolkata	1980
3	Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library	Hooghly	1859
4	North Bengal State Library	Coochbehar	1870
5	Taki Govt. District Library	North 24-Parganas	1860
6	Deshbandhu Govt. District Library	Darjeeling	1955
7	District Library, Uttar Dinajpur	Uttar Dinajpur	2004
8	North 24-Parganas Govt. District Library	North 24-Parganas	1955
9	Govt. Central Library	Darjeeling	1961
10	Central Library	North 24-Parganas	1953
11	Sidhu-Kanhu Birsa Govt. Town Library	Purulia	1989

12	Digha Govt. Town Library	Purba Medinipur	1966
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Table 3.3.1: Government Libraries in West Ben

	District	1901-10	1911-20	1921-30	1931-40
1	Kolkata	20	34	86	87
2	Coochbehar	-	7		1
3	Khulna	3	5	2	18
4	Chittagong	3	3	6	14
5	Jalpaiguri	2	2	7	4
6	Dacca	1	0	1	4
7	Tripura	2	5	5	26
8	Darjeeling	-	2	3	5
9	Dinajpur	3	5	7	31
10	Nadia	2	8	8	6
11	Noakhali	-	1	1	6
12	Pabna		6	9	16
13	Faridpur		1	6	4
14	Bagura		0	3	10
15	Burdwan	3	9	19	36
16	Bankura	3	3	8	24
17	Bakharganj	1	2	1	43
18	Birbhum	3	3	5	27
19	Mymansingh		3	9	19
20	Maldah		3	5	25
21	Murshidabad	1	6	4	16
22	Medinipur		5	7	34
23	Jessore	1	5	1	4
24	Rangpur	4	1	2	15

25	Rajsahi	3	2	2	6
26	Howrah	4	17	21	24
27	Hooghly	9	28	25	42
28	24-Parganas	13	18	15	24
	Total	81	184	268	571

Table 3.3.2: District-wise distribution of Public Libraries in Undivided Bengal

Libraries established during the years 1947-1977							
Districts	State Central Library	District Library	Special status Library	Central Library	Town/ Sub-divisional Library	Rural/ Primary Unit Library	Total
Bankura	-	1		-	1	38	40
Birbhum	-	1		-	1	42	44
Burdwan	-	2		-	4	55	61
Calcutta	1	-		-	1	5	7
Cooch Behar	-	1		-	1	39	41
Darjeeling	-	1		1	3	60	65
Hooghly	-	1	1	-	4	53	59
Howrah	-	1		-	1	52	54
Jalpaiguri	-	1		-	1	34	36
Maldah	-	1		-	2	27	30
Midnapur	-	2		-	5	67	74
Murshidabad	-	1		-	2	38	41
Nadia	-	1		-	3	36	40
Purulia	-	1		-	1	38	40
24-Parganas	-	3		1	6	82	92
W. Dinajpur	-	1			1	35	37
Total		19	1	2	37	701	761

Table 3.3.3: No. of Public Libraries in West Bengal during 1947 – 1977

Other Important Libraries

There are some other important libraries in West Bengal. These libraries are old and have some historical and important books in their collection. There are 21 libraries which are important because of their collection of books, journals, history notes etc.

Sl. No.	Name of the Library	District	Establishment Year	Brief
1	Bose Institute Library	Kolkata	1917	<p>The establishment library is extraordinary compared to other Science Reference Libraries in Eastern India. It expressed its capacity in the primary grounds in 1917. Library gives its administrations to the Bose Institute resources, specialists and staffs and furthermore stretches out its administrations to different Institutions/Universities in and around Kolkata and in addition West Bengal.</p> <p>Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose gathering Archival of Theses abstracts Rare book file [as on 31-03-2008] Total perusing material 38,841 2500 online diaries Subscribed to full content databases of various scholastic.</p>
2	British Council Library	Kolkata	1950	<p>The British Council Library arrange in India is spread crosswise over nine urban areas. The Library in Kolkata was built up in 1950. Through the focuses and projects British Council advances the decent variety and innovativeness of British society and culture. Access to in excess of 4200 e-diaries. Books and different publications 46,309 E-assets Web of science Derwent development list Delphion [Patent database]</p>

				ASTM Standards.
3	Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute [CGCRI] Library	Kolkata	1950	The foundation is the main association in India seeking after R&D in glass and just a single among a not very many doing R&D in earthenware production. CGCRI library was built up in 26th August 1950. Access to in excess of 4200 e-diaries. Books and different publications 46,309 E-assets Web of science Derwent advancement list Delphion [Patent database] ASTM Standards.
4	Central Reference Library	Kolkata	1958	It is the National Bibliographic Agency of the nation. Every bibliographical Record since 1958 are accessible in electronic arrangement. There are in excess of 6 lakhs records accessible in its database.
5	Geological Survey of India	Kolkata	1851	The organization gives the country the fundamental geosciences information both for asset investigation and scholastic interest. Authentic specialists visit the library for its documented accumulations. It is a national fortune of old, uncommon and important chronicled records from sixteenth century to mid twentieth century.
6	The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science [IASC] Library	Kolkata	1876	The IACS library has become out of the exploration needs of the Association from its earliest reference point (1876). So it is the most established library of its kind and involves an extraordinary position among the scholarly community of the Eastern India. "It has huge accumulation of extremely old logical diaries of gigantic recorded and authentic qualities - a gathering that has no

				parallel in some other library of an exploration Institute".
7	Institute of Science Education & Research – Kolkata [IISER-K] Library	Kolkata	2006	The IISER-K Library, began in 2006, works as a library, documentation and data focus obliging training and research in fundamental sciences. It is conceived to venture into a noteworthy asset framework after a short time. The book collection stands at 29,500+ [16,500+ in print and 13,000+ electronic].
8	Indian Association of Special Libraries and Information Centers [IASLIC]	Kolkata	1955	On 3 September 1955 India Association of Special Libraries and Information Centers (IASLIC) was formally settled. Dr. Hora was chosen the primary President and Mr. J. Saha the main Honorary General Secretary of IASLIC.
9	Indian Institute of Chemical Biology Library	Kolkata	1935	With the foundation of Indian Institute of medicinal Research On January 01, 1935, the Library and Documentation Division began its Journey as one of the lofty offices.
10	Indian Statistical Institute Library	Kolkata	1931	Mahalanobis set up the Statistical Laboratory in the Presidency College at some point in the 1920s. On 17 December 1931, the Indian Statistical Institute was established as a scholarly society and housed in the Statistical Laboratory.
11	National Institute of Technology, Durgapur Library	Durgapur	1960	Built up as a joint wander of the Government of India and the Government of West Bengal, Upgraded to National Institute of Technology in 2003 as a Deemed University, Became National Institute of Technology, an Institute of National Importance(INI) in 2007. A head Technological Institute for Teaching and Research.
12	National Library	Kolkata	1836	The National Library is the pinnacle body of the library

				<p>arrangement of India. Filling in as a public library, this is a lasting vault of all reports distributed in India. The National Library, India is the biggest library in the nation. It is a foundation of National significance under the 'Service of Culture, Government of India'. The library is assigned to gather, spread and protect the written word created in the nation. The library is arranged on a picturesque 30 sections of land Belvedere Estate, in Kolkata, some time ago Calcutta City. Indian, English and Foreign dialects, Rare Books, Science and Technology, Indian Official Documents, Foreign Official Documents, Newspapers and Periodicals, Manuscripts, Maps and Prints, Microforms.</p>
13	S.N. Bose National Centre for Basic Science Library	Kolkata	1986	<p>The Center is an Autonomous Research Institute set up under DST, GOI in 1986 as a Registered Society. The Center was built up to respect the life and work of Prof. S. N. Bose who was an epic in hypothetical material science and has made probably the most essential theoretical commitments in the improvement of Quantum Mechanics and Quantum Statistics.</p>
14	Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library	Kolkata	1951	<p>At first a piece of the University of Calcutta, the Institute was concurred self-governance in 1951. From that point forward a Governing Body (Council from 1972), led by the Vice-Chancellor of the University of Calcutta and having delegates from the University of Calcutta, the Union Government and the Government of West Bengal, was in the administration until the point that 1992 when this tripartite assention arrived at an end. The Institute</p>

				entered an agreement with the Department of Atomic Energy,
15	The American Library	Kolkata		The library gathering centers essentially around U.S. government and legislative issues, universal relations, financial aspects, business administration, sociologies, human rights, American history, American writing and worldwide issues, for example, condition, tranquilize mishandle and HIV/AIDS. It keeps up around 15,000 volumes of books, U.S. government and research organization reports, videocassettes on flow themes, and buys in to 162 American periodicals and 3 driving American daily papers. A scope of CD-ROMs and electronic databases accessible for the utilization of supporters give access to edited compositions and full messages of articles from insightful periodicals. Reference experts help supporters in finding data for questions got face to face, by phone, email or by post.
16	Zoological Survey of India Library	Kolkata	1916	The Zoological Survey of India (ZSI) was built up on 1 st July, 1916 to advance review, investigation and research prompting the headway in our insight into different parts of incredibly rich existence of the recent 'English Indian Empire'. The study has its beginning in the foundation of the Zoological Section of the Indian Museum at Calcutta in 1875.
17	Asiatic Society Library	Kolkata	1784	At the point when the ASIATIC SOCIETY was set up on 15 January 1784, its author Sir William Jones (1746-1794) started his work with a fantasy, that envisioned a middle for Asian investigations including nearly everything concerning man and

				nature inside the topographical furthest reaches of the mainland. The vast majority of the secrets of this huge land, similar to its old engravings in Brahmi, were as yet undeciphered, and Comparative Philology as a train or science was not yet conceived.
18	American Library [USIS]	Kolkata		The American Library in the past known as the United States Information Service (USIS) Library is a piece of the Public Affairs Office of the American Consulate General, Kolkata. Through its different exercises and assets the library means to advance a superior comprehension of the strategies, qualities, foundations and culture of the United States. It gives an extensive variety of present, exact and legitimate data from a tremendous determination of print and electronic assets utilizing best in class innovation.
19	Assembly house Library	Kolkata		
20	Bangiya Sahitya Parishad	Kolkata	1893	Bangiya Sahitya Parisad was established in the year 1893.
21	Bangla Academy	Kolkata		
22.	Bidhan Chandra Granthagar [Mahajati Sadan]	Kolkata	1939	Foundation stone was laid on 1939. Mahajati Sadan, "Place of the Nation" was comtemplated by Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose and its foundation stone was laid by Kavi Guru Rabindra ath Tagore.
23.	Botanical Survey of India Library		Howrah	
24.	Centre for Studies in Social Science		Howrah	
25.	Dinesh Majumdar State Youth Library		Kolkata	
26.	Indian Museum Library	1814	Kolkata	The Indian Museum houses an immense gathering of somewhere in the range of fifty thousand books

				and diaries alongside numerous uncommon publications. Books and Journals are accessible on Musicology, Archeology, Anthropology, Art and so on. Researchers, school and undergrads can get to the library by getting to be individuals.
27.	Maxmular Bhavan Library		Kolkata	
28.	National Atlas and Thematic Mapping Org.		Kolkata	The Library and Documentation Center of National Atlas and Thematic Mapping Organization came into picture science its beginning. The Library has a huge and exceptional accumulation of books particularly on Geography and united subjects and in addition maps, geological maps and map book. Books No. 19000, Journals, Maps and Atlases Maps
29.	Ramakrishna Mission Institute of Culture Library	1941	Kolkata	To help researchers in their work of study and research, there is at the Institute, a General Library, with a perusing room joined. The library has practical experience in humanities and sociologies, however it has a decent accumulation of books in different streams as well. These areas keep a decent gathering of books as well. The General Library has more than 2,03,766 books including 5,021 uncommon books and 424 Indian and outside diaries. Moreover, there are rich accumulation of books in the Research Section on Indology and selective unique titles at Vivekananda Archive.
30.	Roopkala Kendra Library	1955	Kolkata	Roopkala Kendro, an Institute of Film and Social Communication in the Information and Cultural Affairs Department, Government of West Bengal has been formed out of an Indo-Italian technical

				cooperation in 1995.
31.	Victoria Memorial Hall Kolkata	1921	Kolkata	The Victoria Memorial Hall was opened in 1921. It is likewise an exhibition hall where individuals could see before them pictures and statues of men who had a conspicuous impact ever of and build up a pride in their past particularly in connection to the historical backdrop of Calcutta.
32.	Bengal Library Association	1937	Kolkata	To start with periodical on Library Science in Bengal was distributed by the Bengal Library Association in 1937 as 'Bengal Library Association Bulletin –Bangiya Granthagar Parishad Patrika'. It was a bilingual diary, which proceeded with upto 1952.
33.	Chitrabani Library		Kolkata	Chitrabani is the social correspondence focus supported by the Kolkata Province of the Society of Jesus.
34.	Satyajit Roy Film & Television Institute Library		Kolkata	SRFTI, Kolkata/Calcutta, is a self-ruling scholarly establishment working under the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Government of India. Satyajit Ray Film and Television Institute.
35.	National Council of Science Museum Library [NCSM]	1978	Kolkata	In 1978, it was chosen by the Government of India to delink from CSIR the two science historical centers officially working at Kolkata and Bangalore and furthermore the one being set up at Mumbai and put them under a recently framed Society enrolled on April 4, 1978 as National Council of Science Museums (NCSM).
36.	Birla Industrial & Technological Museum Library [BITM]	1959	Kolkata	
37.	Science City Library, Kolkata		Kolkata	To depict the development of science and innovation and their

				application in industry, human welfare and condition, with a view to create logical demeanor and to make, teach and maintain a general mindfulness among the general population.
38.	J. C. Bose Botanical Garden of India	1787	Howrah	The Acharaya Jagadish Chandra Bose Botanical Garden beforehand known as Indian Botanical Gardens, Howrah are arranged in Shibpur, Howrah. The Gardens were set up in the year 1787.
39.	Kolkata Little Magazine Library O Gabesana Kendra	1978	Kolkata	Working out of a little room in Tamer Lane, off College Street, in Kolkata, the Little Magazine Library opened to the public in 1978 with Sandip Dutta's own gathering of magazines. Mr. Dutta had started gathering little magazines in the 1970s, yet the drive for the library was his anger at the mass transfer of Bengali little magazines by the National Library in Kolkata.
40.	West Bengal Secretariat Library		Kolkata	Set up under the immediate control of the Government of West Bengal. Uncommon books and archives.
41.	Manmathonath Ghosh Institute of 19th & 20th Century Studies		Kolkata	Secretly Manage Library. Anyone can get to the library with no kind of expenses. Uncommon books/Periodicals/Rare keepsake/Portrait and Paintings/coins

Table 3.3.4: Other Important Libraries

Century Old Libraries

There are 79 oldest libraries in West Bengal which have rare books, manuscripts, old journals, oldest newspapers and maharaja's collection in their library.

Sr. No.	Name Of the Library	Establishment Year	District	Collection
1.	Agarpara Pathagar	1891	24 Parganas(N)	
2.	Ariadaha Association Library	1870	Kolkata	Old Journals, Manuscripts
3.	Asutosh Memorial Library	1891	Kolkata	Rare books, Rare journals, Books on Drama
4.	Asiatic Society	1784	Kolkata	Manuscripts, Coins, Rare books.
5.	Bagbazar Reading Library	1883	Kolkata	Rare books & rare journals
6.	Bagila Bankim Pathagar	1900	Burdwan	
7.	Bally Sadharan Granthagar	1885	Howrah	Manuscripts, Rare books, old journals
8.	Bandhab Library	1869	24 Parganas(S)	
9.	Bangiya Sahitya Parisad	1894	Kolkata	Old paintings, Coins, Sculpture, Manuscripts, Rare books, Old journals & Periodicals
10.	Old paintings, Coins, Sculpture, Manuscripts, Rare books, Old journals & Periodicals	1884	Howrah	Rare books & rare journals
11.	Baranagar Peoples Library	1876	Kolkata	Rare books & Old Journals
12.	Bankim Chandra Library	1906	Murshidabad	
13.	Bansberia Public Library	1891	Hooghly	Manuscripts, Rare books, Old journals
14.	Barisa Pathagar	1904	Kolkata	
15.	Belur Sadharan Granthagar	1895	Howrah	Old Journals, Rare Books
16.	Belegkata Sandhya Samity	1900	Kolkata	Rare Books
17.	Belgharia Parymohan Memorial Town Library	1905	Kolkata	
18.	Bhadreswar Public Library	1909	Hooghly	
19.	Bharati Prasad	1890	Kolkata	Rare books, Old Journals
20.	Boral Priyanath Library	1871	24 Parganas(S)	Manuscripts, Old books

21.	The Boys Own Library and Young Men's Institute	1909	Kolkata	Rare books and periodicals
22.	Chaitanya Library	1889	Kolkata	Rare books & rare journals
23.	Chandan nagar Pustakagar	1873	Hooghly	Rare books, Old Journals
24.	Chandra Saraswati Pathagar	1901	Hooghly	Rare books
25.	Dakhineshwar Ramkrishna Library & Reading Club	1879	Kolkata	Rare books
26.	Freserganj Bijoli Club & Library	1903	South 24 Parganas	
27.	Friends Union Pathagar	1898	Howrah	Gupta Press Panjika (almanac) of last 100 years
28.	Friends Club Library	1901	Howrah	Rare books & Encyclopedia
29.	Hemkali Library	1902	South 24 Parganas	
30.	Hem Chandra Library		Kolkata	
31.	Indian Association Library	1876	Kolkata	Rare books & Old Journals
32.	Jaipur Arya Samity	1896	Howrah	Manuscripts, Rare books, Old journals
33.	Jamgram Nandi sadharan Pathagar	1894	Hooghly	Old Books, Old Periodicals
34.	Kalighat Library	1886	Kolkata	
35.	Kheali Khela Ghar	1910	Kolkata	
36.	Konnaagar Public Library & Free Reading Room	1858	Hooghly	Rare Books, Old & Rare Journals
37.	Krishna nagar Public Library	1856	Nadia	Rare Books & Rare Journals
38.	Kumartuli Institute	1884	Kolkata	
39.	Mahabodhi Society	1892	Kolkata	Rare journals, Rare Books & Rare Journals on Buddhist Philosophy
40.	Mahesh Public Library & Free	1869	Hooghly	Old Journals
41.	Maju Public Library	1905		
42.	Makardaha Saraswat Library	1885	Howrah	Manuscripts, Rare Books, Old Journals, All news papers dated 15th August 1947

43.	Mudiali Library	1876	Kolkata	Rare books & Journals
44.	Mohiari Public Library	1886	Howrah	Rare books & Manuscripts
45.	Mondalai Public Library	1894	Hooghly	Old Books
46.	Nabadwip Sadharan Granthagar	1908	Nadia	
47.	National Library	1903	Kolkata	
48.	North Bengal State Library	1869	Coochbehar	Rare Manuscripts, Rare Books, Old & Rare Journals of Maharaja's Collection
49.	Pally Varati Granthagar	1888	Howrah	
50.	Panihati Bandhab Pathagar	1898	24 Parganas(N)	Rare Books
51.	Purandar Smriti Mandir Pathagar	1910	24 Parganas(S)	
52.	Rajnarayan Basu Smriti Pathagar	1851	Midnapur	Rare Books & Manuscripts
53.	Rajpur Sadharan Pathagar	1877	24 Parganas(S)	Old Journals
54.	Ramkrishnapore Sansad	1900	Howrah	Rare journals, Rare Books & Rare Journals on Buddhist Philosophy
55.	Ramranjan Poura Nigam O Vivekananda Granthagar	1900	Birbhum	Rare Books
56.	Ram Mohan Library & Free Reading Room	1904	Kolkata	
57.	Ranaghat Public Library	1884	Nadia	Rare Books, Rare Journals
58.	Raniganj Public Library	1876	Burdwan	Rare books
59.	Raspore Peoples Library	1883	Howrah	Rare books & Manuscripts
60.	Sadharan Brahma Samaj Library	1879	Kolkata	Rare Journals, Rare Books
61.	Sargachi Ramkrishna Mission Ashram Granthagar	1897	Murshidabad	
62.	Sasadhar Pathagar	1904	North 24 Parganas	
63.	Sashipada Institute Library & Free Reading Room	1867	Kolkata	
64.	Shibpore Public Library	1874	Howrah	Rare books & journals
65.	Sripore Kalyan Samity	1891	Hooghly	Rare books, journals

66.	Sreerampore Public Library & Mutual Improvement Association	1861	Hooghly	Rare books & Old journals
67.	Suburban Reading Club	1888	Kolkata	Rare books & Old journals
68.	Suhrit Library	1891	Kolkata	Rare books & Old journals
69.	Taltola Public Library	1882	Kolkata	Rare journals & Panjika from 1333 Bangabda
70.	The Bagbazar Free Reading Library	1907	Kolkata	
71.	The Boys' Own Library & Young Men's Association	1909	Kolkata	
72.	The United Reading Rooms	1872	Kolkata	Old Books
73.	The United Reading Club & Public Library	1898	Howrah	Few Old Books
74.	Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library	1859	Hooghly	Rare Manuscripts, Rare books, Old & Rare Journals
75.	Uttarpara Saraswat Sammilan	1909	Hooghly	
76.	Vivekananda Granthagar & Ramrajan Town Hall	1900	Birbhum	
77.	William Cerry Granthagar	1818	Hooghly	Rare books, Manuscripts, Old journals
78.	Young Mens' Association	1909	Hooghly	
79.	Garalgacha Public Library (Town)	1913	Hooghly	Rare Books, Old Journals and Periodicals

Table 3.3.5: Century Old Libraries

Figure: 3.1: Distribution of Century Old Libraries in West Bengal

Government Aided Libraries in West Bengal

There are 7 such libraries, most of which are run by Non-Government Organizations. These libraries are assisted with government grants at par with Sub-divisional/ Town Libraries. Managing Committees of such libraries consists at least one Government officer as government nominee.

Of the three tier library system, namely, i) District, ii) Sub-divisional and iii) Primary Unit/ Rural/ Area Library – services mentioned in item numbers 1, 5, and 7 are generally rendered by the Rural/ Primary/ Area Libraries. Selected Rural/ Primary Unit/ Area Libraries render services under item number 2, 4, and 8. Services mentioned in item number 1 to 8, 10 and 11 are rendered by the District Libraries. The State Central library covers all the services of item numbers 1 to 13.

Sr. No.	Library Name	District	Year Of Establishment
1.	Ramkrishna Sarada Mission Ashram Library	Kolkata	1957
2.	Ramkrishna Mission Library	24Parganas (S)	1960
3.	Ramkrishna Mission Janashiksha Library, Belur Math	Howrah	1954
4.	Ramkrishna Mission Student Home Library, Belghoria	Kolkata	1963
5.	Krittibas Memorial Community Hall-cum-M use urn Library	Nadia	1960
6.	Rammohan Library and Free Reading Room	Kolkata	1904
7.	Bangiya Sahitya Parishad Library	Kolkata	1893

Table 3.3.6: Government Aided Libraries in West Bengal

Specialized libraries

Specialized libraries are intended to cater library benefits by giving books and other essential perusing materials on the specialized field of study. Close by the foundation of prominent scholarly establishments and libraries attached with those organizations, some specialized foundations and organizations of innovative work likewise experienced childhood in and around Calcutta amid this time. To say a couple of , the famous Botanical Garden and its library in 1787, Calcutta Medical College Library in 1835, Geological Survey of India Library in 1851, Bengal Engineering College Library in 1856, and the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science Library in 1876.

For sorting out and overseeing Library Services there is an arrangement in the Act for an Advisory Body in the State level, i.e. State Library Council (SLC) which comprises of 31 individuals under the Chairmanship of Hon'ble Minister.

For arranging and regulating Library Services at the locale level according to arrangement of the Act there is an Advisory Body in the region level, i.e. Neighborhood Library Authority (LLA) which comprises of 22 to 24 individuals under the Chairmanship of concerned District Magistrate of the locale.

For arranging and regulating Library Services at the library level according to arrangement of the Act there is an Advisory Body in the library level, i.e. Overseeing Committee (MC) which comprises of 12 to 21 individuals.

3.4 Digital Libraries

The rise of digital libraries in 1990's and their staggering development in the ongoing years has opened up new skylines over a wide cluster of issues identified with outline, execution, advancement and assessment of digital libraries. The different meanings of digital libraries authored by specialists and foundations after some time, bear witness to the developing significance and extent of the digital libraries and the rearrangement and accentuation of the part of individuals, information and technology as key to convey effective digital libraries.

There Are Some Important Laws For Digital Library.

- 1) Books/Information are for utilize:** Before planning the digital library, the digital library ought to be in such a way, to the point that it is simple for use, with an electronic UI that can be modified for the organization, individual or office. Digital Library includes the information in digital configuration that will be less demanding to get to just when vital technology joins, well fabricated foundation and PC frameworks are accessible to clients. The clients must be given introduction for seeking and recovery of information in the huge digital library and which must be accessible for the client.

- 2) **Each Reader his or her book/information:** The information gained, assembled, put away, recovered or spread in the digital library must be so important to the client with the goal that the information can discover its in brief timeframe. The digital library ought to be built in such a way, to the point that it can be effectively available on the web/disconnected database and for that various open source software accessible for the execution of digital library with most recent improvement of information technology.
- 3) **Each Book/Information its Reader:** The client can acquire the required information or information from the database.
- 4) **Save the time of the Reader:** Looking from database apparatuses or way should be very much outlined, the ordering part in the database must be consistently refreshed, subjective file design must be utilized for confining watchwords, and inquiry systems must be simple such that the layman can without much of a stretch recover information. To spare the season of the easy to use software can be utilized with the goal that the client can undoubtedly look through the significant information.
- 5) **Library is a developing life form:** Before planned the digital library, it ought to be an eye for the future which can have capacity limit, equipment abilities and software similarity for the future age.

In spite of the fact that the term digital library has increased exceptionally ubiquity as of late, however it has a long history, back to more than 80 (Eighty) years. Development of imprinting in the second 50% of eighteenth century began an unrest in spreading considerations and grants. Later on microfilm (1839), recording Disk (1877), sound tapes (1899), video tapes, T.V. (1908) microcomputer (1980), CD-ROM and optical stockpiling gadget (1985), DVD Rom (1998) and so forth are affect on distributing. In 1928, IBM delivered a punched card that turned into the prevail methods for contributing information into PC for quite a few years.

The idea of "hypertext" which is the fundamental for the present Internet can be followed back to Vannevar Bush's prophetic article "as we may think" written in 1945 for the Atlantic month to month. Processing information in a machine discernable configuration had turned out to be critical. Eugene intensity of college microfilms Inc. started utilizing microfilm technology in the 1930's. Shrubbery envisioned a "Memex" machine fit for arranging, putting away and showing paper books and other information that would be made accessible at every individual's work area by means of microfilm. In the meantime Ted Nelson imagined and named hypertext and hyperspace in 1974 yet was never ready to manufacture an operational framework. Afterward, different terms, for example, "Electronic Library," "Virtual Library", Library without Wall and so forth has appeared. The principal remotely available database came online in the late 1960's which for the most part managed legitimate logical and government information. In 1972 the principal business online administration named DIALOG showed up which was confined to the content based records as it were. F. W. Lancaster in 1978 in his advanced book "Towards paperless information framework" visualized the upheaval in electronic would prepare for paperless society.

1994	NSF Digital Library Initiative Phase 1(DLI-1).
	The First Annual Conference on the Theory and Practice of Digital Library, College Station, Texas.
1995	First IEEE Advances in Digital Libraries Conference, McClean, Vigrinia.
1996	First ACM Conference on Digital Libraries, Bethesda, Maryland.
1997	First European Conference on Research and Advance Technology For Digital Libraries (ECDL), Pisa, Italy.
1998	The First International Conference on Asian Digital Libraries (ICADL 1998), Hong Kong, China.
1999	President’s Information Technology Advisory Committee (PITAC) Report.
	NSF Digital Library Initiative Phase 2 (DLI-2).
	Institute of Museum and Library Service (IMLS) Program.
	NSF National Science, Mathematics, Engineering and Technology Digital Library (NSDL) Program.
	ICADL 1999, Taipei, Taiwan.
2000	ICADL 2000, Seoul, Korea.
2001	ICADL 2001, Bangalore, India.
	First ACM/IEEE-CS Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL 2001), Roanoke, Virginia.
2002	ICADL 2002, Singapore.
2003	ICADL 2003, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
2004	JCDL 2004, Tucson, Arizone.

Table 3.4:DL Time-Line (Sources: Hsinchun and Yilu, 2005)

In a digital library, information administrations can be given to the clients independent of their area either grounds arrange condition or from different places over web furnished login and secret word with the end clients. According to the administrations accessible in conventional libraries, enhanced administrations can be given which are as per the following:

- Access of CD-Rom based information recovery benefits in a system domain.
- Access to online public access index (OPAC) inside the grounds or over the web.
- Provision of online course benefits like reservation and inquiries.
- Online membership to diary.
- E-mail web get to.
- Access to online database for giving ordering and abstracting administrations.
- CAS and SDI benefits through email alarm or gathering informing.
- Online access to in house database through grounds LAN over web.
- Access to shared or Union list accessible at remote areas.
- Documentation conveyance at digital substance on request and numerous administrations according to the necessity of the clients.

Today, the necessities forced on DLs are altogether different from that early time. A novel thought of DLs additionally alluded to as "Information Commons" (Ioannidis 2005) has as of late risen whose satisfaction requires new innovations and new authoritative models. As indicated by the latest comprehension, the DLs without bounds will be made out of a few multi-sort and interactive media parts amassed in a boundless quantities of organizations. These for instance can blend content, discusses logical information and pictures got by preparing earth perception information or they can blend content tables of logical information and pictures, comments and recordings. These new information items will offer inventive and all the more intense intends to specialists for sharing and talking about the consequences of their work. In the new DLs client are buyers as well as makers of information. By expounding information assembled through the DL they can make new information protests that are distributed in the DL in this manner improving its substance. The new DL are subsequently required to offer administrations that help the writing of these new protests and the work processes that prompt their publication. In parallel with the above advancement of the part of DL frameworks, it is presently watched a substantial development in the interest for DLs. The clients' requests are more affordable and more unique DL advancement models.

They need to have the capacity to set up new DLs that serve their requirements for the length of their coordinated efforts in worthy time allotment and with a satisfactory cost.

There is likewise an activity supported by the Government of India to give a typical structure to all the digital libraries in India to exist together. Tuned in to the exponentially developing stockpiling and band widths, it is proposed by Prof. Raj Reddy to digitize, video and different games diversion and religious talks both live and accomplished. This will upgrade the utility of the DL and furthermore extend the meaning of library to end up genuinely a powerhouse of information. This will likewise help additionally in recording numerous setting conventions and confined information that in the Indian of a "Consortium for Compensating for Creating Contents"- the Four Cs. This plan tends to the likelihood of making a 21st century likeness public libraries, the PBS and the All India Radio to make substance for the Web.

3.5 Digitization of Public Libraries in West Bengal

Information technology has changed the cutting edge libraries when contrasted with the customary library proficient alone can't create digital library as not very many library experts will have all the ability required to set up a digital library. The exertion gathering's participation and coordination can prompt productive outcomes in creating digital libraries. Before starting the venture of setting up a digital library, the essential point that ought to be conceived as a main priority i.e. information is chosen based on quality ought to be available to each one and there is no limitation for clear client gatherings and capacity of information can be changed when required. The five laws of library science instituted by Dr. S. R. Ranganathan ought to be actualized in outline of digital library.

Why Need Digitization

Earlier the library work was done manually but the following factors have forced to adopt automation in the libraries.

Lack Of Space With Increasing Information:

There is seen enormous growth or information explosion of literature in each area, subject in number and size and resulted fragmentation of literature and increasing specialization in every field of knowledge. Due to this information explosion, the quantity, variety and complexity of information are being increased rapidly in every field. Computer application can solve this problem, as it is capable of storing huge bulk of information on tiny storage mediums, i.e., a CD-ROM can store the text of the complete set of Encyclopedia Britannica. Serials, abstracts, indexing periodicals etc. are already available on CD-ROM. Now a days, DVDs with 4.7 GB capacity and Blue Ray Discs with 120 GB capacity of storing data are coming in the market, but their use is yet to be started in library and information centres.

Increase In No. Of Users And Data:

Increasing the number of clientele of library and information centers and their specialized desires forces us to change the method of organizing information because traditional methods are going to become inadequate. The manual method has serious limitations and, facing problem to provide access to reader's information that is available in a wide variety of publications from so many sources. And this is possible through automation of library services.

Price Increase Of Printing And Shareable Material:

The rapidly enhancement price of information materials motivated the library and information centers to share their resources. They realize that the only way they could fulfill their client groups by effective cooperation between libraries, information centers and networks and the sharing of all type of resources.

Increase In Expenses Of Library:

With the increase in the members of the library, cost of information materials, services and growth of information or information explosion, the budget of the libraries is also raised. That is also allowing us to automate the library activities and to make maximum utilization of the library funds.

These facts create a great challenge for every type of library which is providing reading services to their users with greater information, while coping with the pace of technological change and ever-increasing budget pressure. Besides, the growth of electronic information over the decades and the democratization of the Internet have paved the way for the emergence of digital libraries. Digital libraries can be seen as an extension of the existing libraries with all the three basic functions, viz., collection, organization, and dissemination of digital information resources. They also need some system to be tackled efficiently. The use of software applications in Digital Libraries has become essential due to a number of reasons. The most visible factors among them are – growth of electronic resources, anytime anywhere access and resource sharing.

Benefits of Digitization

Digitization which is the utilization of computers in different exercises helps in dealing with the library's resources properly and effectively in the meantime sparing time, cash and labor. For instance, once the bibliographic subtle elements like creator, title, release, distributor, value, ISBN number, and so on are entered at the season of requesting, similar information can be utilized for accessioning, cataloging OPAC, and course. Other essential components related with digitization are speed, and exactness. It additionally encourages age of various reports for better basic leadership in the successful management of the library.

Accessibility of different factual and other utilization reports and execution reports may guarantee better gratefulness from library clients. For instance, merchant execution examination is conceivable and subject-wise or undertaking/division astute spending plan

can likewise be observed. By and large, the Library Automation might be said to be helpful to the supporters, staff also, the organizations.

Advantages for Patrons: The Library Automation offers numerous chances to enhance services to the library clients. Its advantages incorporate quicker access to resources through OPACs, remote access, access to online reference devices, and so forth.

Advantages for Staff: The Library Automation diminishes the need to do dreary occupations physically. It lessens the manual work associated with course, cataloging, acquisitions, and so on. Computerization enables the staff to take profit of online resources, and disconnected databases in giving reference services.

Advantages for Institution: The Library Automation or computerization not just forms positive notoriety of the library services yet it likewise builds access focuses for the clients.

West Bengal towards Digitization

Digitization of uncommon books under the plan of Govt. of India has been finished at State Central library and the work is on advance at Uttarpara Jaykrishna Public Library, North Bengal State Library and furthermore at two other locale libraries.

The digitization of in-house materials was begun in the National Library in 1999 and 3.2 million pages were digitized in to two stages: 1900-2000 and 2005-2006. These were for the most part in Bengali and English books distributed before 1900 and the 1335 composition Tutinamah. From April, 2010 a dynamic site, facilitated by NIC was connected in the before static site. An online public Access index is presently open through the (Web OPAC) in this website (www.nationallibrary.gov.in). A New server-stockpiling frameworks has been made operational, the neighborhood has been broadened. The web-OPAC presently contains around 8,50,000 reference indices records and it appears to have soaked in that electronic index. The insights incorporate a retro-changed over electronic index. The static piece of the site has been altogether altered and

redressed. In 2011, the National Library began buying in to the 10 megabit for every second web rented line from BSNL to give web association with clients and individuals from the staff. After the hole of more than five years, the third period of digitization most chose materials in library began in October, 2011.

Calcutta University Manuscript Resource Center approved by the National Mission for Manuscripts constituted by the Govt. of India has propelled a statewide program for making mindfulness among the different cross areas of the general public in close contact with the Directorate of Library Services. It additionally directs study of compositions lying in various public libraries. Protection work has been attempted at Uttarpara Jaykrishna Public Library, North Bengal State Library and in various locale and different parts of the state.

The State Central Library with help of Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation has gotten ready for digitization of libraries. The work has just been on advance. The State Central Library and the region libraries are on the principal target and in the following stage the plan will be stretched out to town and sub-divisional libraries.

The digital archive enables clients to seek through a wide assortment of book accumulations where one can likewise look a particular book from the pursuit alternative. West Bengal Public Library Network has taken up an initiative to make e-books out of all the uncommon books accessible in the state over a few libraries. Directed at helping academicians, specialists and understudies, the procedure of digitization will be finished with help from the Mass Education and Extension and Library Service Department of the state government.

CDAC, Kolkata has been working in the field of Digitization of uncommon books and reports including Retrieval System arrangement since 2005 and has effectively achieved digitization of around 50 Million pages from in excess of 1 lakh uncommon books of different libraries of Eastern and North-Eastern piece of India under the sponsorship of DeitY and MoC, Government of India.

Hon'ble Chief Minister of West Bengal Smt. Mamata Banerjee endowed CDAC, Kolkata to complete digitization venture entitled "Digitization of Rare Books with Retrieval System and Portal" for around 15 Million pages from roughly 60,000 uncommon books of West Bengal Secretariat Library, under the aegis of Home Department, Government of West Bengal.

The State Government has gotten ready for digitization of public libraries through the help of Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation. In the principal stage, the State Central Library and all District libraries have been automated. A wide region organize has been set up among the libraries. In the second stage, Town/Sub-divisional Libraries have been furnished with PCs. These libraries will likewise be associated.

A West Bengal Public Library Network has been presented with State Central Library and 26 District Libraries. The undertaking of Public Library Network is of three crease nature:

- a) Creation of Bibliographical database;
- b) Creation of digital repository of uncommon books;
- c) Community Information Service.

All these three parts are accessible in a solitary gateway, specifically, www.banglargranthagar.gov.in. For economical advancement of the plan a multi-year venture has gotten managerial simultaneousness of the Finance Department with a reserve of Rs. 1.97 crores in 2008-09 and Rs. 42.47 lakhs in 2011-12. A powerful board of trustees has been endowed for execution of the program.

West Bengal has a solid system of Public Library System involving 12 Government Libraries and 2479 Government Sponsored Libraries and furthermore 7 other Government Aided Libraries. Aside from this framework there are almost 2500 non Govt. /non-supported Libraries in West Bengal.

State Central Library is working at the zenith of the Library framework and another three levels are -

- District Libraries
- Town/Sub Division Libraries
- Rural/Primary Unit/Area Libraries

The Directorate of Library Services under the control of MEE and LS Department, is with the help of Raja Rammohun Roy Library Foundation, actualizing a modernized systems administration arrangement of the libraries in our State, remembering the need to take into account the requests of a changing society and to scatter data through electronic media with the goal of making public libraries an 'Information Center'. Underlined zones of this framework are three overlap.

- (i) Creation of library inventory.
- (ii) Digital document of uncommon books and Government publications
- (iii) Community Information Service

An entryway for the reason has been made for the sake of www.wbpublibnet.gov.in

Raja Rammohan Roy Library Foundation made in 1972 has been advancing exercises like Construction of Library Buildings, Storage and Display of Books, Mobile Library Services and Organizing of Workshops/Seminars on Library matters under the Matching Grant Scheme similarly supported by the State Govt. and Central Govt. In spite of the fact that the Scheme had an unobtrusive start, with the progression of time, the State Govt. in interview with the Foundation has upgraded its commitment to successfully meet the reserve prerequisites of the Govt. Supported Libraries. Amid 2007-08 and 2008-09 commitment from each side was Rs. 1.5 Crore. For Implementation of this Matching Grant Scheme of the RRRLF, there are two Committees:

- 1) West Bengal State Committee for Implementation of Raja Rammohan Roy Library Foundation Program;
- 2) Book Selection Committee.

West Bengal Public Library Network (WBPLN) is a digital repository or digital library of West Bengal, here anyone can search and read copyright free uncommon books which are under the guardianship of different libraries of West Bengal, India. This storehouse is started with the help of Mass Education Extension and Library Services Department, Government of West Bengal and Center for Development of Advanced Computing, under the Ministry of Information and Technology, Government of India. It has begun its excursion on twelfth August 2010. The point of this digital store is to give free support of scholastics, scientists, and understudies. It is a digital administration that gathers, saves, and circulates uncommon digital material.

3.6. Online Public Access Catalogue

An online public access catalog (regularly abridged as OPAC or essentially library catalog) is an online database of materials held by a library or gathering of libraries. Clients look through a library catalog basically to find books and other material accessible at a library. In basic dialect it is an electronic rendition of the card catalog. OPAC is the passage to library's accumulation.

An online public access catalog, otherwise called OPAC, is an online database of the considerable number of assets and materials held by a specific library. It is a card catalog, of sorts, that is accessed by means of PC or other electronic gadget.

Online public access catalogs could conceivably supplant the out-dated card catalog as a method for helping library guests find the assets they look for. Clients can look through the database electronically, which can give them a speedier and more intensive methods for finding vital data, assets, books, writing, or different materials.

One of the one of a kind parts of an online public access catalog is that it is easy to understand and accessible by all gatherings. That implies that anyone, paying little heed to their age, status, or even their level of information about PCs, can utilize the framework.

On the off chance that assistance is required in a pursuit, the framework itself is intended to offer that help by utilization of different prompts, proposals, encourage themes, FAQs, and even blunder messages when required. List items are shown in an organization that is anything but difficult to peruse and get it.

OPAC Appearance to Library

Online catalogs initially turned into a thing in the 1960s, however the main eminent and extensive scale catalogs were not created until the 1970s (particularly at Ohio State University in 1975 and Dallas Public Library in 1978).

OPACs for libraries showed up in the 1980s, Web-based OPACs started to develop in the late 1990s. Web OPACs are a characteristic movement in mechanical improvement and could be named to be a propelled second era OPAC. They are a progressed on conventional OPACs filling in as a door to the assets held by the specific library as well as to the property of other connected libraries and further to provincial, national and global assets. Sooner rather than later one can in the end imagine a full-content condition for Web OPACs as connections to outside sources turn out to be more typical, e.g. tables, distributors, corporate sources, diary titles, tables of substance lastly full content.

Remember this was all preceding across the board utilization of the Internet and any of the web crawlers we have accessible to us today. New frameworks and new advances have put an ongoing spotlight back on OPAC improvement with online catalogs currently being offered at most libraries the nation over.

Since the advancement of the initial two prominent online catalogs, both have been refreshed to use and incorporate ongoing innovations and ebb and flow look conventions. Today, numerous schools and colleges offer a type of online public access catalog to enable their understudies to access the materials housed in their libraries. Most public libraries have additionally built up their own particular renditions of an OPAC, making data promptly accessible to library guests.

OPAC Components and How to Use it

Computer and internet are the main necessity for using Web OPAC administration to whole PC in the library. This issue will be illuminated promptly in and they will give Web OPAC benefit in not so distant future. To utilize an OPAC, a library supporter or school/college understudy essentially needs to access the library interface online and after that snap into the OPAC. Most frameworks do require a record that will request login and secret word data.

Once signed in, an abundance of data about the library and its substance are made accessible through ventures in numerous structures. Quests should be possible by title, creator, date, or even subject. Results offer a connection for snappy electronic access or by make it obvious where everything is physically found.

Till today, we know about OPAC, yet now webOPAC, Social OPAC (SOPAC) and so forth are assuming indispensable part to recover required data and intuitive interface. Web OPAC enhancements are functions that are added to the existing web OPAC system. This most often entails additional product purchases from the automation vendor.

NIT, Durgapur Library; Central Library, Burdwan and other public libraries of West Bengal has been digitized their contents with the help of KOHA and other library softwares by implementing OPAC, Web-OPAC, MOPAC.

3.7 E-Books

A digital book is constructed both with respect to imitating the fundamental attributes of customary books in an electronic configuration, and in addition utilizing Internet technology to make an eBook simple and proficient to utilize. An eBook can appear as a solitary monograph or a multi volume set of books in a digital arrangement that takes into consideration seeing on different sorts of screens, gadgets, and PCs. The technology ought to permit hunting down particular information over an accumulation of books or potentially inside a book. An eBook ought to use the advantages of the Internet by giving the capacity to install sight and sound information, to connection to other electronic assets, and to cross reference information over various assets.

An eBook accumulation ought to be accessible whenever, anyplace by means of the Internet, requiring no gadget however a PC to access the substance. A perfect eBook ought to give substance of significant worth, the capacity to see online, the capacity to download to a PC or view disconnected, and the capacity to see on a handheld gadget or individual digital assistant. Users ought to be ensured protection for the substance they access and utilize and ought to have the capacity to total and alter things and substance paying little respect to design. Copy and print abilities for parts of the eBook ought to be allowed inside copyright and reasonable utilize laws. Copyright insurance must be guaranteed paying little mind to whether the substance is accessed by means of the Internet or through a downloadable pursuer that enables access to the book disconnected.

An overwhelming creating model depends on the conviction that an electronic book (eBook) = Content. In this way, an eBook can't be a gadget; nor would it be able to be a system of creation; nor would it be able to be characterized as one devoted wellspring of substance. An eBook IS simply the substance. It is the protected innovation of the creator and the copyright holders. In view of this introduce, the substance, even in an electronic world, ought to be accessible to share between and among clients, as substance created on paper has been and is right now utilized, while in consistence with reasonable utilize and copyright laws.

The perfect eBook show use the Internet and the electronic condition to give more proficient and powerful methods for collecting, sorting out and making content accessible, while holding the uprightness and pith of the conventional book industry and the utilization of substance that is effectively accessible and not limited by gadgets or specialized conditions.

The Internet has caused an upheaval in the book distributing industry with the rise of the electronic book (digital book). The benefits of eBooks for libraries are clear and include: simple access to content; on-request accessibility; can't be lost, stolen, or harmed; abilities to seek inside a book and over an accumulation of books; connections to different assets, including lexicons and thesauri; no physical space necessities; no gadget prerequisites for access to the substance; access to content utilizing standard Web programs; adaptable pursuit interfaces; effortlessly transported; and access from anyplace.

Open doors for distributors have likewise been made with the introduction of the eBook. E-books have been ascribed to the recovery of the insightful monograph. They likewise give a chance to distributors to keep up an aggressive position in the distributing and web based business markets. The development of the eBook has given distributors better approaches to serve clients by repurposing content and making "living books," which join content, sound, video, and different assets, for example, word references, thesauri, and so on.

West Bengal Public Library Network has list of the public libraries of west Bengal which has been digitized their content. More than 36000 books has been converted to e-book format and are available to public access. User can access then from library websites online using their user-id and password. D-Space at West Bengal public library network provides full information of e-books of libraries in West Bengal. User can search e-books of different authors, genres, subjects, era, communities and many other options.

The Bose Institute Library has a wide range of e-books on physical and biological science, which offers library services through its various Divisions. In 1937 Bose Institute public library started its first Systematic Accession Register and the name of the first favourable and propitious book was "Space, Time and Gravitation" by A.S. Eddington (1929). This library has total 38,841,2500 online e-books and online journals.

Central Library - The University of Burdwan has an amazing blended gathering of both print and electronic assets including books, e-books, diaries, reports, theories and different materials. It has sufficient framework to meet the prerequisites of the client. This library has 252285 books in total.

3.8 E-book Software

E-book Software incorporates the electronic program applications that enable the hardware to play out an arrangement of capacities, for example, following flow or cataloging (Cohn, 1998). An arrangement of summon is known as program, and an arrangement of program is known as software. The hardware works based on an arrangement of programs of software (Sharma, 1993). Fundamentally, software is the program that runs the computer to create the required outcomes. It is said that, "A computer without software is like a man without his mind, or a library with neither books nor curators". Along these lines, on rule, the determination of software precedes hardware. The creator underscored the software required for library housekeeping schedules and information recovery benefits in detail.

A Software bundle can have at least one computer programs to take care of a particular issue. A software dialect gives an uncommon sort of language structure and sentence structure to the programmer to empower him to give directions in a basic and reasonable way. Composing programs and creating software bundles includes extraordinary preparing, diligent work, time and cash. For creating in-house software to take care of complex issues these prerequisites end up serious and unmanageable. Because of these

restrictions, the honing administrators or information researchers are going for business software bundles rather than in-house created ones.

Software is the one of the fundamental segments of the computer framework. It is the fundamental part that makes the computer to control information. Software is an arrangement of programs that decide the preparing of the computer. Without software the computer is only a machine. Software is the principle interface between the machine and man. It is in charge of the handling either numerical or sensible information. Presently a wide range of softwares are accessible for various applications of the library.

To digitize library benefits productively and viably one needs an incorporated library digitization bundle. There are a few commercial library computerization bundles now accessible in the market. To offer the total fulfillment of clients and play out the library exercises and capacities, we should choose skillful and reasonable software which can meet out our prerequisites. Along these lines, administrators and information experts must remember some fundamental angles previously choice of library software. Hence, an assessment of fitting software bundles is particularly required for any scholarly or different libraries for ease of use, proficiency and cost adequacy.

Digitization of library and information services includes non-numeric information handling, content recovery, and control of series of characters. Information can be utilized for these reasons and for particular needs, unique needs software are likewise accessible in the market. The different classifications of such software and their highlights are: Basic software for information passage, approval, arranging, converging of records, and altering of information.

Word processing software to control content stockpiling, review, utilize and change; arrangement of edges, expansion and erasure of series of characters, control passages and so forth.

Database management systems (DBMS) are for creation and management of databases, record management systems, social database management systems (RDBMS), network and hierarchical DBMS. Content recovery bundles for capacity and recovery of non-numeric record (unthinkable and even designs). These are independent software, require least contribution of computer masters, records are autonomous of variable length for normal dialect, content, approach information by setting, upset document access, UIs which makes them straightforward and simple to utilize. These consolidate inquiry and ordering offices and other essential highlights.

3.9 Types of Softwares

Software can likewise be related with looking online recovery framework and Cd ROM databases. Major online systems have their own software for the most part written in order dialect, which give access to outside databases. They additionally give private or individual document office and allow altering of inquiry documents on micros. Library digitization software can be gathered into three general classes which are being utilized as a part of Nepal. They are as per the following:

- Open Source or Free Software – Koha, Dspace,
- Proprietary – Libsys

There are many other software are also available for digital library in all three categories, but we will only focus on the software selected for this study.

Open Source or Freeware

Open Source or Freeware is software that is discharged free of cost in twofold configuration yet just for a constrained time for testing after which clients are urged to buy the software. It is public area software which is generally acquired through shareware libraries. It is additionally called freeware software bundles and its licenses ordinarily disallow changes what's more, business redistribution. Free software is characterized as far as giving the client flexibility. This mirrors the objective of the free software development. Shareware is basically accessible complimentary in spite of the fact that

clients are probably going to be requested to pay a ostensible charge to the library to take care of the expenses of copying the software and the circles on which it is given. Moreover, the first journalists of the software typically charge enrolled clients for manuals. This sort of software can be utilized by anyone for noncommercial purposes.

Open Source Software (OSS) is an antonym for shut source and alludes to any computer software that is discharged free of cost and its licenses more often than not deny changes and business redistribution. Source code is accessible under a permit that licenses clients to study, change, and move forward the software and to redistribute it in altered or unmodified shape. A meaning of open source is "free appropriation and redistribution of software also, source code; licenses that permit dispersion of alterations and inferred works and non-victimization people, gatherings or fields of try" (OSI; www.opensource.org).

Open source software is computer software for which the intelligible source code is influenced accessible under a copyright to permit (or course of action for example, the public space) that meets the Open Source Definition. This grants clients to utilize, change, and enhance the software, and to redistribute it in changed or unmodified frame. Open source software is regularly created in a public, synergistic way. Open source software is the most unmistakable case of open source advancement and regularly contrasted with client produced content.

Open software or Freeware includes any software for which the author and/or publisher seek no remuneration whatsoever from the user for the full software package, i.e., freeware must be able to perform some useful function in and of itself, and not only in conjunction with a "scaled-up" version of the submitted software. Third-party "add on" and "plug ins" to commercial products such as Filmmaker or PhotoShop may still be considered freeware, as long as there is no charge for the use of the entire add-on or plugin.

Freeware may be either copyrighted or public domain. However, most "open source" titles are considered freeware, though products do not by any means have to be open source to be freeware that is binaries without source distribution are freeware as long as they meet the other criteria. Software that is free for private use but fee-based for commercial use may also be considered freeware. Several freeware are available for library automation, for example – Koha, DSpace, GNU Library Management System, ABCD and New Gen Lib etc.

KOHA

In 1999 when the Horowhenua Library Trust (HLT) in New Zealand, was searching for a Y2K consistent trade for their library framework, Katipo Communications proposed another framework, utilizing open source instruments to be discharged under the GPL. Koha (the Maori word for 'blessing' or 'gift') went inhabit HLT in January 2000, and was the world's first open source ILAP and is conveyed under GNU General Public License (GPL). Koha is the first Open Source Library Management System (LMS) with true enterprise class LMS functionalities including circulation, cataloging, acquisitions, serials, reserves, user management, branch relationships, etc. It is built using library standards and protocols to ensure interoperability with other systems and technologies, and provide a platform-independent solution (Sonker, 2001). Developed initially in New Zealand by Katipo Communications Limited, Koha was first deployed in Jan 2000 and has spread across the world since then. It is distributed under the General Public License (GPL). Most recent variant of the Koha will be Koha-3.0.2 (Linux stage just) and Koha 2.9.x (for Windows and different stages) (<http://koha.org>). It keeps running on various stage like Linux, MacOSx, FreeBSD, Solaris, and Windows. Initially created on the Linux OS, is composed in Perl. It keeps running on Apache web server. It has better help for multi-RDBMS like MySQL, PostgreSQL. It has OPAC interface in CSS with XHTML. It underpins all real library norms, for example, MARC record import/send out. Information can be traded utilizing Z39.50 server and SRU/W highlights. Koha-3.x backings Zebra full content web search tool as backend. Records are put away inside in a SGML-like organization and can be recovered in MARCXML, Dublin Core, MODS, RSS, Atom, RDF-DC, SRWDC, OAI-DC and Endnote norms. Its OPAC can be utilized

by reference apparatuses, for example, Zotero. Koha's default establishment bolsters running in Zebra which is arranged to bolster SRU questions on bibliographic and expert information. Zebra itself is equipped for identifying Z39.50 or HTTP and reacting with SRU if the approaching solicitation is HTTP (Anuradha, K.T. what's more, Sivakaminathan, 2009).

Koha is a full included open source Integrated Library System (ILS) for computerizing Library exchanges, grew at first in New Zealand by Katipo Communications Ltd. furthermore, first conveyed in January of 2000 for Horowhenua Library Trust, it is at present kept up by a group of software suppliers and library technology staff from around the world. (www.koha.org) Koha is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS). It bolsters worldwide measures including MARC bibliographic organization and Z39.50 Server. Web driven design (no extra software/utility is required at the customer side, access through the program Mozilla Firefox as it were). It gives huge flexibility to customization. Every one of the modules of LMS including Acquisition, Cataloging, Circulation, OPAC, Membership Management, System Administration, Serial Control, and so on are accessible. Online OPAC framework enables the public to look through the catalog in the library and at homes. The software is UNICODE consistent. The creation and recovery of Indic content based records is conceivable. Fare and import and also reinforcement or rebuilding offices are accessible in it. Koha keeps running on Linux, Unix, Windows and MacOS stage. Koha utilizes MySQL as backend RDBMS and Apache Web server which are additionally open source software (DELNET, 2008).

Features and Modules of KOHA

- Management Interfaces
- Database of Library users
- Overdue Notifications via E-mail
- Acquisition and Circulation
- OPAC
- Membership
- Accounts and reports

- A library catalogue front end/ OPAC
- A library system intranet
- A circulation tracking system
- An acquisition/budgeting system
- A simple web based interface for patrons and library staff
- The search interface is easily customizable
- Simple acquisition system for smaller libraries
- Able to catalogue websites as normal items
- Web based OPAC and circulation system
- Auto- remind notice and fines
- Barcode support
- Full MARC support

Software and Hardware Requirements

- Operating System: Linux or Windows
- Web Server: Apache
- Database: MySQL
- Software Language: Perl
- 1GB RAM, 80GB Hard Disc
- Pentium 4 or Core 2 Duo

DSpace

Dspace is a notable digital institutional repository that kept, stores, records, protects, and redistributes the scholarly yield of a college's exploration workforce in digital configurations. It oversees and conveys digital things, made up of digital documents and takes into consideration the creation, ordering, what's more, seeking of related metadata to find and recover the things. DSpace plan and created by Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Libraries and Hewlett-Packard (HP). DSpace was outlined as an open source application that foundations and associations could keep running with generally couple of resources.

It is to help the long haul safeguarding of the digital material put away in the archive. It is moreover intended to make accommodation simple. DSpace bolsters accommodation, management, and access of digital content.

Modules of DSpace

- Searching by communities, author, books, isbn etc.
- Automation of data migration
- Machine interfaces
- ORCID Integration
- Metadata on all DSpace Objects
- PDF Enhancement

Features of DSpace

- Free open source software.
- Completely customizable to fit user needs.
- Manage and preserve all format of digital content (PDF, Word, JPEG, MPEG, TIFF files).
- Apache SOLR based search for metadata and full text contents.
- UTF-8 Support.
- Interface available in 22 languages.
- Granular group based access control, allowing setting permissions down to the level of individual files.
- Optimized for Google Scholar indexing.

Proprietary/Commercial

Proprietary is a term for computer software with limitations on utilize, and private alteration, or with confinements on copying or distributing of altered or unmodified

renditions. These limitations are put on it by one of its proprietors. Correspondingly, shut source is a term for software whose permit does not meet the Open Source Definition.

In today's digital era, a lot of library digitization/management software are accessible in the market. A large number of them have been created by commercial associations, e.g., LibSys, Troodon and so forth and some by non-commercial or legislative associations, e.g., DRDO, INFLIBNET and so forth. (Dhiman, 2003). Maybe a couple of them are free however lion's share of them are valued, i.e., we need to obtain them.

Commercial Software are just the software utilized as a part of a commercial domain, or then again software built up that has "benefit as a principle point". Commercial software are the software being produced by a business, which means to profit from the utilization of the software. 'Commercial' and 'proprietary' are not a similar thing! Generally commercial software are proprietary, however there is sans commercial software, and there is noncommercial without non software. Dominant part of them are paid i.e., we need to pay cash to buy in them. Alice for Windows, LibSys, Libman and Troodon are a portion of the cases of commercial software.

LibSys

LibSys is incorporated library digitization software created for dealing with substantial gathering in the scholarly libraries. It is most extensive and completely incorporated, multi - client framework intended to keep running on super/Mini/Micro computers including PCs under UNIX, XENIX, and VMS condition. It is outlined and created by LibSys Enterprise, New Delhi. It bolsters for establishment of software and its smooth tasks at a site. It bolsters the whole library related exercises. It has seven essential modules like securing, cataloging, course and serial control, OPAC, Web OPAC, Article Indexing.

It was produced in COBOL dialect however now it has been changed over in to c++ dialect. It has a list age system and in this manner, does not require any isolate database software. It depends on three level engineering giving and autonomous front-UI, the exchanges processor including an intense bibliographic pursuit database chief/motor with

alternative to client Oracle,/SQL server as back-end RDBMS. LibSys, can be changed to work with other software, for example, prophet, Unify, Ingres, and so forth. It likewise underpins CD ROM, Networking (LAN, WAN) and multilingual utilize and is accessible in Client Server usage with web empowered highlights. Consequently can be accessed through an internet browser and accommodates networking of libraries.

With an open framework engineering (3-level) since its initiation and its constant progress from a host multi-client framework to Client-Server usage lastly a add up to electronic arrangement, makes Libsys a progressed multidimensional library framework. A ground-breaking and easy to use WebOPAC alongside Windows based OPAC, settles on it an exceptional decision for a Library framework.

Libsys handles Indian dialects/contents utilizing ISM Publisher and GIST (C-DAC, India). There is an extra 'Unicode' bolster in Libsys that encourages taking care of o f both International and Indian dialects/contents.

With regards to picking an appropriate stage for Libsys usage - there are numerous potential outcomes, for example, WINDOWS (NT/2000/XP), UNIX (different flavors) and LINUX, giving a vibe of open framework for expandability and cross movement in future. Other than its own proprietary database taking care of capacities, any favored industry standard RDBMS, for example, SQL Server, ORACLE, MySQL and so on can be utilized as a back-end.

For a modem library having Electronic Surveillance Gate based security framework introduced, the LSmart interface in Libsys bolsters different self registration counters, Book drops stations, and so forth in view of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) or some other propel technology.

As Libsys can deal with digital substance alongside different media documents and electronic resources, usage of a virtual library is an unmistakable probability and It is very handy and comfortable to work and the library staff can start to utilize it rapidly absent much computers slaughters. It guarantees high profitability on account of insignificant information passage prerequisites, greatest conceivable coordination of

capacities and ground-breaking inquiry and question offices. It has its own particular brought together bibliographic database in light of ANSIZ39.50 arrange. LIBSYS underpins all exercises identifying with securing, cataloging, flow and serials control and has an intense yet in the meantime easy to use OPAC interface(Libsys:Pamphlet,2006).

Modules of Libsys

- Acquisition
- Circulation
- Cataloging
- Serial Control
- Article Indexing
- Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)

Features of Libsys

- Client-Server model
 - a. Various Options for Server
 - b. Choice for Client
- Multi-lingual support for Indian and International languages/scripts
 - a. Unicode Support
 - b. ISM Publisher (C-DAC, India)
 - c. GIST (C-DAC, India)
- User-friendly Windows GUI
- Supports TCP/IP for Communication.
- Z39.50 compliant (Both search engine and LibSys Clients)
- Co-operative Cataloguing (Network Downloading)
- Web OPAC
- MARC Implementation
 - a. UNIMARC
 - b. MARC21 (USMARC + CANMARC)

- c. UKMARC
- d. CCF
- Import/Export of Data in MARC and non MARC
- Supports Barcode/ Smart card/ RFID for capturing of member ED and item ID
- Interface with Digital Video Camera (to capture member's photograph)
- In-built Barcode Printing
- Optional Back-End RDBMS (ORACLE or SQL Server or MYSQL) with ODBC connectivity.
- E-mail interface
- Support Electronic Resources
 - a. URL Multi-media files (TIFF, GIF, JPEG, Wave, Midi, etc.)
 - b. PDF file
 - c. Other file formats
- Optional Add-on features

3.10 Use of E-book Software in Public Libraries in West Bengal

Most of the public libraries has already been connected with West Bengal Public Library Network and has been digitized or digitizing their contents.

We have selected West Bengal Public Library Network for fetching the public library which are using any e-book library software from the selected softwares for this research. We have selected five main libraries of West Bengal - Central Library - The University of Burdwan, The Asiatic Society Library, The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library, Indian Statistical Institute Library and Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library.

Central Library - The University of Burdwan

The University of Burdwan was set up in 1960 and around the same time University Library was set up at 'Naachghar' in Mahatab Manjil (Rajbati), Burdwan with the accumulation of books for Humanities and Mathematics divisions. In 1961, books for

Physics and Chemistry offices were included the library. At show, there are eighteen Seminar Libraries in the particular divisions and eight Seminar Libraries are served from the Central Library.

A three storied building is presently utilized for the Central Library having an aggregate cover region of 37,351.04 Sqft. Add up to number of books in the library till now is 253986 (acquired - 191799 nos., DSA/DRS venture – 20389 nos., Gift – 31415 nos., Raj Collection – 10383) out of which 159300 books (remarkable title - 91984) as of now entered in the KOHA database. Barcoding of books is finished. Computerized issue and return and Web OPAC, MOPAC of library database (books and diaries) will be begun instantly utilizing Koha Open Source Library Management Software.

Central Library is an inside coordinated towards rendering the learning based information administration to each pursuer of any train of the scholastic network. Burdwan University Central Library began its model Digital Library utilizing DSpace software in 2007 for beginning testing. We have quite recently entered the database of every single accessible proposition into the digital library. We have gotten finances as of late from UGC to proceed with our task to serve the Nation.

Aim of the central library is as follows:

- Engaging the University's scholastic, research and learning network with profound aptitude, inventive services and extraordinary accumulations, fortified with delicate human touch.
- To wind up the model college library in the nation.
- To join the most recent technology and embrace easy to understand approach towards the regarded clients

The Asiatic Society Library

The Asiatic Society was conceived in the premises of the Supreme Court of Bengal in the year 1784 on fifteenth January it was moved to a recently built working at 1, Park Street, Kolkata-700016 in the year 1808. Increase of Research exercises, accumulation of original copies from different sources and investigation of Indian Culture and Civilization were the quick points. The Asiatic Society was enrolled in the year 1961 according to the Society's Act. It was an individuals' general public. The spearheading part of the individuals from the Society was noteworthy. In the year 1984 on 25th June the Asiatic Society was announced an Institute of National Importance by an Act of Parliament ensuing whereupon the Asiatic Society Act 1964, Regulations and By-Laws came into drive. The arrangements of the Act will have quick impact despite anything contained in the notice or directions or the West Bengal Societies Registration Act, 1961 or some other law for the present in drive.

The fundamental purposes of the Society are:

- to arrange, start and advance looks into in Humanities and Science in Asia,
- to set up, assemble, erect, develop, keep up and run look into Institutions, perusing rooms, galleries, amphitheaters and address lobbies,
- to sort out addresses, classes, symposia, exchanges, gatherings and honor of awards, prizes and grants in advancement of the targets.

This library has 1, 30, 786 books, 1, 09, 438 Journals and 48, 455 Microfiche in their collection. This collection has wide range of subjects like Anthropology, Archeology, Art & Architecture, Ayurveda and many more. The library has already make digital copy of 5500 books and 3, 12, 000 pages from their collection.

As a piece of Library Automation, information passages, cataloging in LIBSYS software is going ahead to take care of the demand from the clients all through the nation and abroad for online access to the profitable gathering of the library. Aside from the staff of the library, understudies of the Department of the Library and Information Science,

Calcutta University have been locked in intentionally to prepare worksheet of books, entering information in the LIBSYS bundle for full catalog and for planning database.

The library is using Libsys software for e-book and library management.

The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library

The Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science (IACS) is a general public enlisted under Act XXI of 1860 and the comparing State Act viz. the West Bengal State Registration Act 1961, with its central command at 2A and 2B, Raja S. C. Mallick Road, Calcutta - 700 032, West Bengal, India. It has a Governing Council with various individuals chose or selected and the Registrar as its Non-Member Secretary. The Council has the capacities, obligations and power as imagined in the Memorandum and Bye Laws and according to the arrangements of the applicable Act.

The Institute is controlled by the Governing Council, which is the summit arrangement making body. The Director is the CEO of the Institute and maintains the matter of the Association under the supervision of the Council. The Director is helped by the Departmental Heads of the Scientific Departments and Service Departments including Administration. The Administration is going by the Registrar of the Association who helps the Director in his capacity. Enlistment center, who is the in general responsible for the managerial working including Finance and Accounts, is the Drawing and Disbursing Officer of IACS and is additionally helped by the Deputy Registrar, Finance and Accounts Officer, Assistant Registrar and so on. The Registrar offers help services to all the Academic staff. All individuals from the staff including the Registrar and the Head of the Departments are under the regulatory control of the Director.

The library has a large collection of very old scientific journals of immense historical and archival values. The library has more than 81000 bound periodicals and books.

- Books, Standards and Reports (in usable condition): 20,000 (approx.)
- Journals and Serials (Current titles): 1305 (approx.)
- Journals and Serials (Back Volumes): 50,000 (approx.) (in usable condition)

- Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM, Thesis, Micro-fiche, Microfilm):
1,000 (approx.)

The IASC library is using Libsys Library Automation software and DSpace Open Source Software.

Indian Statistical Institute Library

The Central Library of Indian Statistical Institute (ISI) is situated at Kolkata with a system reaching out to different areas of the Institute. Over the years, the library has achieved the qualification of being one of the most extravagant libraries of the nation, especially in the field of Statistics and related controls. The Central Library at Kolkata has more than 2,00,000 volumes of books and diaries other than numerous official reports, reprints, maps, microfilms and microfiches. It gets around one thousand logical and specialized diaries yearly. The Library has gained information bases on CD-ROM and further computerization of the library offices is in advance. The library has built up a different gathering of books and diaries in Mathematics and Statistics known as Eastern Regional Center of NBHM accumulation, out of the gifts from the National Board of Higher Mathematics. The foundation offers a course prompting Associateship in Documentation and Information Science, led by the Documentation Research and Training Center of ISI Bangalore. The Center and the Library constitute the Library, Documentation and Information Sciences Division of ISI.

The Central Library has a very much characterized gathering improvement strategy and utilizations multi-delayed methodologies to create and enhance its accumulation. It buys distributed material all the time by experiencing an assortment of book determination apparatuses. Its gathering of institutional reports/papers is created fundamentally through systems administration at the nearby, territorial, national and worldwide levels. Alongside these stations, the library additionally gets important material as blessings from singular researchers/scientists and associations from time to time. The push branches of knowledge in the course of the most recent couple of years have been Mathematics, Statistics, Physics, Computer Science, Social Science, Sociology,

Statistical Quality Control and Operations Research, Economics and so on. The gathering is principally in the English dialect. Display accumulation comprises of:

- Books: 136000
- E-books: 200000 (counting on membership)
- Blessing and Exchange Documents: 30000
- Reports and Records: 25000+
- Current Journals: 2300
- Bound Volume: 80000+
- Album ROM: 800+
- Reprints: 32000 [Closed]
- General Reading (Circulating Library): 40000

Central library of ISI is using KOHA and DSpace for e-book management and library management.

Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library

The Library was set up in 1950 with a pitiful spending plan of a couple of thousand rupees and a liberal gift of books and periodicals from Profs M N Saha, P C Mohanty, P N Ghosh, N Das Gupta, A K Saha, S K Ghosh and others. Indian Science News Association, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science and the National Institutes of Science in India made blessings of periodicals.

From that point forward the Library has developed consistently in measure (now 12970 Sq.ft.) and assets. Its financial plan, just Rs 50,000 of every 1960, went up to Rs 2 lakhs in 1970 and 14 lakhs in the mid eighties. It remains at 5 Crore now.

The Library has Libsys 7 (with the Web OPAC) software introduced on a Linux stage to help get to the Library Databases utilizing any standard program. On-line access to diaries is accessible to the organization individuals as it were. Diary sharing office exists among a couple of Libraries in Kolkata. The Library offers its perusing room administration to the pariahs on suitable enlistment.

Library Name	Software Used
Central Library - The University of Burdwan	KOHA, DSpace
The Asiatic Society	Libsys
The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library	Libsys, DSpace
Indian Statistical Institute Library	KOHA, DSpace
Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library	Libsys 7

Table 3.10: Software used in Public Library

CHAPTER: 4

DATA INTERPRETATION
AND ANALYSIS

CHAPTER-4

DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

4.2 Data Interpretation and Analysis

4.3 Suggestion

4.1 Introduction

It manages the examination and elucidation of information gathered through questionnaire (given in appendix) conveyed to the Librarians of selected public libraries of West Bengal the data has been gathered.

Only Three software packages have been selected for this study and status of use of software is analyzed on five selected public libraries of West Bengal. They are as follows:

Softwares:

- DSPACE
- KOHA
- LIBSYS

Library:

- Central Library - The University of Burdwan (CLUB)
- The Asiatic Society Library (ASL)
- The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library (IACSL)
- Indian Statistical Institute Library (ISIL)
- Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library (SINPL)

The survey and questionnaire was done on the basis of above given criteria to achieve the objective of this study. Data interpretation and analysis is mainly based on the answers and responses collected from the librarians of these public libraries. Beside this data also gathered form library websites and West Bengal Public Library Network for a comparative statement generation.

4.2 Data Interpretation and Analysis

In this section analysis of the collected data is presented with the comparative statement and relative tables and figures are also included.

Total Resource Collection of Selected Libraries

One of the distributed questionnaires was to obtain the collection details of the selected public libraries of West Bengal. The questionnaires were conveyed to 50 librarians and professionals of different public libraries, only 32 out of 50 responds to questionnaire with answers.

Sr. No.	Library	Resources				Total	Percent
		Books	Journals	Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Micro-fiche)	Digital Content (E-books or E-journals)		
1.	CLUB	252285	29200	1187	159300	441972	38%
2.	ASL	130786	109438	48455	5500	294179	26%
3.	IACSL	20000	51305	1000	6000	78305	7%
4.	ISIL	136000	82300	800	20,000	239,100	21%
5.	SINPL	39100	51974	1217	4301	96592	8%
	Total	578171	324217	52659	195,101	1,150,148	100%
	Percent	50%	28%	5%	17%		100%

Table 4.1: Library Collection Details of Selected Libraries

The data interpreted above in table 4.1 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 4.1.

Figure: 4.1: Library Resources

The table and bar chart shows that most of the libraries have printed books materials in large quantity (50%) where as journals are fewer (28%), Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Micro-fiche) is 5% and Digital Content (E-books or E-journals) is 17%. The table also shows the quantity of resources present in different libraries. CLUB has 38% of total resources, ASL has 26%, IACSL has 7%, ISIL has 21% and SINPL 8% of total resources. Resources contain volume of books, journals, CDs/DVDs, ROM, Microfiche, E-books and E-journals.

Services chosen by Users of library

From the conveyed questionnaire, it was obtained that users from different libraries opted for the services like Web-OPAC, Circulation, Reservation, and Full Text Access which is presented in Table 4.2.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services				Total	Percent
		Web-OPAC	Circulation	Reservation	Full Text Access		
1.	CLUB	8	3	5	4	20	43%
2.	ASL	4	1	2	3	10	21%
3.	IACSL	1	0	0	3	4	9%
4.	ISIL	3	2	2	1	8	17%
5.	SINPL	2	0	1	2	5	11%
	Total	18	6	10	13	47	100%
	Percent	38%	13%	21%	28%		100%

Table 4.2: User Opted Services

The data interpreted above in table 4.2 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 4.2.

Figure: 4.2: Library Services

We can observe from the table 4.2 and figure 4.2 that 38% responding users chose Web-OPAC, 21% responding users chose reservation facility, 13% library professional chose Circulation and 28% librarians wants full text features service of the software used in public library.

Use of Software in Public Library

The response of questionnaire for use of software is given in below table 4.3.

Sl, No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		KOHA	Dspace	Libsys		
1.	CLUB	8	9	6	23	34%
2.	ASL	2	7	4	13	19%
3.	IACSL	2	8	3	13	19%
4.	ISIL	6	4	1	11	16%
5.	SINPL	2	5	1	8	12%
	Total	20	33	15	68	100%
	Percent	29%	49%	22%	100%	

Table 4.3: Use of Software

The data interpreted above in table 4.3 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 4.3.

Figure: 4.3: Use of Software

Above results from table 4.3 we can see that most of the persons wants to use DSpace digital repository (49%) in public libraries and 29% percent shows interest in KOHA. As both KOHA and DSpace are open source software most of the people wants to use them and Libsys is commercial/proprietary software so only 22% respondents shows interest in it.

Views on Different Modules of Software

Next questionnaire is about what modules are most useful. Below table 4.4 shows the responses regarding this.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services						Total	Percent
		ACQ	CAT/W-OPAC	CIR	SC	AI	Other		
1.	CLUB	7	9	8	7	11	4	46	35%
2.	ASL	3	8	6	5	3	3	25	19%
3.	IACSL	2	6	2	3	4	3	20	15%
4.	ISIL	5	7	3	1	8	1	25	19%
5.	SINPL	1	4	3	1	2	1	14	11%
	Total	18	34	22	17	28	12	130	100%
	Percent	14%	26%	17%	13%	22%	9%	100%	

Table 4.4: Useful Modules of Software

The data interpreted above in table 4.4 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 4.4.

Figure: 4.4: Useful Modules of Software

The respondents of five selected libraries answered the questionnaires for useful module of software that they want to use modules such as Acquisition, Cataloguing /OPAC, Circulation, Serial Control, Article Indexing and as in other option full text. 14% wants to use acquisition module, 26% wants to use cataloging / Web-OPAC module, 17% want to use circulation, 13% needs serial control, 22% wants article indexing and other (full text) want to use only 9%.

Difficulties Faced in use of Software

The questionnaire response about difficulties of using software is given in below table 4.5 and chart is also prepared for the same.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		No Technical Person	No Vendor	No admin Support		
1.	CLUB	4	9	5	18	31%
2.	ASL	2	6	3	11	19%
3.	IACSL	3	4	3	10	17%
4.	ISIL	4	4	5	13	22%
5.	SINPL	2	4	1	7	12%
	Total	15	27	17	59	100%
	Percent	25%	46%	29%	100%	

Table 4.5: Difficulties in use of Software

Figure: 4.5: Difficulties in use of Software

The above table shows that library respondents are facing with the problems in using software. 46% tells that no vendor is available for good support of the software. 25% are facing problem due to no technical person and 29% are at lack of no admin support.

4.3 Suggestion

The selected person for the questionnaires provides good information regarding the use of e-book library software in public libraries of West Bengal. The responses show that there is a need to make people more aware about the digitization and use of software in public libraries.

Some points of interest are as follows:

- More user friendly environment
- Awareness about use of software
- More information about the software should be given in library or on their websites.
- More books needs to be converted to e-book format.
- Staff assumes a fundamental part in the library. On the off chance that staffs are not proficient and very much inspired, it might hamper the library administrations. Hence, the library should overhaul the specialized ability of the current staff with fundamental preparing and execution of the reconsidered size of pay of the library staff.
- There is a need to run more awareness programs for users of the library to enhance the use of e-books.
- More public libraries needs to be digitized their content and start the use of e-book and e-book software.

CHAPTER: 5
FINDINGS AND
CONCLUSION

CHAPTER – 5

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Findings

5.2 Conclusion

5.1 Findings

It has been determined from this study that e-book softwares are being used by most of the public libraries of West Bengal. The most often used software are as follows:

- KOHA
- DSpace
- Libsys

Public library aims to freely provide any type of knowledge and information to the user in the possible easy manner. These software are comes in category of open-source and proprietary, which makes these software more reliable to be used in any public library.

KOHA in West Bengal Public Library

More than 10 public libraries in West Bengal are using KOHA. Many training programs and workshops are already running in these libraries for increasing awareness of KOHA and promote it to use by user. Also to motivate users and library staff to use e-books more frequently to replace print media.

Libraries Using KOHA are as follows:

- a) Bose Institute Library,
- b) S.N. Bose Library National Center For Basic Science Library,
- c) Bengal Library Association,
- d) British Council Libraries,
- e) The Belur Public Library
- f) Kuchiakol Basanta Library
- g) Vivekananda Granthagar And R R Town Hall
- h) The Dhakuria Public Library
- i) State Council of Education Research & Training
- j) Srerampore College, Theology Dept.

DSpace In West Bengal Public Library

DSpace is a digital repository for libraries. DSpace is providing facilities to public libraries in West Bengal are as follows:

- a) West Bengal Public Library Network
- b) Indian Association for the Cultivation of Sciences
- c) Indian Statistical Institute Kolkata
- d) National Library

Libsys in West Bengal Public Libraries

Following list shows the use of Libsys in public libraries in West Bengal.

- a) The Asiatic Society
- b) Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library (SINPL)

5.2 Conclusion

With the improvement of ICT, number of modern software are created and ideas like LibraryThing, Library2.0, Web2.0, Learning 2.0, Flash, Facebook and numerous more are coming up, which will be extremely helpful to fulfill the end clients as well as to make the library tasks quick, simple and straightforward. Library computerization is particularly required in any library. Curators must go for coordinated software for library digitization for their individual libraries. Since there is a solid need to give web based library and data bolster administrations to end clients by coordinated library software.

More finished, amid the visit to numerous public libraries of West Bengal, it has been determined that Librarians/data experts know about numerous proficient exercises identified with library administration - library software, library digitization, digital library software and their utilization and furthermore they are intrigued to digitize their imperative materials for safeguarding and remote get to. All are intrigued to fabricate digital library to get to everything at one put and 24*7. In any case, there is absence of IT

framework, in fact gifted experts, IT staff, and authoritative help. In this manner library experts are not intrigued to apply new innovation instantly.

The E-book software's has acquired the upset the every one of the fields of person and furthermore in the field of libraries/data focuses. E-book software's given the path for the free stream of data to the end clients. KOHA is one such software accessible for nothing; certainly it satisfies the prerequisite of any kind library house-keeping activities.

E-book software are ending up to an ever increasing extent easy to use through consolidating different highlights like simple and coordinated get to interface, looking and self - administration offices.

In any case, the choice of right e-book software is dependably a troublesome undertaking for library chiefs. Before utilizing any sort of software a prerequisite investigation ought to be done in the separate library, as the requirements are diverse levels.

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APPENDIX-1

APPENDIX-I

Questionnaires

Dear Librarians/Library Experts,

I am pleased to mention that I am writing my Thesis on “Study On Use Of E-Books Software In Public Libraries In West Bengal” for the partial fulfillment of my AIS Course Master Degree. The main objectives of this research are:

- a) To identify and use of different E-book software for Library management
- b) To identify the features and capabilities of different e-book software for Library Automation and why e-book software is existing opportunity for libraries?

I shall be grateful to you for your valuable information, views, and ideas on selected questionnaires including recommendation of e-book software for library automation.

Name of Researcher Student

College name, Kolkata, West Bengal.

1. Personal Data

- (a) Your Name(Opt.): Qualification:
.....
- (b) Designation:..... Sex(M/F):
.....
- (c) Address:.....

2. Institutional Information

- (a) Name:
- (b) Type of Library: Academic/Public/National/Private:
- (c) Year of Establishment:

(d) Library Budget (2011/2012 in Rs.):

3. Library Resources:

Categories	No of Items	Categories	No. of Items
Books		Journals	
Dissertation		Thesis/ Report	
CD-ROMs		E-Journals	
E-books		Manuscripts	
Micro-fiche		Other Digital Content	

a) What type of services users need from the digital public library?

1. Web-OPAC
2. Fast circulation
3. Book reservation
4. Remotely full text access

4. Details of Library Automation Software:

a) Which is the software you are using for library management and e-book handling?

1. KOHA
2. DSpace
3. Libsys

b) According to your views which of the module are good for public library?

1. Acquisition
2. Cataloguing /Web-OPAC
3. Circulation
4. Serial Control
5. Article Indexing
6. Other

5. Use of E-book

a) Do Librarian use eBooks alongside, or as a replacement for, print books?

1. Both
2. Replacement

6. Evaluation

a) What kind of problems do you face with the library software?

1. Lack of vendors's readability
2. Non availability of technical exports/software specialists?
3. Difficult to use
4. Lack of administrative support

7. If you have any further suggestion for the improvement, development and recommendation of e-book software for library automation, please mention briefly.

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PUBLICATIONS

Library Digitization and Use of E-Books Software in Public Library of West Bengal: A Study

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Abstract:

With the digitization of public libraries it turns out to be simple for everybody to get to any library from remote zone and get the important data. For digitization, printed books should be changed over to the electronic configuration by filtering them or making softcopy adaptation for them. To keep up these e-books and give advanced service to the clients of the library distinctive digital book and library administration software created. These software can store e-books over web in their database, keep up the collection completely, ordering them, keep record of the client activities, give look by writer, type, network, publication, distributing year, one after another in order, name and different strategies. These software reduces the loads of librarians and also make the task of finding and reading of books online for users. The focus of the study is on the use of different e-book library software like KOHA, Dspace and Libsys are three of many in public libraries of West Bengal. West Bengal has its name in the time of library development and advancement in India. Likewise the main completely advanced public national library of India is additionally situated in West Bengal. So this paper will give points of interest of the utilization of software in public libraries in West Bengal.

Key Words: digital library, public library, e-book software, library software, library digitization.

1. Introduction

This is the golden era of digitalization in every field. People can access any information regarding anything in the world by just using their mobile phones. Digital enhancement has make learning very easy for peoples. Nowadays there are many software and websites are available which are providing education online to their user by using mobile phones or computers.

So the technology has also changed the way of reading books. When everything is being digital then why we stick to the traditional method of studying and reading books which is very crucial nowadays when life is on the run. We cannot carry books with us everywhere, some boos are small and easy to carry but what about the books which are thousand pages long and hard bind. So here comes the technology which completely changes the way of reading books and make it very easy to carry books anywhere and read them anytime. This technology is named as E-BOOKS, which are soft copy version of the original hard bind physical books and to read these soft copy books the software used is called e-book reader.

Nowadays most of the libraries are also adopting the digitalization of traditional library system. They are also providing mobile access of their books to their users by storing their books' pdf version. They are making pdf version of each and every books, journals, print media, research papers, newspapers, thesis, national and international documents, maps etc. So that user can access them from anywhere.

A digital library is a sorted out gathering of assets of any kind, made open to a characterized network for reference or getting. The manual techniques for library administration has been supplanted by software driven computerized frameworks to control membership, acquires, book issues, new passages, participation and so forth. Since a digital library offers more stockpiling extension, substance can likewise be as e-books, e-magazines, sounds, and recordings, PPT or some other multi-media based data. Current

digital libraries are storehouses of mass substance, put away as digital items to make them promptly referable.

On characterizing a public library it might be perceived that, "an association set up, upheld and subsidized by the network, either through nearby, territorial or national government or through some other type of network association. It gives access to learning, data and works of the creative energy through a scope of assets and services and is similarly accessible to all individuals from the network, paying little mind to race, nationality, age, sexual orientation, religion, dialect, inability, financial and business status and instructive achievement".

An eBook accumulation ought to be accessible whenever, anyplace by means of the Internet, requiring no gadget however a PC to access the substance. A perfect eBook ought to give substance of significant worth, the capacity to see online, the capacity to download to a PC or view disconnected, and the capacity to see on a handheld gadget or individual digital assistant.

The Public Library made an incredible effect on human personality and human culture. With the headway of human advance, Books multiplied and through books millions got instructed. Instruction realized further changes. The principal change was the adjustment in the attitude. Humankind presently gained intensity of thinking and the estimation of soundness and they never again would submit to superstition and fanaticism.

Software is the one of the fundamental parts of the PC framework. It is the principle segment that makes the PC to control information. Software is an arrangement of projects that decide the preparing of the PC. Without software the PC is only a machine. Software is the primary interface between the machine and man. It is in charge of the handling either numerical or sensible information. Presently a wide horde of software is accessible for various utilizations of the library.

West Bengal Public Library Network begins its development by giving library office at the gateway progress of the customers, who needs extraordinary sorts of information. Any customer can approach the framework at whatever point with the help of a PC terminal. The State Central Library of West Bengal which is taken care of by the Directorate of Library Services, Department of Mass Education Extension and Library Services is the peak Library in the framework. The District Libraries are in like manner part of this electronic system.

Some of the imperative public libraries of Bengal are - State Central Library (Kolkata, Established in 1956), Kolkata Metropolitan Library (Kolkata, Established in 1980), Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library (Hooghly, Established in 1859), North Bengal State Library (Coochbehar, Established in 1870), Govt. Focal Library (Darjeeling, Established in 1961), District Library, Uttar Dinajpur (Uttar Dinajpur, Established in 2004) and others. The oldest district library of West Bengal is BURDWAN UDAYCHAND LIBRARY, which was established in 1954-55 in the heart of the town with two storied building.

This research study was attempted with the review of different online public libraries websites of West Bengal which are using any type of e-book software. Alice for Windows, Virtua, Techlib Plus, Libsys, Granthalay, Maitreyi, Sanjay, DELMS, Librarian, WYLYSYS, DELDOS, TLMS, Libsuite, DSpace, Greenstone, NewGenLib, EPrints, Atrium, Insignia Library System, Density Library Manager, Koha and many more software are used for library management and e-book reading. The accessible data through these software can be in any form like ppt, picture, e-journals, e-book, microfilm or microfiche, chapters of a book, thesis, patents, diaries or annual reports and many more. E-books Software have also affected libraries to experience all the all the more fascinating by empowering self-exchanging/downloading of

reports and customer correspondence on the web. E-books Software has also been instrumental in propelling resource sharing other than filling in as a contraption to bookkeepers to develop their IT capacities.

Library is a not-for-profit association confronting bunches of imperatives like budgetary abridgements, declined client base, deficiency of prepared labor, insufficient space, absence of expert energy and work culture and so forth. Every one of these prompts productive and powerful utilization of labor inside librarian's restrictions, consequently digital library initiatives would be the main reasonable answer for control the immense measure of bibliographic information rose out of publication postpone data blast and data flood. The present study in this way will be sober-mindedly huge for the accompanying reasons.

2. IDENTIFY, RESEARCH AND COLLECT IDEA

The historical backdrop of the advancement of the public library might be said to be as old as that of education in India. Research study for public benefit primarily based with the social phenomena. It studies the behavior of human being as a society and their response and attitude under different circumstances. The quality of any investigation and its timely completion primarily depends upon the size and quality of sample included in the study. Thus the role of sample in this research is quite significant.

For the gathering of information in social research, there are different systems or strategies are received. For the most part, the survey strategy, perception strategy, contextual analysis technique, basic occurrence procedure and Diffusion contemplate system and so on are the few for acquiring data.

Ratna Bandyopadhyay (2010) in her paper ““Come to your Library”: BLA Project for Promotion of Reading in West Bengal, India” talks about the activities of a couple of public libraries in the locale of Howrah, Kolkata also, South 24 Parganas for advancement of perusing and utilization of library.

Educationists, scholarly people and individuals in library cherishing mind began Calcutta Public Library in 1835 and the same was introduced on 21 March 1836 for the public. In 1944, Calcutta Public Library was moved to another and expansive building, raised to pay tribute to Lord Metcalf, the Governor General of India.

West Bengal has a very dense network of Public Library System which has connected total 2480 public libraries from different district and rural areas. 13 out of these are Government Public Libraries, number of Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries are 2460 and Govt. Aided Public Libraries are 7 which are currently maintained by voluntary organizations. The State Central Library is at the summit of the Public Library System in the West Bengal State. The state also has 7 District Libraries, 4 Town / Sub-divisional libraries and 1 library named Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library which has special status. The government sponsored libraries are further divided into 19 District Libraries, 232 Town / Sub-divisional Libraries and 2209 Primary Unit / Rural / Area publiclibraries.319 Community Library cum Information Centers (CLICs) were established in addition to those Gram Panchayats areas which don't comes under any category of Govt., Govt. Sponsored or Govt. Aided Public Library. 344 libraries were established before independence and 418 libraries were established after independence up to implementation of West Bengal Public Libraries Act, 1979, and 1711 libraries were established after independence up to till date amongst these 2480 Government, Govt. Sponsored and Govt. Aided Public Libraries. There are also some very age-old public libraries which has their important role till now.

The rise of digital libraries in 1990's and their staggering development in the ongoing years has opened up new skylines over a wide cluster of issues identified with outline, execution, advancement and assessment

of digital libraries. In spite of the fact that the term digital library has increased exceptionally ubiquity as of late, however it has a long history, back to more than 80 (Eighty) years.

The digital archive enables clients to seek through a wide assortment of book accumulations where one can likewise look a particular book from the pursuit alternative. West Bengal Public Library Network has taken up an initiative to make e-books out of all the uncommon books accessible in the state over a few libraries. Directed at helping academicians, specialists and understudies, the procedure of digitization will be finished with help from the Mass Education and Extension and Library Service Department of the state government.

Digitization work of uncommon books is under CDAC, Kolkata and reports including Retrieval System arrangement since 2005 and has effectively achieved digitization of around 50 Million pages from in excess of 1 lakh uncommon books of different libraries of Eastern and North-Eastern piece of India under the sponsorship of DeitY and MoC, Government of India.

A West Bengal Public Library Network has been presented with State Central Library and 26 District Libraries. The undertaking of Public Library Network is of three crease nature:

- a) Creation of Bibliographical database;
- b) Creation of digital repository of uncommon books;
- c) Community Information Service.

All these three parts are accessible in a solitary gateway, specifically, www.banglgranthagar.gov.in.

The present study incorporates just those public libraries of West Bengal which are computerized and have their collection accessible in digital book arrange for discovering the utilization of digital book software in these public libraries. This investigation endeavors to unfurl the present condition of utilization of existing E-book Software in West Bengal public libraries which have just been digitized and utilizing any sort of accessible digital book software for getting to the digital book collection of their books.

E-book software that are currently being used in the West Bengal public libraries are KOHA, DSPACE and LIBSYS. The public libraries which we takes into consideration for our research are The Central Library of University of Burdwan, The Asiatic Society Public Library, The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library, Indian Statistical Institute Library and Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library.

Koha is a full included open source Integrated Library System (ILS) for modernizing Library trades, developed at first in New Zealand by Katipo Communications Ltd. moreover, first passed on in January of 2000 for Horowhenua Library Trust, it is at exhibit kept up by a gathering of software providers and library innovation staff from around the globe. (www.koha.org) Koha is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS). It supports overall measures including MARC bibliographic association and Z39.50 Server. Web driven outline (no additional software/utility is required at the client side, access through the program Mozilla Firefox in a manner of speaking). It gives immense adaptability to customization.

Dspace is a prominent advanced institutional vault that kept, stores, records, ensures, and redistributes the insightful yield of a school's investigation workforce in computerized arrangements. It supervises and passes on computerized things, made up of advanced reports and thinks about the creation, requesting, additionally, looking for of related metadata to discover and recoup the things. DSpace design and made by Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Libraries and Hewlett-Packard (HP). DSpace was plot as

an open source application that establishments and affiliations could continue running with for the most part couple of assets.

It is to help the whole deal protecting of the advanced material set away in the document. It is in addition expected to make settlement basic. DSpace reinforces convenience, administration, and access of computerized content.

LibSys is fused library digitization software made for managing significant assembling in the insightful libraries. It is most broad and totally fused, multi customer system planned to continue running on super/Mini/Micro PCs including PCs under UNIX, XENIX, and VMS condition. It is sketched out and made by LibSys Enterprise, New Delhi. It reinforce for foundation of software and its smooth assignments at a site. It reinforces the entire library related activities. It has seven basic modules like anchoring, classifying, course and serial control, OPAC, Web OPAC, Article Indexing.

The greater part of the public libraries has just been associated with West Bengal Public Library Network and has been digitized or digitizing their substance. We have chosen West Bengal Public Library Network for getting the public library which is utilizing any digital book library software from the chose software for this examination.

The University of Burdwan has 253986 number of books in the library till now, which includes 191799 acquired books, 20389 DSA/DRS venture, 31415 Gifts and, 10383 special collection named Raj Collection. 159300 books have already been stored in database of software KOHA.

The Asiatic Society has 1, 30, 786 books, 1, 09, 438 Journals and 48, 455 Microfiche in their collection. This collection has extensive variety of subjects like Anthropology, Archeology, Art and Architecture, Ayurveda and some more. The library has as of now make advanced duplicate of 5500 books and 3, 12, 000 pages from their collection.

The Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science (IACS) has an expansive collection of extremely old logical diaries of colossal verifiable and authentic qualities. The library has in excess of 81000 bound periodicals and books.

The Library of Indian Statistical Institute (ISI) is one of the library which comes under the category of biggest libraries in West Bengal The collection of this library has crossed the number 2,00,000 This extensive collection has books, journals, various authority reports, maps, microfilms, reprints and microfiches. Consistently cycle wholes up approximately 1000 uncommon report dearies in this collection. The Library is now digitizing its substance by checking books and putting away them on CD-ROM and their databases.

In 1995, Profs M N Saha, P C Mohanty, P N Ghosh, N Das Gupta, A K Saha, S K Ghosh and other professionals and teachers collected their special edition of books at one place for public access and that place was named Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library, the cost of expenses was few thousands rupees at that time. After that period the library isadvancing itself in area, staff and collection of books. It has covered 12970 Sq.ft. area and its financial position is now 5 caroes which was just Rs 50,000 in 1960. Most of the public libraries has already been connected with West Bengal Public Library Network and has been digitized or digitizing their contents.We have selected West Bengal Public Library Network for fetching the public library which are using any e-book library software from the selected softwares for this research. We have selected five main libraries of West Bengal - Central Library - The University of Burdwan, The Asiatic Society Library, The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library, Indian Statistical Institute Library and Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library.

3. STUDIES AND FINDINGS

Computation of gathered information and its investigation is produced based on the appropriate responses and reactions got from the librarians of these public libraries. A portion of the information collection is additionally done from library websites and West Bengal Public Library Network for a relative statement generation. The survey (given in appendix) was passed on to the curators and experts of the chose public libraries for social event of fundamental information with clarification of each exploration point.

Total Resource Collection of Selected Libraries

32 reactions with clarification of the made inquiry were gathered from 50 experts and librarians, which was given the poll for this examination work. The principal inquire about point was to accumulate the data of the entire collection of public library.

Sr. No.	Library	Resources				Total	Percent
		Books	Journals	Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Micro-fiche)	Digital Content (E-books or E-journals)		
1.	CLUB	252285	29200	1187	159300	441972	38%
2.	ASL	130786	109438	48455	5500	294179	26%
3.	IACSL	20000	51305	1000	6000	78305	7%
4.	ISIL	136000	82300	800	20,000	239,100	21%
5.	SINPL	39100	51974	1217	4301	96592	8%
	Total	578171	324217	52659	195,101	1,150,148	100%
	Percent	50%	28%	5%	17%	100%	

Table 1: Library Collection Details of Selected Libraries

The data interpreted above in table 1 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 1

Figure: 1: Library Resources

The table and bar graph demonstrates that the majority of the libraries have printed books materials in vast amount (50 percent) whereas diaries are less (28%), Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Microfiche) is 5% and Digital Content (E-books or E-diaries) is 17%. The table likewise demonstrates the amount of assets exhibit in various libraries. CLUB has 38% of aggregate assets, ASL has 26%, IACSL has 7%, ISIL has 21% and SINPL 8% of aggregate assets. Assets contain volume of books, diaries, CDs/DVDs, ROM, Microfiche, E-books and E-diaries.

Services chosen by Users of library

The table 2 shows the user choice for different services of the selected library softwares. These services includes Web-OPAC, circulation, reservation, full text accessing and others.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services				Total	Percent
		Web-OPAC	Circulation	Reservation	Full Text Access		
1.	CLUB	8	3	5	4	20	43%
2.	ASL	4	1	2	3	10	21%
3.	IACSL	1	0	0	3	4	9%
4.	ISIL	3	2	2	1	8	17%
5.	SINPL	2	0	1	2	5	11%
	Total	18	6	10	13	47	100%
	Percent	38%	13%	21%	28%	100%	

Table 2: User Opted Services

The data interpreted above in table 2 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 2

Figure: 2: Library Services

Perception of the table 2 and figure 2 demonstrates that 38% reacting clients picked Web-OPAC, 21% reacting users picked reservation facility, 13% library proficient picked Circulation and 28% librarians needs full content highlights service of the software utilized as a part of public library.

Use of Software in Public Library

The response of questionnaire for use of software is given in below table 3

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		KOHA	Dspace	Libsys		
1.	CLUB	8	9	6	23	34%
2.	ASL	2	7	4	13	19%
3.	IACSL	2	8	3	13	19%
4.	ISIL	6	4	1	11	16%
5.	SINPL	2	5	1	8	12%
	Total	20	33	15	68	100%
	Percent	29%	49%	22%	100%	

Table 3: Use of Software

Figure: 3: Use of Software

Above outcomes from table 3 we can see that the vast majority of the people needs to utilize DSpace computerized archive (49%) in public libraries and 29% percent demonstrates enthusiasm for KOHA. As both KOHA and DSpace are open source software the majority of the general population needs to utilize them and Libsys is business/restrictive software so just 22% respondents indicates enthusiasm for it.

Views on Different Modules of Software

Next questionnaire is about what modules are most useful. Below table 4 shows the responses regarding this.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services						Total	Percent
		ACQ	CAT/W-OPAC	CIR	SC	AI	Other		
1.	CLUB	7	9	8	7	11	4	46	35%
2.	ASL	3	8	6	5	3	3	25	19%
3.	IACSL	2	6	2	3	4	3	20	15%
4.	ISIL	5	7	3	1	8	1	25	19%
5.	SINPL	1	4	3	1	2	1	14	11%
	Total	18	34	22	17	28	12	130	100%
	Percent	14%	26%	17%	13%	22%	9%	100%	

Table 4: Useful Modules of Software

The data interpreted above in table 4 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 4

Figure: 4: Useful Modules of Software

The respondents of five chose libraries addressed the polls for helpful module of software that they need to utilize modules, for example, Acquisition, Cataloging/OPAC, Circulation, Serial Control, Article Indexing and as in other choice full content. 14% needs to utilize securing module, 26% needs to utilize listing/Web-OPAC module, 17% need to utilize course, 13% requirements serial control, 22% needs article ordering and other (full content) need to utilize just 9%.

Difficulties Faced in use of Software

The questionnaire response about difficulties of using software is given in below table 5 and chart is also prepared for the same.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		No Technical Person	No Vendor	No admin Support		
1.	CLUB	4	9	5	18	31%
2.	ASL	2	6	3	11	19%
3.	IACSL	3	4	3	10	17%
4.	ISIL	4	4	5	13	22%
5.	SINPL	2	4	1	7	12%
	Total	15	27	17	59	100%
	Percent	25%	46%	29%		100%

Table 5: Difficulties in use of Software

Figure: 5: Difficulties in use of Software

The above table demonstrates that library respondents are looking with the issues in utilizing software. 46% tells that no merchant is accessible for good help of the software. 25% are confronting issue because of no specialized individual and 29% are at absence of no administrator bolster.

CONCLUSION

With the analysis of the result we determine most of the public libraries are using e-book software for the purpose of digitization. Some common e-book softwares that are used in public libraries of West Bengal are KOHA, DSpace and Libsys.

Main objective of the public libraries is to provide information and knowledge in any manner without any cost. KOHA, DSpace and Libsys comes under the open-source category which make them more reliable and efficient to be used in the public libraries of West Bengal..

KOHA in West Bengal Public Library

Most of the public libraries in West Bengal use KOHA as e-book software approximate more than 10 public libraries. To increase awareness between the users of public libraries to use KOHA as e-book software many training programs and workshops are already running to encourage users to use it. Users and library staffs are motivated to use e-book in place of printed media in the public library.

Libraries Using KOHA are as follows:

1. Bose Institute Library,
2. S.N. Bose Library National Center For Basic Science Library,
3. Bengal Library Association,
4. British Council Libraries,
5. The Belur Public Library
6. Kuchiakol Basanta Library
7. Vivekananda Granthagar And R R Town Hall
8. The Dhakuria Public Library
9. State Council of Education Research & Training
10. Srerampore College, Theology Dept.

DSpace In West Bengal Public Library

DSpace is a digital repository for libraries. DSpace is providing facilities to public libraries in West Bengal are as follows:

1. West Bengal Public Library Network
2. Indian Association for the Cultivation of Sciences
3. Indian Statistical Institute Kolkata

4. National Library

Libsys in West Bengal Public Libraries

Following list shows the use of Libsys in public libraries in West Bengal.

1. The Asiatic Society
2. Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library (SINPL)

The E-book software in public libraries of West Bengal has acquired a good place among the users of the library. These software has also enabled users to freely use the library at any time with remote access and access their needed information at any time from any public library in the form of e-book of their choice or print version of the book. DSpace, Libsys and KOHA are some of these digital library automation software which are free for any user and have all the necessary features that can provide the feel of library to the user.

Appendix

Questionnaires:

Dear Librarians/Library Experts,

I am pleased to mention that I am writing my research paper on “Study On Use Of E-Books Software In Public Library In West Bengal” for the partial fulfillment of my AIS Course Master Degree. The main objectives of this research are:

- a) To identify and use of different E-book software for Library management
- b) To identify the features and capabilities of different e-book software for Library Automation and why e-book software is existing opportunity for libraries?

I shall be grateful to you for your valuable information, views, and ideas on selected questionnaires including recommendation of e-book software for library automation.

Name of Researcher

Student

College name, Kolkata, West Bengal.

1. Personal Data

- (a) Your Name(Opt.): Qualification:
- (b) Designation:..... Sex(M/F):
- (c) Address:.....

2. Institutional Information

- (a) Name:
- (b) Type of Library: Academic/Public/National/Private:
- (c) Year of Establishment:
- (d) Library Budget (2011/2012 in Rs.):

3. Library Resources:

Categories	No of Items	Categories	No. of Items
Books		Journals	
Dissertation		Thesis/ Report	
CD-ROMs		E-Journals	
E-books		Manuscripts	
Micro-fiche		Other Digital Content	

a) What type of services users needs from the digital public library?

1. Web-OPAC
2. Fast circulation
3. Book reservation
4. Remotely full text access

4. Details of Library Automation Software:

a) Which is the software you are using for library management and e-book handling?

1. KOHA
2. DSpace
3. Libsys

b) According to your views which of the module are good for public library?

1. Acquisition
2. Cataloguing /Web-OPAC
3. Circulation
4. Serial Control
5. Article Indexing
6. Other

5. Use of E-book

a) Do Librarian use eBooks alongside, or as a replacement for, print books?

1. Both
2. Replacement

6. Evaluation

a) What kind of problems do you face with the library software?

1. Lack of vendors's readability
2. Non availability of technical exports/software specialists?
3. Difficult to use
4. Lack of administrative support

7. If you have any further suggestion for the improvement, development and recommendation of e-book software for library automation, please mention briefly.

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Study on Use of E-Books Software in Public Library in West Bengal

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Abstract

Public Libraries were established for collecting books of different categories, different time, authors, religion, community, history, and different subjects at one place with purpose of caring them and make them accessible to the public who is seeking information on a topic. Collecting and accessing of every type of informatics data at the same time is very strenuous for a person in perspective of an organization or financial statement. It is also not possible that a single library can provide all type of information and fulfill the demand of every type of user. So idea of digitization of libraries becomes helpful for handling this situation.

With the digitization of public libraries it becomes easy for everyone to access any library from remote area and get the relevant information. For digitization, printed books needs to be converted to the electronic format by scanning them or making softcopy version for them. To maintain these e-books and provide digital service to the users of the library different e-book and library management software developed. These software has the ability to store e-books over internet in their database, maintain the collection categorically, indexing them, keep record of the user activities, provide search by author, type, community, publication, publishing year, alphabetically, name and other methods. KOHA, Dspace and Libsys are three of many available e-book reading or library management software. This study focuses on the use of different e-book library software in public libraries of West Bengal. West Bengal has its name in the era of library growth and development in India. Also the first fully digital public national library of India is also located in West Bengal. So this paper will provide details of the use of software in public libraries in West Bengal.

Index Terms- digital library, public library, e-book software, library software, library digitization

Introduction

A Public Library is the finished result of man's battle against syndication and centralization of human information in the hands of few. The idea of democratization of learning came in the Nineteenth Century England as a result of long renaissance movement. From antiquated mud

tablet storage facility to the new age digital library this change was not straightforward and simple and took around 2500 years to cover the way. Library is one of only a handful couple of most established foundations that still survive. Amid days of yore libraries went about as support of human progress.

Digitization of library and data administrations includes non-numeric information preparing, content recovery, and control of series of characters. Data can be utilized for these reasons and for particular needs, unique reason software are likewise accessible in the market. The different classes of such software and their highlights are: Basic software for information section, approval, arranging, converging of documents, and altering of information. Word handling software to control content stockpiling, review, utilize and alter; arrangement of edges, expansion and cancellation of series of characters, control passages and so on.

Software can likewise be related with seeking on the web recovery framework and CD-ROM databases. Major online frameworks have their own particular software generally written in order dialect, which give access to outer databases. They likewise give private or individual document office and allow altering of pursuit records on micros.

West Bengal Public Library Network starts its balance by giving library office at the entryway advance of the clients, who needs different sorts of data. Any client can approach the system whenever with the assistance of a PC terminal. The State Central Library of West Bengal which is handled by the Directorate of Library Services, Department of Mass Education Extension and Library Services is the zenith Library in the system. The District Libraries are likewise part of this electronic system.

Some of the important public libraries of Bengal are - State Central Library (Kolkata, Established in 1956), Kolkata Metropolitan Library (Kolkata, Established in 1980), Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library (Hooghly, Established in 1859), North Bengal State Library (Coochbehar, Established in 1870), Govt. Central Library (Darjeeling, Established in 1961), District Library, Uttar Dinajpur (Uttar Dinajpur, Established in 2004) and others.

The study has been undertaken by studying the different websites of online public libraries of West Bengal which use one or the other e-books software. Some of these e-books software are: Alice for Windows, Virtua, Techlib Plus, Libsys, Granthalay, Maitreyi, Sanjay, DELMS, Librarian, WYLYSYS, DELDOS, TLMS, Libsuite, DSpace, Greenstone, NewGenLib, EPrints, Atrium, Insignia Library System, Density Library Manager, Koha and many more. New data made accessible through library locales utilizing e-books software include: Pictures, Theses, Research Papers, Book Chapters, Patents, Annual Reports, Videos/Audios, PPTs, Rare books, Institutional productions, Book Cart office, and so on. E-books Software have additionally influenced libraries to encounter all the more intriguing by encouraging self-transferring/downloading of reports and client communication on the web. E-books Software

have additionally been instrumental in advancing asset sharing other than filling in as an apparatus to librarians to build up their IT abilities.

IDENTIFY, RESEARCH AND COLLECT IDEA

West Bengal has a strong network of Public Library System comprising of total 2480 public libraries out of which 13 are Government Public Libraries, 2460 Govt. Sponsored Public Libraries and 7 Govt. Aided Public Libraries run by voluntary organizations. Out of total Govt. Libraries, State Central Library is at the apex of the Public Library System in the State. Besides, there are 7 District Libraries, 4 Town / Sub-divisional libraries and one library of special status namely Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library. In addition, there are 2460 Govt. Sponsored public libraries which include 19 District Libraries, 232 Town / Sub-divisional Libraries, 2209 Primary Unit / Rural / Area Libraries.

Amongst these 2480 Government, Govt. Sponsored and Govt. Aided Public Libraries, 344 libraries were established before independence, 418 libraries were established after independence up to implementation of West Bengal Public Libraries Act, 1979, and 1711 libraries were established after independence up to till date. Some libraries are age-old and bear their important role till date.

Sl. No.	Name of the Library	District	Year of Establishment
1	State Central Library	Kolkata	1956
2	Kolkata Metropolitan Library	Kolkata	1980
3	Uttarpara Joykrishna Public Library	Hooghly	1859
4	North Bengal State Library	Coochbehar	1870
5	Taki Govt. District Library	North 24-Parganas	1860
6	Deshbandhu Govt. District Library	Darjeeling	1955
7	District Library, Uttar Dinajpur	Uttar Dinajpur	2004
8	North 24-Parganas Govt. District Library	North 24-Parganas	1955
9	Govt. Central Library	Darjeeling	1961
10	Central Library	North 24-Parganas	1953
11	Sidhu-Kanhu Birsa Govt. Town Library	Purulia	1989
12	Digha Govt. Town Library	Purba Medinipur	1966

Table 1: Government Libraries in West Bengal

There are some other important libraries in West Bengal. These libraries are old and have some historical and important books in their collection. There are 21 libraries which are important because of their collection of books, journals, history notes etc. There are 79 oldest libraries in West Bengal which have rare books, manuscripts, old journals, oldest newspapers and maharaja's collection in their library.

Distribution of Century Old Libraries in West

Figure: 1: Distribution of Century Old Libraries in West Bengal

There are 7 such libraries, most of which are run by Non-Government Organizations. These libraries are assisted with government grants at par with Sub-divisional/ Town Libraries. Managing Committees of such libraries consists at least one Government officer as government nominee.

Of the three tier library system, namely, i) District, ii) Sub-divisional and iii) Primary Unit/ Rural/ Area Library – services mentioned in item numbers 1, 5, and 7 are generally rendered by the Rural/ Primary/ Area Libraries. Selected Rural/ Primary Unit/ Area Libraries render services under item number 2, 4, and 8. Services mentioned in item number 1 to 8, 10 and 11 are rendered by the District Libraries. The State Central library covers all the services of item numbers 1 to 13.

Sl.No.	Library Name	District	Year Of Establishment
1.	Ramkrishna Sarada Mission Ashram Library	Kolkata	1957
2.	Ramkrishna Mission Library	24Parganas (S)	1960
3.	Ramkrishna Mission Janashiksha Library, Belur Math	Howrah	1954
4.	Ramkrishna Mission Student Home Library, Belghoria	Kolkata	1963
5.	Krittibas Memorial Community Hall-cum-M use urn Library	Nadia	1960
6.	Rammohan Library and Free Reading Room	Kolkata	1904
7.	Bangiya Sahitya Parishad Library	Kolkata	1893

Table 2: Government Aided Libraries in West Bengal

The present study includes only those public libraries of West Bengal which are digital and have their collection available in e-book format for finding out the use of e-book software in these public libraries. This study tries to unfold the current state of use of existing E-book Software in

West Bengal public libraries which have already been digitized and using any type of available e-book software for accessing the e-book collection of their books.

E-book softwares that are used in the West Bengal library are DSPACE, KOHA and LIBSYS. We consider Central Library - The University of Burdwan, The Asiatic Society Library, The Indian Association for Cultivation of Science Library, Indian Statistical Institute Library and Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library for the research work on use of e-books software in public library in West Bengal.

Koha is a full included open source Integrated Library System (ILS) for computerizing Library exchanges, grew at first in New Zealand by Katipo Communications Ltd. furthermore, first conveyed in January of 2000 for Horowhenua Library Trust, it is at present kept up by a group of software suppliers and library technology staff from around the world. (www.koha.org) Koha is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS). It bolsters worldwide measures including MARC bibliographic organization and Z39.50 Server. Web driven design (no extra software/utility is required at the customer side, access through the program Mozilla Firefox as it were). It gives huge flexibility to customization.

Dspace is a notable digital institutional repository that kept, stores, records, protects, and redistributes the scholarly yield of a college's exploration workforce in digital configurations. It oversees and conveys digital things, made up of digital documents and takes into consideration the creation, ordering, what's more, seeking of related metadata to find and recover the things. DSpace plan and created by Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Libraries and Hewlett-Packard (HP). DSpace was outlined as an open source application that foundations and associations could keep running with generally couple of resources.

It is to help the long haul safeguarding of the digital material put away in the archive. It is moreover intended to make accommodation simple. DSpace bolsters accommodation, management, and access of digital content.

LibSys is incorporated library digitization software created for dealing with substantial gathering in the scholarly libraries. It is most extensive and completely incorporated, multi client framework intended to keep running on super/Mini/Micro computers including PCs under UNIX, XENIX, and VMS condition. It is outlined and created by LibSys Enterprise, New Delhi. It bolster for establishment of software and its smooth tasks at a site. It bolsters the whole library related exercises. It has seven essential modules like securing, cataloging, course and serial control, OPAC, Web OPAC, Article Indexing.

Most of the public libraries has already been connected with West Bengal Public Library Network and has been digitized or digitizing their contents. We have selected West Bengal Public Library Network for fetching the public library which is using any e-book library software from the selected softwares for this research.

The University of Burdwan has number of books in the library till now is 253986 (acquired - 191799 nos., DSA/DRS venture – 20389 nos., Gift – 31415 nos., Raj Collection – 10383) out of which 159300 books (remarkable title - 91984) as of now entered in the KOHA database. Barcoding of books is finished. Computerized issue and return and Web OPAC, MOPAC of library database (books and diaries) will be begun instantly utilizing Koha Open Source Library Management Software.

The Asiatic Society has 1, 30, 786 books, 1, 09, 438 Journals and 48, 455 Microfiche in their collection. This collection has wide range of subjects like Anthropology, Archeology, Art & Architecture, Ayurveda and many more. The library has already make digital copy of 5500 books and 3, 12, 000 pages from their collection.

The Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science (IACS) has a large collection of very old scientific journals of immense historical and archival values. The library has more than 81000 bound periodicals and books.

The Library of Indian Statistical Institute (ISI) is one of the library which comes under the c-category of largest libraries in West Bengal The collection of this library has crossed the number 2,00,000 This large collection has books, diaries, numerous official reports, maps, microfilms, reprints and microfiches. Every year cycle sums up approx 1000 special report dearies in this collection. The Library is already digitizing its content by scanning books and storing them on CD-ROM and their databases.

In 1995, Profs M N Saha, P C Mohanty, P N Ghosh, N Das Gupta, A K Saha, S K Ghosh and other professionals and teachers collected their special edition of books at one place for public access and that place was anmed Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library, the cost of expenses was few thousands rupees at that time. After that period the library is advancing itself in area, staff and collection of books. It has covered 12970 Sq.ft. area and its financial position is now 5 cores which was just Rs 50,000 in 1960.

STUDIES AND FINDINGS

Calculation of collected data and its analysis is developed on the basis of the answers and responses received from the librarians of these public libraries. Some of the data collection is also done from library websites and West Bengal Public Library Network for a comparative statement generation. The questionnaire (given in appendix) was conveyed to the librarians and professionals of the selected public libraries for gathering of necessary data with explanation of every research point.

Total Resource Collection of Selected Libraries 32 responses with explanation of the asked question were collected from 50 professionals and librarians, which was given the questionnaire

for this research work. The first research point was to gather the information of the complete collection of public library.

Sr. No.	Library	Resources				Total	Percent
		Books	Journals	Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Micro-fiche)	Digital Content (E-books or E-journals)		
1.	CLUB	252285	29200	1187	159300	441972	38%
2.	ASL	130786	109438	48455	5500	294179	26%
3.	IACSL	20000	51305	1000	6000	78305	7%
4.	ISIL	136000	82300	800	20,000	239,100	21%
5.	SINPL	39100	51974	1217	4301	96592	8%
	Total	578171	324217	52659	195,101	1,150,148	100%
	Percent	50%	28%	5%	17%	100%	

Table 3.1 Library Collection Details of Selected Libraries

The data interpreted above in table 3.1 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 2.1

Figure: 2.1: Library Resources

The table and bar chart shows that most of the libraries have printed books materials in large quantity (50%) whereas journals are fewer (28%), Other Materials (like CD/DVD-ROM/Micro-fiche) is 5% and Digital Content (E-books or E-journals) is 17%. The table also shows the quantity of resources present in different libraries. CLUB has 38% of total resources, ASL has 26%, IACSL has 7%, ISIL has 21% and SINPL 8% of total resources. Resources contain volume of books, journals, CDs/DVDs, ROM, Microfiche, E-books and E-journals.

Services chosen by Users of library

The table 4.2 shows the user choice for different services of the selected library soft wares. These services includes Web-OPAC, circulation, reservation, full text accessing and others.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services				Total	Percent
		Web-OPAC	Circulation	Reservation	Full Text Access		
1.	CLUB	8	3	5	4	20	43%
2.	ASL	4	1	2	3	10	21%
3.	IACSL	1	0	0	3	4	9%
4.	ISIL	3	2	2	1	8	17%
5.	SINPL	2	0	1	2	5	11%
	Total	18	6	10	13	47	100%
	Percent	38%	13%	21%	28%		

Table 3.2: User Opted Services

The data interpreted above in table 3.2 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 2.2

Figure:2.2: Library Services

Observation of the table 4.1 and figure 2.2 shows that 38% responding users chose Web-OPAC, 21% responding users chose reservation facility, 13% library professional chose Circulation and 28% librarians wants full text features service of the software used in public library.

Use of Software in Public Library

The response of questionnaire for use of software is given in below table 3.3

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		KOHA	DSpace	Libsys		
1.	CLUB	8	9	6	23	34%
2.	ASL	2	7	4	13	19%
3.	IACSL	2	8	3	13	19%

4.	ISIL	6	4	1	11	16%
5.	SINPL	2	5	1	8	12%
	Total	20	33	15	68	100%
	Percent	29%	49%	22%	100%	

Table 3.3: Use of Software

Figure: 2.3: Use of Software

Above results from table 4.3 we can see that most of the persons wants to use DSpace digital repository (49%) in public libraries and 29% percent shows interest in KOHA. As both KOHA and DSpace are open source software most of the people wants to use them and Libsys is commercial/proprietary software so only 22% respondents show interest in it.

Views on Different Modules of Software

Next questionnaire is about what modules are most useful. Below table 3.4 shows the responses regarding this.

Sl No.	Library	Chose Services						Total	Percent
		ACQ	CAT/W-OPAC	CIR	SC	AI	Other		
1.	CLUB	7	9	8	7	11	4	46	35%
2.	ASL	3	8	6	5	3	3	25	19%
3.	IACSL	2	6	2	3	4	3	20	15%
4.	ISIL	5	7	3	1	8	1	25	19%
5.	SINPL	1	4	3	1	2	1	14	11%
	Total	18	34	22	17	28	12	130	100%
	Percent	14%	26%	17%	13%	22%	9%	100%	

Table 3.4: Useful Modules of Software

The data interpreted above in table 3.4 has been depicted as bar diagram below in Figure 2.4

Figure: 2.4: Useful Modules of Software

The respondents of five selected libraries answered the questionnaires for useful module of software that they want to use modules such as Acquisition, Cataloguing /OPAC, Circulation, Serial Control, Article Indexing and as in other option full text. 14% wants to use acquisition module, 26% wants to use cataloging / Web-OPAC module, 17% want to use circulation, 13% needs serial control, 22% wants article indexing and other (full text) want to use only 9%.

Difficulties Faced in use of Software

The questionnaire response about difficulties of using software is given in below table 3.5 and chart is also prepared for the same.

Sr. No.	Library	Chose Services			Total	Percent
		No Technical Person	No Vendor	No admin Support		
1.	CLUB	4	9	5	18	31%
2.	ASL	2	6	3	11	19%
3.	IACSL	3	4	3	10	17%
4.	ISIL	4	4	5	13	22%
5.	SINPL	2	4	1	7	12%
	Total	15	27	17	59	100%
	Percent	25%	46%	29%		100%

Table 3.5: Difficulties in use of Software**Figure: 2.5: Difficulties in use of Software**

The above table shows that library respondents are facing with the problems in using software. 46% tells that no vendor is available for good support of the software. 25% are facing problem due to no technical person and 29% are at lack of no admin support.

CONCLUSION

It has been determined from this study that e-book softwares are being used by most of the public libraries of West Bengal. Commonly used e-book and library software in public library of West Bengal are:

- KOHA
- DSpace
- Libsys

Public library aims to freely provide any type of knowledge and information to the user in the possible easy manner. These software are comes in category of open-source and proprietary, which makes these software more reliable to be used in any public library.

KOHA in West Bengal Public Library

More than 10 public libraries in West Bengal are using KOHA. Many training programs and workshops are already running in these libraries for increasing awareness of KOHA and promote it to use by user. Also to motivate users and library staff to use e-books more frequently to replace print media.

Libraries Using KOHA are as follows:

1. Bose Institute Library,
2. S.N. Bose Library National Center For Basic Science Library,

3. Bengal Library Association,
4. British Council Libraries,
5. The Belur Public Library
6. Kuchiakol Basanta Library
7. Vivekananda Granthagar And R R Town Hall
8. The Dhakuria Public Library
9. State Council of Education Research & Training
10. Srerampore College, Theology Dept.

DSPACE in West Bengal Public Library

DSPACE is a digital repository for libraries. DSPACE is providing facilities to public libraries in West Bengal are as follows:

1. West Bengal Public Library Network
2. Indian Association for the Cultivation of Sciences
3. Indian Statistical Institute Kolkata
4. National Library

Libsys in West Bengal Public Libraries

Following list shows the use of Libsys in public libraries in West Bengal.

1. The Asiatic Society
2. Saha Institute of Nuclear Physics Library (SINPL)

The E-book software's has acquired the upset the every one of the fields of person and furthermore in the field of libraries/data focuses. E-book software's given the path for the free stream of data to the end clients. KOHA is one such software accessible for nothing; certainly it satisfies the prerequisite of any kind library house-keeping activities.

E-book software are ending up to an ever increasing extent easy to use through consolidating different highlights like simple and coordinated get to interface, looking and self-administration offices.

Appendix

Questionnaires

Dear Librarians/Library Experts,

I am pleased to mention that I am writing my research paper on “Study On Use Of E-Books Software in Public Library in West Bengal” for the partial fulfillment of my AIS Course Master Degree. The main objectives of this research are:

- a) To identify and use of different E-book software for Library management
- b) To identify the features and capabilities of different e-book software for Library Automation and why e-book software is existing opportunity for libraries?

I shall be grateful to you for your valuable information, views, and ideas on selected questionnaires including recommendation of e-book software for library automation.

Name of Researcher

Student

College name, Kolkata, West Bengal.

1. Personal Data

- (a) Your Name(Opt.): Qualification:
- (b) Designation:..... Sex(M/F):
- (c) Address:.....

2. Institutional Information

- (a) Name:
- (b) Type of Library: Academic/Public/National/Private:
- (c) Year of Establishment:
- (d) Library Budget (2011/2012 in Rs.):

3. Library Resources:

Categories	No of Items	Categories	No. of Items
Books		Journals	
Dissertation		Thesis/ Report	
CD-ROMs		E-Journals	
E-books		Manuscripts	
Micro-fiche		Other Digital Content	

a) What type of services users needs from the digital public library?

1. Web-OPAC
2. Fast circulation
3. Book reservation
4. Remotely full text access

4. Details of Library Automation Software:

- a) Which is the software you are using for library management and e-book handling?
1. KOHA
 2. DSpace

3. Libsys

b) According to your views which of the module are good for public library?

1. Acquisition
2. Cataloguing /Web-OPAC
3. Circulation
4. Serial Control
5. Article Indexing
6. Other

5. Use of E-book

a) Do Librarian use eBooks alongside, or as a replacement for, print books?

1. Both
2. Replacement

6. Evaluation

a) What kind of problems do you face with the library software?

1. Lack of vendors' readability
2. Non availability of technical exports/software specialists?
3. Difficult to use
4. Lack of administrative support

7. If you have any further suggestion for the improvement, development and recommendation of e-book software for library automation, please mention briefly.

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